

ENTRUST

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D2.2 ENTRUST Reference Architecture – Final Release

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Abstract	<p>Deliverable D2.2 is dedicated to the documentation of the final reference architecture of the ENTRUST framework, building upon the initial definition provided in D2.1, towards providing a complete Trust Assessment solution for ensuring the trustworthiness of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs) throughout their lifecycle. Thus, we first provide a description of the final architecture considering the advancements in all technical components and the interactions between them, and we provide a complete action workflow of the ENTRUST framework throughout its three core operational phases, i.e., Manufacturing, Pre-deployment, and Runtime. Then, for each technical component, we provide detailed information flows, focusing on the interactions between components and their positioning within the ENTRUST. Next, we provide a refined list of Framework, Security, and Operational requirements of ENTRUST, as well as a final list of KPIs that will guide the evaluation activities, and their mapping with the requirements they evaluate. We also define the Most Valuable Product (MVP) of ENTRUST, including a set of "must-have" and "should-have" requirements. We conclude with a comprehensive construction of the threat landscape of ENTRUST following a top-to-bottom methodology, starting from a generic list of most prominent threats and mapping these threats with the practical, real-world scenarios identified by the use case demonstrators.</p>		
Keywords	Reference architecture, Formal verification, Risk Assessment, Software Verification Threat Modelling, Tracer, Most Valuable Product, Requirements, Threat Landscape		

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PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive, confidential to ENTRUST project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

DMP: Data Management Plan

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Term	Description
AAA	Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting
ABAC	Attribute-based Access Control
ABE	Attribute-based Encryption
ABS	Attribute-based Signatures
ACL	Access Control List
AK	Attestation Key
AOO	Actions on Objectives
APT	Advanced Persistent Threat
ATL	Actual Level of Trust
ATL	Actual Level of Trust
ATT&CK	Adversarial Tactics, techniques & Common Knowledge
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
C2	Command and Control
CA	Certification Authority
CEGAR	Counterexample-Guided Abstraction Refinement
CFA	Control-Flow Attestation
CIV	Code Integrity Validation
CMD	Connected Medical Device
CPSs	Cyber-Physical Systems
CVE	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
DDoS	Distributed Denial-of-Service attacks
DDRV	Distributed and Decentralized Runtime Verification
DFG	Data Flow Diagram
DID	Domain Identifier
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DoS	Denial of Service
DT	Digital Twin
EMTs	Emergency Medical Technicians
ENISA	European Network and Information Security Agency
FES	Feel Emotion Sensor
FL	Federated Learning
FV	Formal Verification
FW	Firmware
HDOs	Healthcare Delivery Organizations
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
HRV	Hardware-supported Runtime Verification
ICT	Information and Communications Technology

IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IoC	Indicator of Compromise
IoT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LTL	Linear Temporal Logic
MD	Medical Device
MDR	Medical Devices Regulation
MDSW	Medical Device Software
mHealth	Mobile health
MISP	Malware Information Sharing Platform
MITM	Man-In-The-Middle
ML	Machine Learning
MUD	Manufacturer Usage Descriptions
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
OSN	Online Social Networks
PACS	Picture Archiving and Communication System
PHG	Tellu Personal Health Gateway
PMS	Patient Monitoring Systems
PUF	Physical Unclonable Function
QMS	Quality Management System
QoS	Quality of Service
RA	Risk Assessment
ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit
RoT	Root-of-Trust
RPMS	Remote Patient Monitoring Systems
RTL	Required Level of Trustworthiness
SA	Static Analysis
SBOM	Software Bill of Material
SDL	Secure Development Lifecycle
SL	Subjective Logic
SMT	Satisfiability Modulo Theories
SoS	System of Systems
SPLC	Secure Product Life Cycle
SSI	Self-Sovereign Identity
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
STRIDE	Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Denial of Service and Elevation of Privilege
SUT	System Under Test
SW	Software

SWaP	Size, Weight, and Power
TAR	Trust Assessment Request
TARA	Threat Agent Risk Assessment
TC	Trusted Component
TDE	Trust Decision Engine
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TI	Threat Intelligence
TLEE	Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine
TM	Threat Modelling
TMM	Trust Model Manager
TOE	Target of Evaluation
TSM	Trust Sources Manager
TTP	Tactics, Techniques and Procedures
UID	Unique Initial Identification
UML	Unified Modelling Language
VC	Verifiable Credential
VP	Verifiable Presentation
YANG	Yet Another Next Generation

Executive Summary

In contemporary medical ecosystems, such as hospitals and Healthcare Delivery Organizations (HDOs), there is a shift towards large-scale infrastructures consisting of multiple heterogeneous **Connected Medical Devices (CMDs)**, subject to different trustworthiness, security, and privacy requirements, originating from different manufacturers, and with varying computational capabilities. These may be categorized into (i) **low-end devices** with limited computational capabilities, such as sensors for the collection of medical data (EKG, sweat, blood pressure, etc.), and (ii) **high-end devices** with the capability for the execution of more computationally intensive operations, such as gateway devices responsible for gathering the aforementioned sensor data and forwarding it to the backend infrastructure of the hospital or HDO for medical diagnosis purposes and further manipulation. It follows that, in such infrastructures, the use of such diverse types of devices, as well as the interconnectivity between them, leads to **a widely expanded threat landscape, which may significantly affect the capability of such organizations to provide healthcare services in a trustworthy manner.**

In this regard, the core offering of ENTRUST is a complete **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)**, with the capability to evaluate dynamically during runtime the trustworthiness level of CMDs through the calculation of their **Actual Trust Level (ATL)**, and comparing it with its **Required Trust Level (RTL)** based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities and the available mitigation actions. The ENTRUST framework also offers the capability for the identification of the appropriate countermeasures in order to address those threats and vulnerabilities, whether they are known in advance (e.g., provided by the Manufacturer or Domain Administrator or available in threat/vulnerability databases) or they have been identified by the ENTRUST security enablers during runtime, thus ensuring the trustworthiness of not only each individual CMD, but of the system infrastructure as a whole.

The **TAF** of ENTRUST is supported by a wide variety of processes and components, which have been analyzed in detail in D3.2 [6]. For instance, the **Formal Verification** component which verifies the correctness of the security processes of ENTRUST based on the identified requirements, the **Threat Modeling** component that utilizes Large Language Model (LLM)-based methods for formulating a unified threat landscape of a device, and the **Software Verification** component for verifying the correctness of the software processes running on the CMDs. Based on these, the **Risk Assessment** component formulates the risk graph for the device based on the domain infrastructure and calculates the RTL of the device, against which the ATL will be compared. The secure lifecycle management of CMDs is supported by a wide variety of **crypto structures and primitives** (analyzed in D4.2 [7]), leveraging the **ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base (TCB)**, which is instantiated via OP-TEE in high-end devices and through a **Physical Unclonable Function (PUF)** in low-end devices. The **ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure** (analyzed in D5.1 [8]) aims to ensure the auditability of the actions related to trust assessment, such as through the issuance of **Conformity Certificates (CCs)**, the storage of attestation outcomes and raw traces, and the sharing of identified threat information on a **Threat Intelligence Database**.

Thus, D2.2 provides a final update of the reference architecture, consolidating all aforementioned components and enablers into a unified framework with a clearly defined and structured action workflow. This builds upon the architecture that was initially defined in D2.1 [5], which has evolved based on the

progress of the development of the individual technical components of ENTRUST, as well as feedback received from the use case partners with regard to the needs of medical domain infrastructures. Thus, the present deliverable functions as a reference document regarding the entire action workflow of the ENTRUST framework, which includes all the latest updates which were documented in the aforementioned technical deliverables. This will also guide the evaluation activities of ENTRUST, which will be performed as part of WP6.

Recall that the initial set of technical and functional requirements of the ENTRUST framework has been defined in D2.1 [5], split into the following overarching categories: (i) **Framework Requirements**, (ii) **Security Requirements**, and (iii) **Operational Requirements**. Here, we present an updated and refined list of those requirements, including detailed descriptions, and the identification of the core components or security enablers of ENTRUST that can be used in order to fulfill those requirements. In addition, D2.1 provided an initial set of quantitative **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** per use case, based on the specific needs and requirements of the corresponding medical organizations. Here, we provide an expanded list of qualitative and quantitative KPIs per use case, including concrete numerical values for each quantitative KPI. These will guide the evaluation activities documented in D6.1, and will provide values against which the actual performance of the ENTRUST framework will be compared.

In addition, D2.1 included an analysis of the threat landscape targeting each medical domain application based on the feedback from all use case demonstrators. In this deliverable, we provide a comprehensive threat landscape per use case, including detailed information for each threat, such as application scenarios, types of threat actors, affected assets, severity of the threat, and exploited vulnerabilities. We also provide detailed information on how the offerings of the ENTRUST framework are able to address those threats, thus ensuring the secure and uninterrupted provision of healthcare services in a wide range of medical application domains.

Overall, deliverable D2.2 serves as the final reference for the ENTRUST project architecture initially defined in deliverable D2.1, with a comprehensive overview of the design and its possible implementation. It includes technical details on methodologies, components, requirements, validation activities and real-life scenarios through four demonstration use cases of the ENTRUST solution.

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¹Source: MDCG 2019-16, Annex II – Examples of cybersecurity incidents/serious incidents (https://health.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-01/md_cybersecurity_en.pdf)

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Scope and Purpose

Modern medical domain infrastructures, such as hospitals and Healthcare Delivery Organizations (HDOs), are increasingly adopting the use of multiple heterogeneous devices related to various aspects of healthcare service provision, such as **collection of medical data from patients**, **continuous monitoring of patient health status**, and **use of such data for medical diagnosis purposes**, which may either be performed on-site or remotely. Such devices can be categorized into **high-end devices** (devices with high computational capabilities, such as gateways) and **low-end devices** (devices with limited computational capabilities, such as medical sensors). These devices are not only subject to various device-specific requirements, but are also deployed as part of complex, large-scale medical infrastructures, thus significantly increasing the threat landscape with domain-specific requirements.

From all the above, it follows that there is a need for a holistic approach towards the trustworthy provision of healthcare services, while also adhering to the relevant regulations that have been set forth in response to these advancements in the domain of medical device security. For instance, these include the **EU Regulation 2017/745** [2] on medical devices, and the **EU Regulation 2017/746** [3] on in vitro diagnostic medical devices. Thus, ENTRUST provides a complete solution for the continuous trust assessment of **Connected Medical Devices (CMDs)**, as well as the medical infrastructure as a whole, centered around a **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)** (described in D3.2 [6]) that is able to calculate the **Actual Trust Level (ATL)** of the CMD and evaluate it against its **Required Trust Level (RTL)**. This framework is applicable throughout the operational lifecycle of the device, and its operation is split into three core phases: the **Manufacturing (Design) Phase**, the **Pre-deployment Phase**, and the **Runtime Phase**. This framework also provides devices with the capability to **verifiably prove that they are in a correct configuration and operational state during runtime**, through a set of security enablers (described in D4.2 [7]) based on the **ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base (TCB)**, instantiated with a **Trusted Execution Environment (TEE)** in high-end devices and a **Physical Unclonable Function (PUF)** in low-end devices. In addition, the **certifiability and auditability** of the outcomes of the implemented security enablers is achieved through the use of an **ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure**, as detailed in D5.1 [8]. Thus, the ENTRUST solution achieves the appropriate balance between **security**, **safety**, and **performance**, considering the resource-constrained nature of the examined medical devices, and without limiting their applicability and normal operational state.

In D2.1 [5], we provided an initial version of the ENTRUST reference architecture, as well as an overview of all the technical components and security processes and their positioning within the overall action workflow. We had also provided an initial description of the requirements that need to be fulfilled by the ENTRUST framework, following a methodology based on the **extraction of all relevant domain**

requirements from all current standards and regulations, as well as the alignment of these requirements with those identified for various medical application domains, leveraging the feedback received from the use case demonstrators. This analysis led to a refined list of requirements, categorized into **Framework Specifications, Security Requirements, Operational Requirements, and Legal/Ethical Requirements**. Based on the contributions of the use case demonstrators, we had also identified an initial **threat landscape** targeting each medical application domain, as well as a list of **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** that can be used in order to evaluate the effectiveness and performance of the ENTRUST framework against the identified threat landscape.

In this deliverable, we expand upon all the aforementioned aspects, and we provide a detailed, definitive reference document regarding the overall ENTRUST architecture, as well as its applicability in various practical, real-life medical scenarios, thus demonstrating its ability to enable the provision of trustworthy medical services in a wide range of medical organizations. Specifically, we provide a comprehensive description of the **final version of the ENTRUST reference architecture**, consolidating all the latest versions of the technical artefacts detailed in all aforementioned technical deliverables, and dealing their positioning within the overall ENTRUST architecture. We also provide individual **sequence diagrams for each technical component, describing their internal operations carried out as part of the ENTRUST framework**. We also provide a **refined list of requirements** building upon the aforementioned ones, as well as a detailed **threat landscape** for all use case demonstrators, including information on the **countermeasures offered by ENTRUST for addressing these threats**, as well as **concrete quantitative and qualitative KPIs** for evaluating the effectiveness and performance of ENTRUST against these threats, which will provide the evaluation activities to be documented as part of D6.1.

The document starts with **Chapter 2**, where we introduce the final version of the ENTRUST reference architecture, split into its three core phases, highlighting the positioning and all relevant operations of the ENTRUST technical artefacts within the overall framework. In **Chapter 3**, we focus on each component within the ENTRUST framework, providing design and implementation details, This section also includes updated details of workflows, giving a clearer picture of the actions and interactions that serve towards the core target of ENTRUST towards ensuring the trustworthiness of CMDs and medical infrastructures. **Chapter 4** revisits the essential requirements that the ENTRUST framework needs, covering technical, security, and operational aspects, as well as KPIs. We also define the ENTRUST Minimum Viable Product (MVP) and outline which requirements that apply to each specific use case. **Chapter 5** presents a comprehensive list of threats and vulnerabilities that could compromise the confidentiality and integrity of CMDs of each use case, along with a corresponding list of ENTRUST functionalities that can help counter these threats and possible countermeasures. Finally, **Chapter 6** concludes with a summary of the key points and overall results of the deliverable.

1.2 Relation to Other WPs and Deliverables

Figure 1.1 depicts the relationships of this deliverable with other Work Packages (WPs), as well as other tasks in the same WP(2). As aforementioned, the main purpose of this deliverable is to expand upon the initial reference architecture defined in the previous version of this deliverable, D2.1 [5], and document the final version of the reference architecture of ENTRUST, considering all updates in the core technical artefacts of ENTRUST. Thus, this deliverable receives input from the technical deliverables where these are documented, namely D3.2 [6] for artefacts supporting the trust assessment process, D4.2 [7] for cryptographic enablers and security processes, and D5.1 [8] for processes centered around the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure.

In addition, D2.2 expands upon the definition of the requirements which were documented in D2.1, and

provides a refined, comprehensive list of requirements that need to be fulfilled by the ENTRUST framework. In addition, it expands upon the threat model defined in D2.1 for each use case demonstrator, including information on how the core offerings of ENTRUST can lead to the mitigation of these threats. In addition, D2.2 provides a refined and expanded list of KPIs for each use case demonstrator, which will guide the experimental and evaluation activities to be carried out as part of WP6 and are documented in D6.1, where their fulfilment will also be evaluated.

Figure 1.1: Relation of D2.2 to other ENTRUST WPs and Deliverables

1.3 Deliverable Structure

This deliverable is structured as follows:

Chapter 1: Introduction

Introduces the document’s purpose, scope, and structure.

Chapter 2: ENTRUST Final Architecture Overview

Describes the ENTRUST architecture split into three core phases: manufacturing, pre-deployment, and runtime.

Chapter 3: ENTRUST Components and Information Flows

Summarizes the main components and their interactions inside the ENTRUST framework.

Chapter 4: ENTRUST Technical and Functional Requirements

Presents technical and functional requirements for the secure operation of the ENTRUST framework.

Chapter 5: Threat Landscape and ENTRUST Countermeasures

Identifies threats and the countermeasures applied to protect each use case.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

Summarizes the document and highlights project progress.

Chapter 2

ENTRUST Final Architecture Overview

One core offering of ENTRUST is a complete framework for the **monitoring and maintenance of the level of trust and trustworthiness of medical devices** throughout their operational lifecycle. Thus, the ENTRUST framework aims to ensure that the trustworthiness level of **Connected Medical Devices (CMDs)**, but also the domain infrastructures where they are deployed, remain at an acceptable level. This process is centered around the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)** of ENTRUST, which aims to calculate the **Actual Trust Level (ATL)** of the device during runtime, and compare it to the **Required Trust Level (RTL)** of the device, which has previously been calculated based on the existing identified threats and vulnerabilities for the specific type of the device and the identified countermeasures. To this end, ENTRUST offers a wide variety of components participating in the trust assessment process (D3.2 [6]), crypto enablers (D4.2 [7]), and a Blockchain Infrastructure (D5.1 [8]), which all support the aforementioned process.

The action workflow of the ENTRUST framework can be split into three distinct core phases: (i) The **Manufacturing (Design) Phase**, which entails the manufacturing process of the device and the creation of the device-level Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD), (ii) the **Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase**, which entails the deployment and secure enrolment of the device into the infrastructure of the target medical organization, including the extension of the device MUD into an extended domain-specific eMUD, and (iii) the **Runtime Phase**, which includes actions taken during the normal operation of the CMD for the evaluation of the trustworthiness level of the CMD and the actions taken for trust establishment.

In this Chapter, we provide a consolidated architecture for the entire ENTRUST Framework, considering the role and positioning of all technical components and security processes that have been extensively described in the three aforementioned technical deliverables (D3.2, D4.2, D5.1). We also provide a detailed breakdown of all actions taken in each of the three operational phases of the ENTRUST workflow. Figure 2.1 depicts the reference architecture of ENTRUST, containing the action workflow for each of the three aforementioned phases, and will be analyzed extensively throughout the remainder of this Chapter.

Figure 2.1: ENTRUST reference architecture

2.1 Manufacturing (Design) Phase

The first phase of the ENTRUST workflow is the **Manufacturing (Design)** phase, which contains all actions taken at the side of the Manufacturer, up until the moment the device leaves the manufacturing floor in order to be deployed to a medical domain infrastructure. The core outcome of this phase is the **device-level MUD**, which *defines the foundational security requirements of the device, outlining the necessary operational characteristics in order to mitigate threats and ensure safe interactions within a network infrastructure*. Note that, at this phase, the device is considered **in isolation, without being a part of a domain infrastructure**, as it has not yet been deployed. Thus, the action workflow of this phase consists of the following steps:

1. In the beginning of the Manufacturing phase, the Manufacturer conceptualizes the device, based on the medical scope where the device is intended to be used, including specifications, requirements, and protocols, *considering the device in isolation, and not as part of a specific domain or medical infrastructure*.
2. The Manufacturer provides a set of known threats and vulnerabilities known for the device to the **Risk Assessment** component, which performs risk calculation, quantifying the level of risk for the aforementioned threats and vulnerabilities. During the Manufacturing Phase, the device-level risks are given by the Manufacturer to the Risk Assessment component through the Device-level MUD, which is stored on the **MUD server**. Conversely, during the Pre-deployment Phase, the Risk Assessment component receives information about the asset topology and domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities from the **System Administrator**. Thus, the Risk Assessment component calculates the RTL, which is then sent to the **Trust Policy** on the ledger, containing the types of evidence that needs to be collected by the security controls in the context of trust assessment. Note that, in the context of ENTRUST, there are two types of Trust Policies, namely the **Device-level Trust Policies** and **Domain-level Trust Policies**, depending on whether they refer to device-level or domain-level threats. These assist the formulation of the **Trust Model Templates**, which are going to guide the trust assessment of the device when it is eventually deployed to a medical domain infrastructure. Note that these are initially formulated during the Manufacturing phase, but will eventually be updated during the Pre-deployment and Runtime phases.
3. The **Threat Modeling** component retrieves information on the threats and vulnerabilities from various online databases (such as NVD and MITRE CWE). Then, through a **Large Language Model (LLM)**, it creates attack scenarios that go through the Threat Model builder, who in turn provides the attack path vectors to the Risk Assessment component.
4. The **Formal Verification** component receives the security requirements from the Manufacturer (during the Manufacturing Phase) and the Security Administrator or Use Case demonstrators (during the Pre-deployment Phase and Runtime Phase). The Formal Verification component also receives the ENTRUST security protocols to be formally verified as input. Considering the above, the schemes to be verified are passed through the Formal Verification Toolchain (ProVerif, Tamarin, Verifpal). It should be noted that **any requirement or aspect that cannot be formally verified needs to be attested during runtime** using the **remote attestation** schemes of ENTRUST (analyzed in detail in D4.2 [7]). Thus, with the support of the Security Administrator, the types of properties that cannot be formally verified are sent by the Formal Verification component to be added to the Trust Policy on the ledger.
5. The **Software Verification** component receives input from the **Software Service Provider**, who provides the software binaries running on the device, so that **Malware Scanning** and **Fuzzing** processes can be performed. Thus, a testing plan is created based on various intelligence sources,

using **Indices of Compromise (IOC)**. Note that this module contains a binary code analyzer and a source code analyzer, which are used in order to identify whether the files or binaries related to the target device demonstrate vulnerabilities or malicious patterns. Then, the Software Verification component provides any newly identified threats or vulnerabilities as output to the Risk Assessment Engine, so that it can update the risk calculation and risk graph.

6. A digital representation of the device, i.e., the **Digital Twin**, is created in order to enable **attack simulation** during runtime, based on information collected during the operation of the device (e.g., bandwidth or energy consumption). This is essentially an enriched version of the information that can be received from the physical device, and can be used in order to identify deviations from the expected behavior of the device. Note that, during the Manufacturing phase, *the device is considered in isolation, without including any domain- or infrastructure-specific information*, but will provide the basis for the operation of the **AI-based Misbehavior Detection** component during the Runtime phase.
7. If any zero-day threats or vulnerabilities (in addition to the ones initially defined by the Manufacturer) are identified as a result of any of the aforementioned processes, they are forwarded to a **Threat Intelligence Database**, which is a public channel of the **ENTRUST Distributed Ledger (DLT)**, functioning as a **hygiene marketplace**, aiming to enhance the security posture of devices operating in the medical domain. They are also sent to the Risk Assessment component, in order to update the RTL based on the newly identified threats and vulnerabilities.
8. Considering all the above, the **Device-level MUD** is created and sent to the **MUD Server**, which is a channel of the ENTRUST DLT. Note that Protection Profiles in the context of ENTRUST extend the definition of the MUD profile, as standardized by the IETF in RFC 8520. In addition, the information on the identified threats, vulnerabilities, as well as associated security controls are included into the device-level MUD. The calculated RTL, as well as the types of trust evidence to be collected in order to verify the correctness of the trust attributes, are added to the **Trust Policy**, which is a smart contract that is deployed to the private ledger. In the device-level MUD, there will be a pointer to the Trust Policy in the ledger that enables the collection of the required evidence and the execution of the appropriate mitigation measures in case any of the identified threats or vulnerabilities are detected during runtime.

2.2 Pre-Deployment (Domain-Specific) Phase

After the Manufacturing Phase is complete, the device can be deployed to the medical domain infrastructure where it is intended to operate, thus initiating the **Pre-deployment (Domain-Specific) Phase**. The core difference with the Manufacturing phase is the **consideration of all the assets belonging to the Service Graph Chain (SGC)** of the target medical domain, as well as the interconnectivity between them. Specifically, its positioning within such an infrastructure may lead to the emergence of additional types of threats and vulnerabilities, and a device operating within a domain may also be subject to domain-specific requirements. In addition, this phase entails the authentication, onboarding, and enrollment of the device into the domain, as well as the generation of the required **cryptographic material** (i.e., cryptographic keys and certificates) needed for the device to be able to utilize the various security enablers of ENTRUST. Thus, this phase consists of the following steps:

1. The Pre-deployment Phase begins when a new device aims to enter the target medical domain infrastructure, and notifies the **Domain Manager** to initiate this process. Note that, in the context of ENTRUST, we consider both **High-end devices** and **Low-end devices**, depending on their

available computational capabilities (which dictate the choice of an appropriate RoT for the instantiation of their TCB). High-end devices equipped with an OP-TEE as their RoT) are authenticated directly through the Domain Manager, while Low-end devices (equipped with a PUF as their RoT) are authenticated through their respective parent High-end device through their **Secure Communication Extension** components using Merkle Trees. At a high level, this process can be split into the **Authentication, Onboarding, and Enrollment** phases as follows:

- (a) In order to initiate the **Authentication** process, the Domain Manager notifies the **Authentication Server** of the Manufacturing domain. Afterwards, the Authentication Server sends a challenge, which is signed by the device with its pre-established **Root ID Key** which is installed and known by the manufacturer. This process ensures the authenticity of the device, and when complete, enables the device to be onboarded and enrolled into the actual domain.
- (b) After the authentication of the device is complete, the **Zero-Touch Onboarding process** is performed, which is described in detail in D4.2 [7]. This entails the issuance of the **Verifiable Credentials (VCs)** of the device by the Domain Manager, in collaboration with the **Privacy Certification Authority (CA)**. These VCs contain device attributes or characteristics that can be used in order to provide trustworthiness evidence during runtime in a verifiable manner in the context of the **Trust Assessment** process (note that a trust property is verified based on the presence and correctness of a set of attributes). These refer to any attributes that denote the trust characteristics of the device and are related to the trust properties of interest (e.g., secure boot, PUF, the device TCB, the authentic tracer, OP-TEE). Note that the VCs are issued for both High-end and Low-end devices. In the case of a **high-end** device, able to support **Attribute Based** cryptographic protocols, for each of those attributes, the Privacy CA will also generate and return an **Attribute Key**. It is important to state that, those attribute keys will be bound to the device's Root ID key, in a way that only the specified high-end device will be able to use them. Also, although there are not any identity privacy requirements for the use of those credentials, there is still the need to guarantee device binding, i.e., that only the device for which the VC is intended can actually use it. This is done through the binding of the VC with the device's Root ID key. In the case of the low-end device, this also means that VC verification will require the support of the device's Manufacturer for the validation of its key. The purpose of these credentials is *the provision of the ability of the device to share trust evidence during runtime in the form of a **Verifiable Presentation (VP)**, which enables sharing evidence in a privacy-preserving manner.* VPs in the context of ENTRUST offer two types of privacy:
 - (i) **attribute anonymity**, which enables the device to demonstrate the possession of a set of attributes without disclosing the attributes themselves, and
 - (ii) **attribute value anonymity**, which enables the device to disclose a set of attributes without revealing their exact values.
- (c) After the onboarding process is complete, the device sends a request to the Domain Manager to initiate its **Enrollment** into the domain. To this end, the Domain Manager possesses a set of policies that dictate a set of attributes that the device needs to prove ownership of in order to be enrolled into the medical domain **Service Graph Chain (SGC)**. If the DM is able to verify those proofs, and the attributes of the device satisfy their policy, the device will be enrolled to the Domain. In that case, devices will establish new **symmetric keys** with the DM, used for authentication and secure communications. High-end devices will use **Attribute Base Signcryption (ABSC)** to prove ownership of attributes that satisfy the **DM's policy** and authenticate a Diffie-Hellman key exchange for **symmetric key establishment**. On the other hand, the low-end device will use its **Verifiable Credential** to prove possession of the required attributes. In ENTRUST, each low-end device will be **paired** with a corresponding high-end, so as to offload the more resource consuming tasks (i.e., processing and relaying medical data to the backend system etc.) to the more powerful device. Assuming both device's have enrolled to the (same) Domain, the high-end will **authenticate** the low-end through the help of the DM.

- (d) After successful **enrollment** to the Domain, each device will also **receive a Conformity Certificate (CC)** from the **TAF**, attesting to the device characteristics enabling its participation to the Domain infrastructure (**security appraisals**). Although only the high-end CMD will be able to use the privacy preserving properties of the issued CC (i.e., selective disclosure of attributes and unlinkable presentations), device binding is required for both high-end and low-end devices. In the case of the high-end device, the CC will be directly **bound to the device's Root ID key**, in a way that presenting that CC will require access to that key. For low-end devices, the same procedure cannot be used, given its limited availability of cryptographic capabilities. In that case, the CC will be **bound to keys generated by the device's PUF**, by using a construction similar to the Merkle tree used for authentication.
2. The Risk Assessment component receives information about the asset topology and domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities from the **System Administrator**. Thus, the RTL that had been calculated during the Manufacturing phase is updated correspondingly by the Risk Assessment component calculates the RTL, followed by the updating of the **Trust Policy** and the **Trust Model Templates**. This process consists of the following steps:
 - (a) First, the Domain Manager notifies the **Risk Assessment** component about the addition of the new device. This triggers a re-quantification of risk, as well as the creation of the **risk graph**, considering the assets belonging to the domain infrastructure and the interconnectivity between them. Thus, the Risk Assessment component performs **attack path calculation** considering the asset topology of the domain, and calculates the **updated risk score** considering the specific domain characteristics, the **impact per vulnerability**, and the identified **attack paths**. This leads to an update in the RTL against which the ATL of the device will be compared during runtime in the context of the trust assessment of the device.
 - (b) Next, the **Formal Verification** component verifies, in offline mode, the protocols that are executed by the device as part of each security service, such as attestation processes, secure communication, secure update processes, and any other process that can be formally verified offline. Note that the output of the Formal Verification component constitutes the **trust boundary** of the device, which contains all processes, binaries, and software which are known to be correct and trustworthy. Any other element or process that cannot be verified is considered to be outside the trust boundary, and needs to be attested during runtime through the verification of the correctness of the required trust properties or attributes.
 - (c) Afterwards, the addition of a new device triggers the **Digital Twin** component to extend the virtual representation of the device considering its positioning within the domain infrastructure, and performs the emulation of the identified types of attacks, as outlined in the Manufacturing Phase. However, the difference here is that emulation is also performed on domain-specific threats, i.e., threats and vulnerabilities that have been identified either by the System Administrator or the Threat Modeling component.
 - (d) After the aforementioned processes are complete, the newly identified threats and vulnerabilities based on the domain-specific information provided by the System Administrator, or identified by the Formal Verification and/or Digital Twin components, are sent back to the Risk Assessment in order to calculate the updated RTL for the device.
3. Recall that, during the Design phase, a Device-level MUD of the device has been created and stored into the MUD server. Here, we extend this into a **Domain-level eMUD** (D5.1 [8], flow A), which is stored on the public channel of the DLT and also contains the threat vector identified at the domain by the Threat Modeling component and the System Administrator, i.e., the domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities, associated with the security controls that can be used in order to mitigate those threats. In addition, the **Policy Hashes** field of the eMUD (which was initially

empty) is populated with the **Key Restriction Usage Policy** (that enable the proof of ownership of specific attributes without disclosing them) specific to the domain, in order to verify the correctness of the device during runtime. Afterwards, the **Device-level** and **Domain-level Trust Policy** on the ledger are updated accordingly.

4. When a device has already been enrolled into the domain, it may be request to be **registered to the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure** in order to have access to the private channel (D5.1 [8], flow B). This request is initiated by the device providing the Domain ID, which has been acquired during domain enrollment from the Domain Manager, to the **Security Context Broker (SCB)**, which then forwards the request to the **Membership Service Provider (MSP)**. This process results in the issuance of a **Blockchain Certificate**, which is linked/binded to the VC of the device, thus ensuring that no impersonation attacks can be performed when interacting with the Blockchain. This certificate is provided to the MSP for enabling the access control mechanisms of ENTRUST.

2.3 Runtime Phase

After the Pre-deployment Phase is complete, the CMD is considered to be part of the medical domain infrastructure. Thus, the **Runtime Phase** entails all the actions taken during the normal operation of the device in order to ensure that its trustworthiness remains at an acceptable level. This process is centered around the ENTRUST TAF, which aims to calculate the ATL of the device, compare it to the previously calculated RTL, and determine if further mitigation actions are required. In addition, this phase includes the creation of the required material to ensure the **auditability and certifiability of the CMD** (such as the **Conformity Certificates** that demonstrate the correctness of the device state), by leveraging the **ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure**.

1. After the device has been successfully authenticated, onboarded, and enrolled into the domain, the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)** is considered to be running in the backend, and a Trust Assesement process may need to be performed based on the **Trust Policies** that have been constructed, dictating the actions that need to be taken. These policies may be (i) **synchronous**, meaning that the calculation of the ATL of the device is requested at fixed time intervals, or (ii) **asynchronous**, meaning that a security control needs to be deployed on demand, for instance in case a change has been detected in the system. In order to execute an attestation process on a CMD for verifying the correctness of one or more of its Trust Properties, the Domain Manager retrieves the Domain-level eMUD of the device dictating the attestation challenges corresponding to the device. For the execution of the attestation process, the **Trust Model Manager** component of the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)** retrieves the Trust Policy Template from the DLT.
2. Then, the **Trust Source Manager** of the TAF retrieves the **Trust Policy**, which dictates the **Trust Sources** from which trustworthiness evidence will be received (D5.1 [8], flow E). Such sources are the **remote attestation**, the **AI-based Misbehaviour Detection**, etc. Depending on whether this action needs to be performed on a high-end or a low-end device, this process is differentiated as follows:
 - (a) In the case of **high-end devices (CMDs)**, the MUD URL is sent to the Domain Manager by the CMD. If the corresponding Domain-level eMUD is available on the MUD Server, it is retrieved by the Domain Manager. Recall that this eMUD also contains the pointer to the location of the Trust Policy on the ledger, which contains the types of evidence that need to be collected in the context of the specified security control(s).

- (b) In the case of a **low-end devices (CMD)**, these may not be directly exposed to the network, as it is possible that they are connected to the network through a parent high-end device. Thus, communication with the Domain Manager for the retrieval of the eMUD and the collection of trust evidence is performed through the parent high-end device.
3. The attestation actions performed by ENTRUST’s CMD include the following:
- (a) **High-end** devices enrolled in ENTRUST services, equipped with certified **attribute and attestation keys** issued during onboarding, can provide attestation evidence and create **attribute-based signatures (ABS) or signcryptions (ABSC)**. The trust assessment process begins when a Verifier sends a challenge and a policy to a Signer, requesting proof that the device meets specific criteria without revealing its attributes. The Signer, using its **Trusted Component and attestation key**, generates a signature—either a conventional signature or a privacy-preserving **Direct Anonymous Attestation (DAA)**—certified by the Domain Manager. This signature confirms the device’s configuration matches its **”Golden”** state which is predefined in the **eMUD**. Subsequently, the device produces a **Verifiable Presentation (VP)** using its certified attribute keys, generating ABS for same-domain verification or ABSC for cross-domain scenarios, where attestation data is encrypted for policy-based access. Attribute anonymity is ensured using digital signatures, preventing collusion. Additionally, devices can leverage **Conformity Certificates** to establish trust within ENTRUST, which supports cryptographic agility to evaluate performance and scalability across different schemes.
- (b) Unlike high-end devices, **low-end** devices rely on **symmetric signatures generated using a PUF output as the signing key**, with verification requiring, known only to the device’s Manufacturer. To streamline trust assertions without repeatedly contacting the Manufacturer, a **Merkle** signature scheme is used, allowing the Manufacturer to certify multiple one-time public keys, which the device uses individually for runtime trust processes. Low-end devices lack selective disclosure or privacy-preserving capabilities for **Conformity Certificates (CC)**, meaning Verifiers gain full visibility of the certificate’s contents and can recognize previously interacted devices. However, the Merkle-tree approach ensures only the intended device can use its CC in a valid configuration. During a CC presentation, the device generates a **one-time public key** tied to its secure state and proves its linkage to the Merkle tree root in CC. Verifiers validate the proof, ensuring freshness by using unique, disjoint challenges supplied by the **Domain Manager (DM)**. For verifying Verifiable Credentials (VCs), which include device-specific attributes bound to its **root ID key**, a Verifier forwards the signed challenge and VC to the Manufacturer, which reconstructs the signing key based on the device’s expected configuration. The Manufacturer validates the signature, ensuring the device is in its correct **”golden”** configuration during trust assessment.
- (c) ENTRUST’s **Swarm Attestation** enables efficient and secure validation of groups of connected devices in complex network topologies. In ENTRUST, we utilize is to be able to attest a large number of low-end CMDs in a computationally efficient way, since the number of such CMDs is generally big in medical SGCs. Low-end devices, constrained in resources, rely on **PUF-based keys** for attestation, while high-end devices aggregate these proofs and forward them to a central Verifier. Using a **Merkle-tree** structure, the system ensures each device’s integrity without exposing sensitive attributes, enabling scalable and privacy-preserving attestation. **Semi-trusted** high-end devices act as **intermediaries**, securely managing communication while leveraging strong cryptographic primitives to prevent tampering or replay attacks. This approach ensures trust across the network while optimizing computational efficiency.
4. For the execution of the attestation action, as attestation evidence, the **Device Tracer** for the High-end device or the **Static tracer** for the low-end device collect the raw data required as attestation

evidence. After an attestation action is executed, the result is sent to the **Trust Source Manager** of the TAF, as it constitutes a Trust Source, as aforementioned. Note that, when a low-end device wants to provide a Trust Source, this is performed through the high-end device, which receives its Trust Appraisal through the Secure Communication Extension and sends it to the Trust Source Manager.

5. The Trust Source Manager forwards the attestation evidence to the **Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine** of the TAF, which calculates the ATL of the device based on the use of Subjective Logic and provides it to the **Trust Decision Engine** of the TAF. There, the ATL is compared to the RTL, as calculated by the Risk Assessment component, and a decision is made on the trustworthiness of the device. The Trust Decision Engine also pushes the history of the ATLs of the device to the Trust Policy on the ledger.
6. The action sequence is differentiated depending on the outcome of this Trust Decision. If **ATL < RTL**:
 - (a) In case of a successful attestation (i.e., $ATL > RTL$) the TAF generates the **Device-level Conformity Certificate (CC)** or **Domain-level CC**, which are stored on the public channel of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure for auditability and certification purposes (D5.1 [8], flow D). The CC contains the trust appraisal attributes as defined in the Domain-level eMUD and is protected under the p-ABC scheme, in order to enable the device to only share the attributes it wishes to, following the **selective disclosure** principle. This is performed through the issuance of **Privacy Attribute-Based Credentials (pABCs)** in high-end devices, while low-end device that do not have the necessary crypto capabilities, the CC is presented as-is, bound to the outcome of its **Physical Unclonable Function (PUF)**. Note that it is possible for a CC to be revoked by the SCB in case a change in the trust level of the device is detected.
7. Conversely, if **ATL < RTL**:
 - (a) In case of a failed attestation (i.e., $ATL < RTL$), the the raw traces used as attestation evidence are sent from the High-end device (or from the Low-end device through the corresponding high-end device) to the **Attack Simulation** component of the **Digital Twin**, so that it can generate the attack execution paths that led to the failed attestation. Thus, the DT has a synchronized view of the corresponding data on the physical device, and can emulate the attack path that led to the failed attestation (D5.1 [8], Flow F). These attack paths are provided as input to the Software Verification component, so that it is able to create the **Fuzzing test cases**. The traces are also sent to the **AI-based Misbehaviour Detection** component of the DT to identify any anomalies or deviations from the expected behavior of the device.
 - (b) If a new threat or vulnerability is identified following this process, the Risk Assessment Engine is notified, in order to update the risk calculation and the risk graph, as well as calculated the updated RTL based on the newly identified threats and vulnerabilities.
 - (c) Then, the DT generates the harmonized and privacy-preserving threat intelligence data (i.e., by abstracting any sensitive or domain-specific information so that it can be shared with other domains), which is pushed to the **Threat Intelligence Database** via the **Security Context Broker (SCB)** as **STIX-formulated data**. The same data, as well as the **attestation report**, is sent to the **Trust Source Manager**. These, as aforementioned, function as additional Trust Sources that can be used for calculating the ATL of the device in any subsequent trust assessments.
 - (d) The attestation evidence is also sent (via the SCB) to the **Off-Chain Storage Facility**, so that they can become available to any responsible auditing or certification parties that possess the

appropriate permissions. Afterwards, a location pointer to this data is recorded to the ledger, for enabling the retrieval of the data from the Off-chain Storage.

- (e) The **Device-level** and **Domain-level Trust Policy** on the ledger (D5.1 [8], flow C) specifying the types of evidence that need to be collected by the newly specified security controls are updated based on the trust opinion of the TAF specifying any additional trust evidence that needs to be monitored, and are stored on the private channel of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure. To this end, the Trust Policies and the VP of the device are forwarded to the SCB by the TAF, and the two-step authentication process is followed: (i) the SCB interacts with the MSP to check if the device has access to the ledger based on its Blockchain Certificate, and (ii) if successful, the SCB invokes the corresponding smart contracts on the private channel to store the Device-level and Domain-level Trust Policies. Then, the Domain Manager notifies the MUD server with the **Device-level Trust Policy Pointer** and amends the stored **Domain-level eMUD** through the SCB with the **Domain-level Trust Policy Pointer**.
- (f) The output of the Software Verification component (which, as previously outlined, has received the attack paths as input from the DT) also feeds the **Software Update** component, which gives a clean software update version to be pushed to the **Digital Twin** through the **Update Server** (D5.1 [8], Flow G). Note that the Digital Twin component possesses the **Subfleet Manager**, which contains the virtual representations of the assets of the topology (both High-end and Low-end devices), as well as the topology itself. The Subfleet Manager is responsible for pushing the updates to their respective components.

Chapter 3

ENTRUST Components and Information Flows

In Chapter 2, we provided a complete reference architecture of the ENTRUST framework, including a detailed action workflow of all three distinct phases (Manufacturing, Pre-deployment, and Runtime), and specifying the role and positioning of each individual technical component and security process of ENTRUST within the overall architecture and workflow. Here, we expand on each individual component, and we provide detailed information on their **role and positioning within the ENTRUST framework**, through detailed **sequence diagrams capturing all interactions with other components of the ENTRUST framework**.

Note that, as all these components are centered around the Trust Assessment process of ENTRUST, which is the core responsibility of the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)**. This has been the core focus of D3.2 [6], where the action workflow of the ENTRUST TAF has already been analyzed in detail, considering all interactions with the components participating in this process.

3.1 Formal Verification Component

Figure 3.1: Formal Verification Component Interaction Diagram

The Formal Verification component in the context of the ENTRUST architecture aims to apply the 'secure-by-design' approach and to support the zero-trust concept through the application of formal verification

techniques for all the phases of the CMD lifecycle. Formal verification of all internal operations might be unfeasible due to the high complexity level. Therefore, we aim to make proper abstractions to achieve an effective verification process.

This component uses as input the security properties and schemes defined for the ENTRUST framework in deliverables D2.1, D4.1, and D4.2 from WP2 and WP4 as presented in Figure 3.1. The Formal Verification components identify which security properties can be verified during design time and what needs to be attested during runtime under the form of trust policies. This will ensure that the security schemes envisioned for the CMD lifecycle achieve the required security properties, on the one hand, before implementing the ENTRUST framework, and on the other hand during runtime. Additionally, the verification results are used to improve the security schemes.

Figure 3.2: Formal Verification Component Within ENTRUST Architecture

Figure 3.2 illustrates a sequence diagram detailing the steps required for the formal verification component to obtain the necessary input for verifying security properties at design time. The security properties and the domain hardware topology are provided as input to the formal verification process. The verification results are then sent to the ENTRUST Security Protocols component, which can leverage them to enhance the protocols. Security properties that cannot be verified at design time are flagged for runtime verification.

3.2 Software Verification and Threat Modeling Component

This section extends the description of the Software Verification and Threat Modeling components provided in Chapter 2. It provides details regarding the role of the modules and how both are interacting with their consumers: Risk Assessment, Digital Twin and the CMD service provider.

The section begins by presenting the Software Verification component during the pre-deployment and the runtime phases. Afterwards, it continues with showcasing the flow of the Threat Modeling module during the design phase.

3.2.1 Software Verification

In this subsection the software verification component is presented, along with its two sequence diagrams.

The role of the Software Verification component within the ENTRUST project is to check the security of software intended for medical devices. This component is used during both the pre-deployment phase and the runtime phase.

In the Figure 3.3 the pre-deployment process steps are depicted as follows:

1. The process starts by gathering threat intelligence data, with the help of **YARA Rules Datasets Provider**. These rules contain descriptions of known malicious applications that can be detected in a static manner. They can include strings that prove that an application is connecting to a Command & Conquer server, such as an IP, or binary patterns that show that a certain function is being called.
2. When the **Manufacturer** sends a binary to the Software Verification API, it can trigger two verification processes: malware scanning and fuzz testing.
 - (a) The **Malware Scanner** statically analyzes the received binary using YARA rules to check for any malicious pattern.
 - (b) **Fuzzer** generates multiple inputs in order to find if the binary can lead to an unintended state, which could lead to further exploitation. Such a state can be if the binary has a buffer overflow that can be further exploited for a Remote Command Execution attack.
3. After these processes have been completed, the **JSON Processor** sends a JSON representation of the results to the Risk Assessment, Digital Twin and to the Service Provider for further evaluation, such as simulating the attacks.

Figure 3.3: Software Verification pre-deployment sequence diagram

The Figure 3.4 describes the process where new fuzz test cases are provided to the fuzzing engine, based on real-time traces from the device. The following steps are involved in this workflow:

1. The process starts from the **Device** that sends trust evidence to the TAF (Trust Assessment Framework) for verification.

2. **TAF** checks if the ATL is less than the RTL. If the condition is met, the TAF signals the Device to start sending traces towards Digital Twin.
3. On request, the **Device** sends raw system traces to the Digital Twin component.
4. The **Digital Twin** simulate attack scenarios considering the input trace data.
5. A system administrator reviews the **Digital Twin** results and creates new test cases, in a **super-vised** manner, that are used as a starting point by the Software Verification for fuzz testing.
6. The **Fuzzer** generates multiple inputs in order to find if the binary can lead to an unintended state in the provided test cases, which could lead to further exploitation. Such a state can be if the binary has a buffer overflow that can be further exploited for a Remote Command Execution attack.
7. The **JSON Processor** sends a JSON representation of the results to the CMD Service Provider for further evaluation, such as simulating the attacks.

Figure 3.4: Software Verification runtime sequence diagram

3.2.2 Threat Modeling

This subsection presents the Threat Modeling component, along with its sequence diagram.

The main role of this component is to generate attack vectors based on the specific characteristics of a device. The key steps are described below.

1. The process is triggered when the Threat Modeling API is receiving device-specific data from the **Risk Assessment**. This data includes the Common Platform Enumeration (CPE) identifier of the device, which enables a more formal way of describing the setup of a system.
2. The **Threat Landscape Processor** collects from multiple **Threat Intelligence Providers** relevant threat landscape for the input device data from known databases, such as the NIST National Vulnerability Database (NVD). Such data include vulnerabilities that were recently found and described using the Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) method.

3. The **Threat Landscape Processor** sends the collected threat intelligence towards the Threat Model Builder in a formatted way for being analyzed.
4. The **Threat Model Builder** processes each vulnerability individually and invokes an **LLM** (Large Language Model) to create attack scenarios. The LLM enables the system to generate attack vectors that use information from multiple domains. For example, this allows for the generation of possible attacks using information from IT, healthcare and low-end device development domains.
5. The **Threat Model Builder** processes the attack scenarios into a threat model that is sent to both Risk Assessment and Digital Twin modules in **JSON** format.
 - (a) The **Risk Assessment** module is processing the Threat Modeling results in order to compute RTL
 - (b) The **Digital Twin** module conducts simulation tests to validate the attack scenarios based on the Threat Modeling results. This validation step ensures that any inaccuracies or hallucinations of the LLM are identified, minimizing the risk of unintended consequences from hypothetical attack vectors.

Figure 3.5: Threat Modeling sequence diagram

3.2.3 Infrastructure

In this subsection the infrastructure regarding where the modules are deployed is presented.

As previously seen in Figures 3.3, 3.4 and 3.5, both the Software Verification and Threat Modeling components are currently deployed within the ENTRUST back-end infrastructure. This centralized deployment was chosen to simplify the next phase of the project, namely the benchmarking phase. By doing this, it enables us to simplify the API management and ensure that all UC partners have access to the latest versions of each module without requiring independent updates on individual UC infrastructures. This centralized API exposure helps maintain consistency in functionality, reduces potential incompatibility issues, and allows our team to monitor performance metrics more efficiently.

During this phase, benchmarking data will provide insights into how the Software Verification and Threat Modeling components perform under various operational conditions. The results of this analysis will guide decisions on whether it would be advantageous to migrate or replicate these components on infrastructures specific to ENTRUST use cases. This potential transition would allow for a more decentralized architecture, enabling use case partners to tailor and scale these modules as needed.

3.3 Risk Assessment Component

As described in Chapter 2, the core responsibility of the Risk Assessment component as part of the Trust Assessment process of ENTRUST is the calculation of the **Required Trust Level (RTL)** of a device, so that it can afterwards be compared to its **Actual Trust Level (ATL)** in order to determine if it can be considered trustworthy or not. Specifically, as previously outlined, an initial value of the RTL is calculated during the Manufacturing Phase, which is subsequently updated whenever any new threats or vulnerabilities are uncovered, during the Pre-deployment or the Runtime phase. In Figure 3.6, we provide the action workflow of the Risk Assessment process in the context of the ENTRUST framework, which can be summarized into the following steps:

1. The **Domain Manager** sends a risk assessment request, either through the OLISTIC Frontend, or using the appropriate OLISTIC Backend API calls (e.g., via a third-party application).
2. This request is forwarded to the **Risk Quantification Engine** of the Risk Assessment component, which is responsible for executing the logic of the Risk Assessment process.
3. If the asset has already been deployed to the target domain (i.e., in the Pre-deployment or the Runtime Phase), the Risk Quantification Engine retrieves the asset graph (including all assets of the target domain and their interdependencies), from the **Asset Modeling and Visualization Engine**.
4. The Risk Quantification Engine retrieves information on associated threats and vulnerabilities from the **Threat Modeling** component of ENTRUST, which includes vulnerability impact attributes based on their CVSS specification, as well as the likelihood of the threat.
5. The impact of the vulnerability, as well as the Individual Risk Level (IRL) of the asset, is computed based on CVSS attributes. The details of this process are provided in D3.2 [6].
6. The Risk Quantification Engine invokes the **Attack Path Calculator** component, in order to initiate an attack path discovery across the monitored edge topology. Note that, in order to identify the attack paths, the CVSS attributes characterizing a vulnerability are employed. However, we envision to investigate additional strategies beyond those defined by predetermined rules (e.g., based on the output of the Digital Twin for the construction of concrete attack paths).
7. After evaluating the discovered attack paths, the Risk Quantification Engine computes the Attack Path Risk Level (APRL) for each of them.
8. All aforementioned information is forwarded to the **RTL Calculator** for the calculation of the RTL for each asset. Note that, as outlined in Chapter 2, during the Manufacturing phase, an initial value of the RTL is computed and stored on the ledger as part of the **Device-level Trust Policy** of the device. The results are stored or updated in the database, where they can be retrieved by the System Administrator.
9. In the Pre-deployment phase, the Device-level Trust Policy is extended into a **Domain-level Trust Policy**, where the above process (steps 1-8) are performed again, considering any additional domain-specific threats which may be provided by the System Administrator.

- In the Runtime Phase, after the execution of the Trust Assessment process as outlined in Chapter 2 where any additional threats and vulnerabilities have been discovered (e.g., through the Attack Simulation process via the Digital Twin or the AI-based Misbehavior Detection component), steps 1-8 are performed again, and the Domain-level Trust Policy is updated.

Figure 3.6: Risk Assessment Sequence Diagram

3.4 Digital Twin

The ENTRUST Digital Twin represents a cornerstone of the project’s architecture, serving as a virtualized counterpart to physical IoT systems to enhance security, reliability, and operational efficiency. By mirroring real-time dynamics of connected devices within a controlled digital environment, the digital twin enables advanced anomaly detection and secure software/firmware update management. This section provides a comprehensive exploration of the digital twin’s role within the ENTRUST reference architecture, detailing its integration with other components, its methodologies, and its contribution to ensuring trust in IoT ecosystems. The two key subsections focus on the core functionalities of the digital twin: the “Digital Twin and Anomaly Detection Component,” which identifies potential security and operational threats through unsupervised learning techniques, and the “Secure Software/Firmware Update Component,” which safeguards the integrity of device updates through robust validation and management processes. Together, these components underscore the pivotal role of the digital twin in advancing the ENTRUST solution.

Figure 3.7 provides a detailed representation of the digital twin architecture, showcasing its core components and their interactions with external systems. The digital twin is depicted as the central entity, designed to interface seamlessly with various external components via an API layer. This architecture enables the digital twin to perform advanced security, monitoring, and operational functions within the ENTRUST framework.

Figure 3.7: Digital Twin Component Diagram.

The figure illustrates the digital twin as a central component, seamlessly interfaced with multiple external components through an API layer. Interactions with the digital twin are depicted by arrows, with incoming arrows representing requests to the digital twin and outgoing arrows indicating responses or data sent from it.

The operator, depicted in the diagram, is a human role responsible for overseeing the digital twin’s operation and effectiveness. This role involves managing its components to ensure accurate representation, efficient performance, and secure functioning of connected medical devices. The operator interprets the digital twin’s analysis results, translating complex data into actionable insights. This role may also be

assumed by other ENTRUST roles, such as the Security Administrator, who manages the Risk Assessment process and makes informed decisions about device operations. These decisions include adjusting operational parameters, deploying preventative maintenance, or responding to emerging threats. By evaluating potential risks identified by the digital twin, the operator develops strategies to mitigate their impact on system functionality and patient safety.

The **WebUI** serves as the primary interface for human operators, providing a dashboard that digitally represents connected medical devices, along with other functional reports. It allows users to inspect individual device properties and states or analyze the collective behavior of the device network. Seamlessly integrated with the digital twin system and external components, the WebUI facilitates data exchange and coordination, enhancing usability and overall functionality.

Knowledge Graph (Neo4J) provides a structured repository for storing and managing information about the relationships and properties of connected devices (assets), which represents the network topology between them. It supports advanced querying and visualization, enabling the system to map vulnerabilities and trust relationships effectively. The assets and relationships for the knowledge graph can be obtained from the trust policies in the TAF.

Time-Series Database (InfluxDB) is responsible for storing and managing time-series data such as performance metrics (e.g., CPU and memory usage, network activity). This database supports continuous monitoring and facilitates anomaly detection.

Object Database (MinIO) is an object storage solution where larger datasets, such as logs and binary files, are stored. It can also be used for storing digital artifacts such as configurations, models, and attack scenarios. It acts as a data lake, enabling the secure storage and retrieval of historical datasets for analysis and simulation.

API Layer (Flask, HTTP) serves as the central communication hub, allowing seamless interaction between internal and external components. It facilitates data exchange, processes incoming requests, and supports integration with the external components of the ENTRUST framework.

Analysis Model (Machine Learning/AI) implements unsupervised learning techniques to detect anomalies in system behavior by analyzing time-series data and system traces. The insights derived from this component inform other processes, such as threat analysis, mitigation, and serve as secondary trust evidence to the TAF component.

Attack Simulator simulates various attack scenarios based on threat intelligence and device configurations. This component helps evaluate the system's resilience to cyber-attacks and exploits device-specific vulnerabilities in a controlled environment.

Hardware Emulator emulates the behavior of physical devices using hardware configuration files. It replicates the operating environment of connected medical devices, allowing for realistic testing and analysis without impacting live systems.

Introspection Agent (Telegraf) monitors device properties, including performance metrics and system traces, from emulated devices. This data forms the foundation for anomaly detection and trust evaluation.

Orchestrator acts as the internal coordinator for the digital twin, managing interactions between the various internal components and external systems through the API layer. It ensures that all processes, such as attack simulations and data analysis, are executed efficiently.

Interaction with other ENTRUST Components. The digital twin interfaces with a range of external components in the ENTRUST framework:

- **Threat Intelligence Database** stores data on known threats and vulnerabilities, which the digital twin uses for attack simulations and mitigation planning.
- **Threat Modeling Component** provides modeled attack data, which informs the simulation of attacks within the digital twin.
- **Risk Assessment Component** receives insights from the digital twin to calculate and update risk levels based on detected vulnerabilities or system anomalies.
- **Software Verification and Assignment Components** work with the digital twin to verify software updates and ensure secure deployment to connected medical devices.
- **Blockchain Infrastructure** acts as a repository for trust evidence, enabling traceability and integrity of trust-related data.

This modular architecture ensures that the digital twin serves as a versatile, scalable, and integrative tool for enhancing the trustworthiness and resilience of connected medical devices within the ENTRUST framework.

3.4.1 Digital Twin and Anomaly Detection

This subsection explores the application of the ENTRUST digital twin integrated with anomaly detection across three critical phases of the system lifecycle: design time, pre-deployment time, and runtime. For each phase, the digital twin plays a pivotal role in enhancing the security and reliability of connected IoT systems by leveraging real-time and historical data, emulating scenarios, and detecting anomalies. To provide a clear understanding of its functionality, we present sequence diagrams illustrating the data flow, interactions, and decision-making processes involved at each phase. These diagrams highlight how the digital twin and anomaly detection work together to enable proactive security measures, informed system design, and dynamic runtime monitoring.

3.4.1.1 Digital Twin Workflow for Design-Time Analysis

Figure 3.8 illustrates the workflow of the ENTRUST Digital Twin during the design phase, where new hardware specifications are analyzed, and potential vulnerabilities are identified using simulation and anomaly detection. This process ensures that CMDs are robust and secure even before deployment. Each step tied to the specific calls depicted in the diagram are the following:

1. **Recording New Hardware Specifications:** The process begins when the **Orchestrator** receives new hardware specifications (New HW specs recorded). This information is initially stored in the **MinIO** database, then fetched (through Fetch HW specs) calls and subsequent updates (HW specs) and used to create nodes in **Neo4J**, using Trigger creation (HW specs) containing the HW specifications as properties.
2. **Hardware Emulation:** The **Orchestrator** listens to new additions into the corresponding **MinIO** bucket concerning threat models. Once a new threat model is recorded, this process triggers the hardware emulation process (Trigger hardware emulation for device (HW specs)) which uses the hardware specifications to configure the devices that are to be emulated inside the HW Emulator component. The emulator creates a virtual environment replicating the device's configuration and operational behavior (Hardware emulation).

3. **Collecting Monitored Data:** The **Introspection Agent** is instantiated under the emulation process (Instantiate) to monitor the emulated device's performance and behavior during the simulation (Monitor emulation). It collects detailed traces of the device's behavior under various conditions and stores these into **InfluxDB**.
4. **Simulating Attacks:** The **Orchestrator** fetches the threat model (Fetch threat model and Threat model), and then the **Attack Simulator** is triggered (Trigger attack simulation for device (threat model)), simulating potential attack scenarios on the emulated hardware. The simulated behavior is monitored, and relevant traces—both benign and attack-related—are recorded (Simulate attack(s) and Store monitored emulation traces (benign and attack)).
5. **Performing Anomaly Detection:** After the attack is performed, the **Orchestrator** will fetch the traces generated under simulations (New traces recorded and Fetch new traces). This is followed by the **Analysis Model** component which is triggered to analyze the recorded traces for unusual patterns or behaviors (Trigger anomaly detection for emulated device (traces) and Anomaly Detection). The results of this analysis are returned as detection outputs (Detection results), which help identify potential vulnerabilities or weaknesses in the system.
6. **Storing Results for Further Use:** The detection results and identified attack paths are stored in the system (Store detection results and Store attack path for fuzzing cases). These outputs inform subsequent validation activities, such as fuzz testing, and support the refinement of the system's security posture.

Figure 3.8: Digital Twin Sequence Diagram for Design-Time.

This diagram illustrates the workflow of the ENTRUST Digital Twin during the design phase, showcasing interactions between internal components and external ENTRUST systems. The process includes recording hardware specifications, generating threat models, emulating hardware, simulating attacks, and performing anomaly detection. Results are stored for further validation and testing, ensuring robust design-time analysis of CMDs.

Key Interactions Highlighted in the Design-Time Sequence Diagram (Figure 3.8):

Interactions with Databases. Calls to **Neo4J**, **InfluxDB**, and **MinIO** store and retrieve critical data such as hardware specifications, monitored traces, and detection results.

Orchestrator as the Central Coordinator. The orchestrator manages all calls and triggers interactions between components, ensuring a seamless workflow.

Role of External Components. Components like **Threat Modelling** provide essential inputs, such as threat models, while the digital twin generates actionable insights through anomaly detection and attack path identification.

3.4.1.2 Predeployment Phase: Ensuring System Resilience with the Digital Twin

Figure 3.9 outlines the workflow of the ENTRUST Digital Twin during the predeployment phase, emphasizing the process of preparing the CMDs for secure and reliable operation. The predeployment phase focuses on analyzing the configuration and topology of the system, evaluating domain-level threats, and testing the system's resilience to potential attacks using emulation and anomaly detection techniques. Each step tied to the specific calls depicted in the diagram are the following:

1. **Topology Configuration and Initialization:** The process begins with the **Operator** who is providing the topology file of the CMDs by storing it into the **MinIO** database (Provide topology file). The **Orchestrator** records the addition of the topology file (New topology recorded) and fetches this configuration from the **MinIO** database (Fetch topology). The topology defines the relationships and interconnections between CMDs, enabling the **Orchestrator** to establish these connections in the knowledge graph (Connect KG nodes according to topology).
2. **Domain-Level Threat Analysis (Optional):** If the threat model is updated with domain-level threats, the **Orchestrator** records the updated domain-level threat data (New threats recorded) by listening to the new additions into the corresponding **MinIO** bucket and fetches this information (Fetch threat model). The updated model is initially provided by the **Threat Modelling** component and becomes the basis for subsequent emulation, simulation and analysis.
3. **Hardware Emulation, Data Monitoring and Attack Simulation:** Similarly to the design-time process, the **Orchestrator** triggers hardware emulation for the system's configuration (Trigger hardware emulation for target domain (HW specs)), which is executed by the **HW Emulator** (Hardware emulation). As previously seen for design-time, the **Introspection Agent(s)** are instantiated under the emulation process for all the devices pertaining to the domain (Instantiate) in order to monitor their performance and execution (Monitor emulation). Using the updated threat model, the **Attack Simulator** initiates simulation of attacks on the emulated devices (Trigger attack simulation for domain (threat model) and Simulate attack(s)). The emulation generates monitored traces for both benign and malicious behaviors, which are stored for further analysis into **InfluxDB**(Store monitored emulation traces (benign and attack)).
4. **Anomaly Detection:** After the simulation of attacks is finalized, the monitored traces are recorded and fetched by the **Orchestrator** (New traces recorded, Fetch new traces and New traces), which also triggers the **Analysis Model** module (Trigger anomaly detection for target domain (traces)). These traces are used by the **Analysis Model** component as input to the analysis which identifies potential anomalies and generates detection results (Report detection results).
5. **Results Storage and Further Use:** The detection results and identified attack paths are stored into **MinIO** (Store detection results and Store attack path for fuzzing cases). These outputs are used to inform software verification activities and to enhance the system's resilience against known and emerging threats.

Figure 3.9: Digital Twin Sequence Diagram for Pre-deployment Time.

This diagram illustrates the sequence of activities performed by the ENTRUST Digital Twin during the Pre-deployment phase. The process begins with configuring the system’s topology and analyzing domain-level threat models. It involves hardware emulation, attack simulation, and anomaly detection to assess the system’s resilience and identify potential vulnerabilities. The insights generated are stored for further analysis and validation, ensuring robust preparation before deployment.

Key Interactions Highlighted in the Predeployment Time Sequence Diagram (Figure 3.9):

Data Collection and Monitoring. The **Introspection Agent(s)** actively monitor the emulated devices, collecting operational data, including performance metrics and behavior under simulated attacks. This monitored data is stored to be further processed by the analysis model module.

Anomaly Detection and Reporting. The **Analysis Model** component analyzes the monitored traces for deviations and anomalies that may indicate vulnerabilities or weaknesses. Detection results and insights

are reported back to the orchestrator and stored for future analysis.

Results Utilization for Risk Mitigation. Identified vulnerabilities and attack paths are documented and stored for use in fuzz testing and software verification activities. The insights generated are used to refine the system's security configuration before deployment.

3.4.1.3 Runtime Operations: Real-Time Monitoring and Anomaly Detection

Figure 3.10 illustrates the operations of the ENTRUST Digital Twin during runtime, emphasizing real-time monitoring, anomaly detection, and the incorporation of trust-related evidence to enhance the security and resilience of CMDs. Each step tied to the specific calls depicted in the diagram are the following:

1. **Threat Model Update (Optional):** If the **Threat Modelling** component updates the device or domain-level threat model (Device or domain-level threat model update) during runtime, then a similar hardware emulation, attack simulation and analysis process is performed, as seen for design- and pre-deployment-time.
2. **Hardware Emulation, Data Monitoring and Attack Simulation:** After recording new changes into the **MinIO** bucket dedicated for threat models (New threats recorded), the **Orchestrator** triggers the **HW Emulator** to replicate the real device or domain configuration (Trigger hardware emulation for target device/ domain (HW specs)) based on the HW specifications from previous development phases. As seen previously for design and predeployment phases, monitoring (Monitor emulation) happens thanks to the instantiation (Instantiate) of **Introspection Agent(s)**, the resulting traces being stored in **InfluxDB**. Once the emulated system is ready, the threat model is fetched from the **MinIO** database (Fetch threat model and Threat model), which eventually triggers the **Attack Simulator** to simulate attack scenarios (Trigger attack simulation for device/domain (threat model) and Simulate attack(s)), and the monitored traces, both benign and malicious, are stored (Store monitored emulation traces (benign and attack)).
3. **Anomaly Detection for New Threats and Reporting:** The **Orchestrator** listens to the monitored traces and fetches these (New traces recorded, Fetch new traces and New traces). Then the **Orchestrator** triggers the **Analysis Model** module (Trigger anomaly detection for target domain (traces)). Traces are analyzed by the **Analysis Model** component and results are reported (Report detection results). The detection results and identified attack paths are stored into **MinIO** (Store detection results and Store attack path for fuzzing cases) and made accessible to other components.
4. **Real-Time Anomaly Detection and Reporting:** The **Tracer** component deployed on the CMDs monitors the device during runtime and collects system traces. The **Trust Assessment Engine** sends these system traces to the digital twin (Send raw system traces for device/domain). The **Analysis Model** module processes these traces to identify potential security risks (Trigger anomaly detection for device/domain (traces)), generating actionable detection results. These results are stored and made available as additional trust evidence for further decision-making processes (Store detection results and Additional trust evidence).
5. **Integration with Other Components:** Detection outputs and attack paths are shared with external ENTRUST components, such as the **Risk Assessment** and **Software Verification** modules. These interactions enable a continuous feedback loop, enhancing the overall trustworthiness of the system.

6. **Iterative Analysis and Refinement:** The digital twin collects raw system traces and performs anomaly detection, ensuring that emerging vulnerabilities or security threats are promptly identified and mitigated. This real-time feedback mechanism supports dynamic trust assessments and facilitates secure, resilient operations.

Figure 3.10: Digital Twin Sequence Diagram for Runtime.

This diagram illustrates the real-time operations of the ENTRUST Digital Twin during system runtime. It shows interactions for monitoring system behavior, running anomaly detection on real-time traces, and

provision of additional trust evidence. The diagram also highlights optional updates to the threat model, attack simulations on emulated configurations, and iterative data processing, which collectively ensure the security and resilience of the system during operational use.

Key Interactions Highlighted in the Runtime Sequence Diagram (Figure 3.10):

Real-Time Threat Model Update and Integration. The **Threat Modelling** component will provide the updated threat models. Once fetched by the **Orchestrator**, it will initiate processes that take in updated device or domain-level threat data, obtained at runtime. These updates inform subsequent emulation, attack simulation, and anomaly detection processes.

Hardware Emulation and Attack Simulation. The **HW Emulator** creates virtual replicas of devices or domains based on current configurations. The **Attack Simulator** then uses these emulated environments to simulate attack scenarios using the provided threat models, generating traces of both benign and malicious behaviors.

Anomaly Detection and Real-Time Data. The **Tracer** component collects raw system traces from the CMDs in real time. These traces are analyzed by the **Analysis Module** module, which identifies deviations or anomalies indicative of potential security issues. The same module can be used at runtime on emulated traces, given that a new threat is added to the threat model.

Integrating Real-Time Anomalies with Simulated Insights. The outputs of anomaly detection on real-time data are combined with the results of hardware emulation and attack simulation to provide a comprehensive analysis of the system's behavior under both real-world and simulated conditions. Anomalies detected in real-time data can indicate potential vulnerabilities, which are further investigated by comparing them with the emulated attack traces. This integration helps identify whether real-time anomalies are caused by known attack patterns or system misconfigurations. The combined insights enable more informed decision-making for risk assessment, trust evaluation, and the implementation of mitigation strategies, ensuring robust and proactive security management.

3.4.2 Secure Software/Firmware Updates Using Digital Twins

ENTRUST aims to establish a robust and secure ecosystem for Connected Medical Devices (CMDs), ensuring their reliable and secure operation throughout their lifecycle. Central to this vision is the Secure Software Update (SSU) process, a foundational component of the broader trust management framework. A critical aspect of trust relationships between devices, as well as trust in the data they produce, is the assurance that up-to-date software and firmware are consistently deployed within the system. This envisioned system seeks to safeguard sensitive patient data, ensure uninterrupted healthcare services, and comply with stringent regulatory requirements. SSUs enable the safe and seamless evolution of device capabilities, protecting against emerging cyber-threats. They play an important role in ENTRUST's Trust Assessment Framework, ensuring the trustworthiness of both individual devices and the broader CMD ecosystem.

In the context of ENTRUST, devices that require updates can generally be categorised into two types: **high-end devices** and **low-end devices**. High-end devices, such as personal healthcare gateways, are directly connected to the Internet and possess sufficient computational resources to independently download, verify, and install software updates. These devices act as central nodes in a healthcare system, managing communication between the broader network and connected devices, making them well suited for direct update delivery over the network.

In contrast, low-end devices, such as medical IoT sensors, operate under different constraints. These devices often lack direct Internet connectivity, relying on high-end gateways to act as intermediaries for

updates. Additionally, low-end devices are typically less computationally powerful, making them reliant on gateways not only to relay updates, but also to handle computationally intensive tasks such as cryptographic verification of firmware integrity. The gateway receives the update from the Internet, verifies its authenticity and integrity, and then propagates it to the connected low-end devices.

These differences in device characteristics directly influence the design and delivery of SSUs. High-end devices can accommodate more sophisticated, autonomous update mechanisms, while low-end devices require a proxy-based approach that minimises resource overhead on the device itself. To address these requirements, the remainder of this section will discuss separately the SSU design strategies for high-end and low-end devices, tailoring the solutions to their respective capabilities and constraints.

Regardless of the type of CMD, the SSU mechanism in ENTRUST includes: (i) verification of the provenance and integrity of the update, (ii) robustness in the distribution system to guarantee the authenticity of the exchanges, (iii) secure installation processes with verifiable evidence of the updated software stack's integrity, and (iv) post-installation checks to validate the correctness of deployed updates.

3.4.2.1 Secure Software Updates for High-End Devices

The sequence of SSUs for high-end CMDs in ENTRUST, as represented in the sequence diagram in Fig. 3.11, unfolds as follows:

Secure coding and signing: The process begins with the Software Developer creating the software update using secure coding practices. Once finalised, the update is cryptographically signed and uploaded to the Software Repository, ensuring its integrity and authenticity. At the same time, the update is registered in the Digital Twin Platform, acting as a central control hub. From this point on, the SSU process can be triggered automatically upon the notification of a new software update, or the System Administrator can trigger the update distribution manually via the Digital Twin Platform.

Robust Distribution: Within the platform, the Assignment Engine and the Subfleet Manager analyse the fleet of devices using the information from their digital twins. The twins' desired and reported properties are compared to identify devices requiring updates. The Assignment Engine determines the update scope, enabling targeted (one-to-one or one-to-many) or broad (one-to-all) deployment strategies. The assignment of software updates to target devices is then passed to the adapter, instantiated, and tailored for the specific device type, which ensures compatibility and secure communication.

Installation: The High-end Device receives the information about the update from the Adapter and pulls the assigned software from the repository. During installation, the embedded cryptographic keys of the device are used to verify the signature of the update, ensuring that it remains unchanged and originates from a trusted source. The installation process is executed securely via the device's APIs, guided by the Adapter.

Post-install verification: After installation, a Monitoring Agent running on the device collects runtime telemetry, such as software versions and execution traces, and transmits these data back to the Digital Twin Platform. The platform confirms that the update has been successfully applied and verifies the device's operational integrity through ongoing monitoring. This final verification step ensures the update's correctness and addresses any potential issues proactively.

Figure 3.11: Secure Software Updates for High-End Devices.

3.4.2.2 Immediate Response to Detected Vulnerabilities in High-End Devices

In addition to the long-term process of software patch development and distribution, there is a critical need for immediate responses to detected vulnerabilities (e.g. ATL < RTL identified by the Trust Assessment Framework) to maintain device security and functionality. Such rapid responses help mitigate potential risks while new patches are being developed. As illustrated by Fig. 3.12, the SSU engine is designed to address these scenarios through two alternative pathways: deploying an existing patch or executing a rollback to a previous stable version. These mechanisms ensure that devices remain operational and secure during the interim period before the release of a long-term solution (as described in the previous subsection).

Existing Patched Software Version: When a patched software version addressing the vulnerability is already available, the SSU engine leverages this version for an immediate update. The process begins with the SSU engine consulting the Digital Twin Platform to retrieve the registered patch. The Distribution Engine identifies affected devices by analysing their attributes and runtime data and securely delivers the patch through encrypted channels. Each device validates the update’s integrity and authenticity via cryptographic checks before installation. Post-update, the Monitoring Agent ensures the vulnerability is resolved, confirming the restored trustworthiness of the devices.

No Patched Software Version Available: If no patched version exists, a rollback mechanism is initiated to mitigate the vulnerability. The SSU engine retrieves the last verified stable version of the software from the Digital Twin Platform. The Distribution Engine identifies vulnerable devices and securely delivers the stable version for installation. During installation, cryptographic validation ensures the rollback software’s integrity. The Monitoring Agent verifies that the rollback resolves the issue and restores device functionality. This rollback serves as a temporary measure while a new patch is developed. Once available, the patch is distributed using the standard SSU flow to replace the rollback version, ensuring long-term

security.

Figure 3.12: Secure Software Updates for High-End Devices as an Immediate Response to Detected Vulnerability.

3.4.2.3 Secure Firmware Updates for Low-End Devices

For low-end CMDs, the SSU process depicted in Fig. 3.13 involves additional layers of interaction and adaptation due to their limited computational capabilities and lack of direct Internet connectivity. These devices rely on high-end gateways for update management, forming a hierarchical relationship that influences several phases of the SSU lifecycle.

Secure Development and Signing: As with high-end devices, updates for low-end devices are securely developed and cryptographically signed by the Firmware Developer, also notifying the Digital Twin Platform of new versions. These updates are stored in the Repository, ready for distribution. Updates for low-end devices include firmware files, tailored for the specific hardware and operational requirements of these constrained devices.

Robust Distribution: In the distribution phase, the unique architecture of low-end devices comes into play. These devices are proxied by high-end gateways, meaning their status and update requirements are incorporated into the DT representations of the high-end gateways. This hierarchical modelling allows the Assignment Engine within the Digital Twin Platform to determine targeted updates for low-end devices by analysing the properties of their proxying high-end gateway’s DT. The gateway, functioning as an intermediary, uses its embedded Level-2 Adapter to communicate with the low-end devices. These

adapters support protocols such as Bluetooth, Zigbee, or USB, facilitating reliable and secure interactions between the gateway and the low-end devices.

Secure Installation: Once the information about the update is transferred to the high-end gateway, the Level-2 Adapter initiates the installation process on the paired low-end devices. The adapter ensures that the update package is verified against its cryptographic signature before installation. This verification leverages keys pre-embedded in the low-end devices during manufacturing to confirm the update’s authenticity and integrity.

Post-install verification: Low-end devices do not run independent Monitoring Agents. Instead, the monitoring responsibilities are handled by the high-end gateway’s agent. This agent collects operational telemetry and update status from the low-end devices, either directly or through the Level-2 Adapter, and communicates this data back to the Digital Twin Platform. The platform integrates this information into the gateway’s digital twin, enabling real-time tracking and post-update verification for both high- and low-end devices.

Figure 3.13: Secure Firmware Updates for Low-End Devices.

3.4.2.4 Immediate Response to Detected Vulnerabilities in Low-End Devices

Similar to high-end devices, the SSU engine incorporates two response pathways for low-end devices: deploying an existing firmware patch or rolling back to a previously verified stable firmware version, as illustrated in Fig. 3.14. Unlike high-end devices, low-end devices rely on their paired high-end gateways to mediate firmware update processes. The gateways act as proxies, leveraging Level-2 Adapters to communicate with low-end devices (e.g., via Bluetooth or USB) and employing the Digital Twin Platform to orchestrate update assignment and monitoring. Immediate responses are executed as follows.

Existing Patched Firmware Version: In scenarios where a patched firmware version already exists, the update is initiated through the high-end gateway acting as a proxy. The Digital Twin Platform identifies the affected low-end devices, leveraging the digital twins of their corresponding gateways. The firmware

is securely distributed to the gateways, which use Level-2 Adapters to propagate updates to paired low-end devices. Cryptographic verification ensures the integrity and authenticity of the firmware before installation, with the gateway's Monitoring Agent confirming the update's success and resolution of the vulnerability.

No Patched Firmware Version Available: If no patched firmware version is available, the system employs a rollback to the last stable version. This process also relies on the Digital Twin Platform and high-end gateways for device identification and update delivery. The rollback serves as a temporary mitigation, with the stable firmware applied to affected devices. Meanwhile, a new patch is developed and distributed through the standard SSU flow once it becomes available.

Figure 3.14: Secure Firmware Updates for Low-End Devices as an Immediate Response to Detected Vulnerability.

3.5 ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure

ENTRUST's vision focuses on advancing the secure life-cycle management of CMDs, encompassing zero-touch onboarding, operational assurance and data sharing, all within a secure and privacy-preserving framework. To achieve this, **ENTRUST employs a Blockchain infrastructure designed to handle various aspects of data sharing, provenance and auditability.** This infrastructure supports trustworthiness evidence, as well as user data compliance with stringent privacy requirements. Additionally, the Blockchain infrastructure facilitates the storage and management of security policy data and threat intelligence reports, contributing to certifiability- a critical aspect of CMDs.

The ENTRUST Blockchain architecture, described in detail in D5.1, combines permissioned and public networks. This dual approach ensures that (i) authenticated and authorized members can access sensitive medical system data with the highest security guarantees, and (ii) public information, such as

Conformity Certificates and Threat Intelligence, is accessible to all. To meet diverse privacy requirements, the architecture incorporates three distinct channels. Firstly, a private channel stores sensitive information such as trust policies, application-related data and attestation data to support ENTRUST stakeholders. Secondly, a public channel houses public information, including Conformity Certificates (CC) and domain-specific eMUDs per device, augmented with identified domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities. Finally, another public channel, the Hygiene Marketplace channel, facilitates the storage and sharing of identified threat intelligence data with other medical domain stakeholders.

ENTRUST’s Blockchain infrastructure bolsters the traceability and verifiability of CMDs’ operations. To enhance scalability, multiple nodes can be deployed to host chaincode, supporting on-chain interactions across these channels. It is important to note that off-chain data storage is employed for raw data, which is inherently large, using encrypted formats. The corresponding storage pointers are stored on-chain. To ensure the integrity and confidentiality of off-chain data, ENTRUST has developed a novel, decentralized Attribute-based Encryption (ABE) mechanism that ensures only authorized entities can decrypt and access the data. Furthermore, a two-layered access control mechanism is implemented for Blockchain authorization, combining Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) with HyperLedger Fabric’s Membership Service Provider (MSP).

The Security Context Broker (SCB) of the ENTRUST Blockchain serves as an intermediary between the Blockchain Infrastructure and external entities. It manages communication between Peers, Off-chain Storage and access control requests from other ENTRUST entities. By serving as a bridge between the Blockchain network and the external environment, this component mitigates the attack surface by introducing a centralized entity to mediate interactions with off-chain data. Moreover, it enhances control over data interactions since all operations are routed through the SCB.

3.5.1 Blockchain Architectural Workflows

ENTRUST’s Blockchain architecture is organized into three distinct flows to facilitate the secure life-cycle management of CMDs, including the establishment of trustworthy CMD domains. These flows represent the dedicated phases that ensure the secure lifecycle management of CMDs, starting from the initial bootstrap phase, where the device is securely onboarded into a domain and equipped with necessary cryptographic primitives, through its runtime operation, and extending to its ability to respond to potential events that require re-establishing its trust level. The three architectural flows of the ENTRUST Blockchain are:

- (a) the preparatory phase where the device is enrolled in the ENTRUST domain and Blockchain network, referred to as “Flow1: Preparing the Device for Trustworthiness Establishment”,
- (b) the phase where the device is equipped with the required cryptographic primitives and its trustworthiness is established for the first time, with all necessary evidence stored on the Blockchain. This phase is termed “Flow2: Establishing Device Trustworthiness”,
- (c) the phase dedicated to re-establishing trust when a new threat or risk is identified, ensuring the stored information is updated accordingly. This is known as “Flow3: Re-establishing Device Trustworthiness”.

3.5.1.1 Preparing the Device for Trustworthiness Establishment

This workflow centers on the device preparation phase for establishing trustworthiness. It encompasses the device’s enrollment into the ENTRUST Domain to facilitate zero-touch onboarding and registration with the Blockchain network. This workflow presumes that the Manufacturing (Design) Phase has already been completed and corresponds to the Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase. This phase includes all actions performed after the device is deployed to the medical domain but before it begins actual

operation. Consequently, the RTL has already been initially calculated by the Manufacturer, and the Device-level eMUD has been created and stored in the MUD Server.

At the beginning of this workflow, the device requests its eMUD (Device-level eMUD) URL from the MUD Server located on the Manufacturer's side. The MUD Server responds with the requested eMUD URL, which hosts essential information for the device, including identified threats, vulnerabilities, and associated security controls, formatted in XML. Upon successfully receiving the required information listed in the Device-level eMUD, the high-end device proceeds to request enrollment in the medical domain or organization, forwarding the acquired Device-level eMUD URL to the Domain Manager.

The Domain Manager oversees the initiation of authentication, onboarding, and enrollment into the domain. Based on the information extracted from the eMUD on the Blockchain, the Domain Manager verifies that the enrolled devices adhere to the correct key restriction usage policies, enabling subsequent trust assessment and monitoring. Simultaneously, with assistance from the Domain Security Administrator, the Domain Manager begins the risk assessment process and generates a risk graph. This graph considers the assets within the specific medical domain and their interconnectivity, updating the device's risk graph to include additional attack vectors that emerge upon its integration into the target CMD domain. This process results in a new RTL, which becomes part of the trust policy. The risk results include quantified risks for the device and security controls recommended for mitigation.

Furthermore, the collective threat analysis conducted during this process allows the Risk Assessment engine to extend the threat vectors incorporated into the Domain-level eMUD for each device. The MUD Server is notified of these updates and ratifies the MUD profile accordingly. The Risk Assessment engine shares the risk results across the ENTRUST architecture, including with the Domain Security Administrator and the Domain Manager. Working in collaboration with the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF), the Risk Assessment engine facilitates trust assessment by initially generating the Device-level Trust Policy. When a device joins the domain, it generates the Domain-level Trust Policy. Both trust policies are stored as smart contracts within the private channel of the ENTRUST Blockchain.

The Domain Manager extracts the key restriction usage policies from the Device-level eMUD and verifies the successful enrollment of the device. At this stage, the Domain Security Administrator approves the enrollment request and generates the Domain-level eMUD for the device, which includes a list of threats enriched with domain-specific vulnerabilities. This Domain-level eMUD is stored in the public channel of the ENTRUST Blockchain network. The Domain Manager, via the Security Context Broker (SCB), pushes the Domain-level eMUD onto the ledger. The SCB stores the Domain-level eMUD for the device in the public channel of the Blockchain as a smart contract.

When the device is enrolled in the domain and seeks to register with the specific private channel of the ENTRUST Blockchain infrastructure, it submits a request to register with the ENTRUST Blockchain infrastructure at the target domain, including the domain ID obtained during enrollment by the Domain Manager. The domain ID is an attribute included in the issued VC and VP. The SCB forwards the registration request, along with the domain ID, to the Membership Service Provider (MSP) to initiate the device's membership registration. The MSP engages the Blockchain CA to issue a Blockchain identity certificate for the device requiring registration. This certificate is used to manage the access control capabilities of components when interacting with the Blockchain. Once issued, the certificate is returned to the MSP to facilitate access control at a later stage.

Subsequently, the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) receives trustworthiness evidence from the devices, which it uses to calculate a device-level trust opinion. These opinions are then aggregated to provide a trust appraisal for the entire domain. The TAF forwards the trust policies along with the device's VPs to the SCB for access control and to invoke the corresponding smart contracts. ENTRUST's authentication process comprises two layers.

First, the SCB interacts with the Membership Service Provider (MSP) to verify the attributes of the

Blockchain certificate issued by the Blockchain CA, determining whether the device has access to the specific Blockchain channel. The MSP then informs the SCB whether the first authentication layer is successful. If successful and the device is granted access to the requested channel, the SCB proceeds with the second authentication layer using Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC). This layer leverages the provided VP from the high-end device by invoking the corresponding smart contract of the channel.

The SCB invokes the relevant smart contracts of the private channel to store the Device-level Trust Policy and the Domain-level Trust Policy, utilizing inheritance functions. Blockchain pointers that reference the stored Device-level Trust Policy and Domain-level Trust Policy are returned to the Domain Manager, who updates the Device-level eMUD and Domain-level eMUD accordingly. Finally, the Domain Manager notifies the MUD Server with the Device-level Trust Policy pointer and updates the stored Domain-level eMUD via the SCB with the Domain-level Trust Policy pointer.

Figure 3.15: Workflow of preparing the device for trustworthiness establishment

3.5.1.2 Establishing Device Trustworthiness

This workflow centers on establishing the device’s trustworthiness. It involves storing Conformity Certificates (CC), application-related data, attestation-related data and threat intelligence data within the Blockchain infrastructure. ENTRUST supports two modalities for initiating the trust assessment process:

a synchronous mode (e.g., where the TAF runs periodically) and an asynchronous mode (e.g., triggered by changes detected on a device).

Conformity Certificates (CC) operate in two modalities: a synchronous mode, where an auditor requests a CC to verify the trustworthiness of a device or domain, and an asynchronous mode, where the auditor sets a policy to generate CCs periodically or when the trust state of the device or domain changes. The TAF generates a CC containing trust appraisal attributes as specified in the Domain-level trust policy. This CC, formatted as a VC and secured under the p-ABC scheme, is shared with the device, enabling it to selectively disclose only the information required by the requesting auditor.

The resulting VP is then stored on the Blockchain, where it can be accessed by the auditor. If the device's trust level changes, the SCB can revoke the CC. To ensure this, the TAF checks the Blockchain for a valid (non-expired) CC before revocation. Importantly, revocation does not compromise the auditability of the stored information.

The issued CC is sent to the device for a Device-level CC or to the Domain Manager for a Domain-level CC. The device or Domain Manager then generates a Privacy Attribute-Based Credentials (p-ABC) VC, which uses zero-knowledge proofs to disclose only the attributes requested by the auditor. The SCB invokes the relevant smart contracts on the public channel to store both Device-level CCs and Domain-level CCs.

Upon a request from the TAF, based on the trust sources outlined in the trust policy, the medical device generates attestation-related data. Specifically, all devices produce attestation evidence in the form of signatures. High-end devices can also generate attestation reports on behalf of low-end devices, which lack the capability to communicate directly with the TAF. The attestation signatures are collected by the TAF for trust assessment purposes.

The SCB interacts with the Membership Service Provider (MSP) to verify the attributes of the Blockchain certificate issued by the Blockchain CA, determining whether the device has access to the specific Blockchain channel. The MSP informs the SCB whether the first authentication layer is successful. If the first authentication layer is successful, the device gains access to the requested channel after also passing the ABAC check. The SCB then invokes the appropriate smart contract, and based on the provided VP from the high-end device, determines whether the device can access the private channel for storing the attestation raw data and attestation report.

If the data exceeds the volume limitations of the ENTRUST ledger, it is encrypted through dedicated ABE mechanisms of the ENTRUST Blockchain. This typically applies to attestation raw data. After encryption, the encrypted data is stored off-chain, and the corresponding storage pointer is returned to the private ledger. The SCB invokes the same smart contract to update it with the storage pointer information.

When the medical device generates application data and network traces to monitor system behavior within the context of a specific application, these application-related data and network traces, along with the VPs, are pushed to the ledger through the SCB. Simultaneously, the data is forwarded to Digital Twins, which employs an internal AI-based anomaly detection system to investigate potential new threats and vulnerabilities. Digital Twins analyzes the data for possible threats, and if a new threat is identified through anomaly detection, a risk assessment process is triggered to calculate an updated RTL. If the ATL is lower than the newly calculated RTL, the risk assessment initiates mitigation actions, such as a software update process. This scenario leads to an updated Device-level eMUD, initiated by the SW Service Provider. The Domain Manager is then notified to begin updating the device policy hashes in a verifiable manner.

If no threats are detected, Digital Twins generates harmonized, privacy-preserving threat intelligence data in STIX format. These data are forwarded to the Hygiene Marketplace channel via the SCB and also shared with the TAF (and Risk Assessment) as an additional trust source. The SCB invokes a specific smart contract on the private channel for the application data and network traces. If the data volume

exceeds the ledger’s limitations, it is encrypted using Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE). The encrypted data is stored off-chain, and the corresponding storage pointer is returned to the private ledger by invoking the same smart contract to update it with this information. Additionally, the SCB invokes the appropriate smart contract on the Hygiene Marketplace channel to store the harmonized threat intelligence data.

Figure 3.16: Workflow of establishing device trustworthiness

3.5.1.3 Re-establishing Device Trustworthiness

This workflow addresses the re-establishment of a device’s trustworthiness (e.g., in cases of failed attestation or when the ATL falls below the RTL). It involves defining a security policy that is subsequently enforced, which may include actions such as a software or firmware update. This process ensures that updated reference values for the device’s expected configuration and behavior are properly applied.

In the event of a failed attestation or a change in trust level caused by monitored trustworthiness evidence (e.g., attestation reports or detected misbehaviors), the TAF notifies the Digital Twins to retrieve raw evidence for further analysis (e.g., application data and network traces). This analysis includes attack emulation to identify the specific attack execution path, performed by the internal Attack Emulation sub-component. The results from the Attack Emulation process are sent to the SW/FW Verification service for fuzzing test case generation. Based on these test cases, the Security Administrator can create an updated software binary with the required patches. This new software update is passed to the Secure SW Update service, which, with assistance from the Digital Twins, delivers it to the target device. The

recipient device, utilizing its internal attestation mechanisms, then provides the necessary evidence to the TAF to confirm whether its ATL has risen above the RTL following the software update.

Figure 3.17: Workflow of re-establishing device trustworthiness

3.6 Tracer - Connected Medical Device State Monitoring

The Tracer of Entrust serves two primary functions. First, the static traces generated by the tracer are a core input to the attestation process. These traces capture predefined system behaviors and properties, providing evidence of trustworthiness that can be validated during attestation procedures and ensuring that the system maintains a reliable and secure operational state. Second, the runtime tracer, which operates during system execution, feeds real-time data into the Digital Twin/Anomaly Detection Module. This dynamic tracing allows for continuous monitoring of the system’s behavior, enabling the detection of anomalies that could indicate potential security threats or operational issues. By integrating with the anomaly detection module, the runtime tracer enhances the system’s ability to proactively address vulnerabilities and maintain the integrity of connected medical devices. Figures 3.18 and 3.19 depict two primary interaction groups: Normal Operation, which includes the generation of the trustworthiness claims (static and runtime properties) for the attestation process, and the input to train the Anomaly Detection Module of the Digital Twin.

3.6.1 Normal Operation

In the normal operation phase, the **Tracer** plays a central role in the attestation and verification process by generating and providing trustworthiness evidence for high-end devices. This process is initiated by the **Domain Manager** and facilitated by a structured series of interactions with key components, ensuring that the Tracer’s outputs effectively support continuous trustworthiness assessment.

1. The **Domain Manager** starts the process by sending an attestation request to the **Attestation Agent** of the connected high-end device.

2. The **Attestation Agent** responds with the URL for the device's eMUD file, which contains the device's security policies and operational guidelines.
3. The **Domain Manager** then retrieves the relevant domain-level eMUD file from the **eMUD Server** to ensure that the latest security specifications are applied to the attestation process.
4. With the eMUD information on hand, the **Domain Manager** issues an attestation challenge to the **Attestation Agent**, specifying the requirements for trustworthiness verification.
5. The **Attestation Agent** forwards this challenge to the **Tracer**, which is responsible for generating trustworthiness evidence in response to the request.
6. Internally, the **Tracer** processes the request and produces the necessary trustworthiness evidence, which is then submitted to the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)** for evaluation against established security and operational standards.

3.6.2 Attestation Failure Scenario

In instances where the attestation process fails, the **Tracer** remains integral to the recovery protocol, ensuring that generated trustworthiness evidence is securely encrypted, stored, and made available for future assessments or anomaly detection analysis.

1. Upon detecting an attestation failure, the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)** initiates encryption of the trustworthiness evidence produced by the **Tracer** using Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE), safeguarding the evidence before storage.
2. The **TAF** then submits a request to the **Secure Context Broker (SCB)** to access ENTRUST's Trusted Computing Base (TCB), including a Validity Proof (VP) for the device's authorization.
3. Following successful validation by the **SCB**, the **TAF** is authorized to securely store the encrypted evidence.
4. Finally, the **TAF** records the encrypted trustworthiness evidence on the **Blockchain** off-chain data storage, where it is preserved for future analysis, ensuring that even if immediate attestation fails, evidence generated by the **Tracer** is securely available for post-failure examination and anomaly detection.

3.6.3 Training Input for Anomaly detection Module

The **Tracer** also generates traces as part of its operation. These traces are used in the digital twin to train the anomaly detection modules. Thus:

1. The **Tracer** generates traces that capture the system's behavior, including both normal and anomalous behavior.
2. It also sends these traces to the **Anomaly Detection Module (DT/ADM)** for training. The anomaly detection module evaluates these traces to identify any potential anomalies in the system's performance or behavior.

3.6.4 Differences between high- end and low- end devices

By comparing Figure 3.18 with Figure 3.19, it can be observed that there are no significant differences in the core operation of ENTRUST's **Tracer**. The key distinction lies in the deployment of the **attestation agent** and **tracer**. In high-end devices (Figure 3.18), both the attestation agent and tracer are located on the same device (high-end device). In contrast, in low-end devices (Figure 3.19), these components are distributed across different devices: the attestation agent is housed in a high-end module, while the tracer resides on the low-end device. This separation is necessary due to the limited processing capabilities of low-end devices, which are unable to handle both modules within the same hardware. As a result, the attestation agent is offloaded to the more capable high-end module.

Figure 3.18: Tracer’s high-end device Sequence Diagram

Figure 3.19: Tracer's low-end device Sequence Diagram

Chapter 4

ENTRUST Technical and Functional Requirements

In D2.1 [5], an initial definition of technical requirements of the ENTRUST framework was provided, by following a methodology entailing gathering requirements from relevant medical standards and regulations, and their refinement based on the needs set forth by organizations belonging to the healthcare sector. Since this initial definition of requirements, there have been advances in the development and refinement of the framework, . Specifically, the requirements have been **adjusted to align with real-world applications** and feedback received from the technical and use case partners of ENTRUST. These updates ensure that the framework remains compatible with all phases of the device lifecycle: manufacturing, deployment, and operation.

As in D2.1, in the following sections, we provide Tables where each requirement is accompanied by its ID, name, description, reasoning, connection to ENTRUST component, and corresponding KPI ID. Note that these requirements are categorized as follows: (i) **Framework Requirements**, which contain the functional requirements of ENTRUST pertaining to actions that need to be performed in all phases of the operational lifecycle of the CMD, (ii) **Security Requirements**, which are related to the secure operation of the CMD and the integrity of the exchanged data, and (iii) **Operational Requirements**, which are related to the domain-specific operation of CMDs in the context of medical organizations.

4.1 Framework Requirements

Framework requirements capture the entire range of functionalities performed during all three core phases of the operational lifecycle of the CMD (Manufacturing, Pre-deployment, Runtime), and their goal is to ensure the safe, secure, and uninterrupted provision of healthcare services according to the capabilities of the device. This includes actions revolving around the Trust Assessment process of ENTRUST, related to the collection of trustworthiness evidence, the use of security or attestation enablers, and the use of the Blockchain infrastructure for ensuring the auditability and certifiability of these actions.

Id	Name	Description	Reasoning	Connect to	KPI
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FR.1	Device and Network threat modelling	Identify and prioritize potential threats according to the device context (e.g., the location the device will be deployed, network characteristics, capabilities of in terms of processing power and the available connectivity interfaces (Bluetooth, RF, etc.). It should provide indicative mitigation actions (e.g., disable network interfaces)	The analysis of the threat model will allow the risk assessment to quantify the risks given the threat context (e.g., connection to other devices, mobility aspects, introduction of new technological and cross-cutting developments) and extract risk scores, possible attack paths, and attack simulation by the validation component	Threat Modelling	KP_20, KP_21, KP_26
FR.2	Software threat modelling	Identify and prioritize vulnerabilities based on static code analysis and known vulnerabilities collected by external public sources such as OSV, CVE databases and others. It should provide indicative mitigation actions (e.g., patches)	Using data from the static analysis, this module will provide a report regarding threats that could use the analysed software as an attack vector. This analysis will allow the risk assessment to quantify the risks and extract risk scores, possible attack paths, and attack simulation by the validation component	Threat Modelling	KP_20, KP_21, KP_26
FR.3	Source code static analysis and SW validation mechanism	Analyse source code for known security vulnerabilities through SW unpacking techniques such as memory fuzzing and concolic testing	Catching security vulnerabilities early in the development process, before being deployed to the medical devices	SW Verification	KP_20, KP_21, KP_26
FR.4	Security code coverage	Identify areas that are not adequately covered by security tests	Helps developers identify vulnerable areas and comply with industry regulations, by measuring the quality and completeness of security tests	SW Verification	KP_20, KP_21, KP_26
FR.5	Awareness on potential vulnerabilities and threats	The ENTRUST framework should be able to collect and report information regarding vulnerable assets/devices or assets being under attack	Based on this evidence will perform an informed analysis over the deployment being monitored	Risk Assessment	KP_20, KP_21, KP_26
FR.6	Complete overview of the deployed environment	The framework should offer an interactive tool for visualizing the assets taking part in a monitored environment including their characteristics, network topology and dependencies/inter-connections among them	The risk assessment needs a detailed overview of the connected assets to produce attack risk graphs based on the network topology, dependencies, and the involvement of a threat in the network's assets	Risk Assessment	KP_35
FR.7	Risk quantification and impact analysis	The framework should be able to quantify the risks and analyse the impact of the successful exploitation of each identified vulnerability and calculate cascading effects to other connected devices in the network	The security admin needs an overview of the identified risks so as to deploy mitigation actions given the results of the risk assessment, for regulating the risk to the desired level and meeting a desired protection level	Risk Assessment	KP_20, KP_21, KP_26

FR_8	Device lifecycle modelling	The formal verification component allows explicit specification of the overall device behaviour throughout its lifecycle	The Formal Verification component should be able to provide rigorous mathematical proofs for the correctness of all implemented processes where such a verification is possible, considering the limitations of the verification method, thus ensuring that all security requirements are met, and the behaviour of the device is correct based on the provided specifications	Formal Verification Toolset	KP_22
FR_9	Service modelling considering the concept of trust explicitly	The component allows specification of the behaviour of all services that are relevant for the safe and secure device operation	The mathematical analysis performed by the Formal Verification component should be conducted for each possible service, considering the limitations of the employed verification methods, and ensure that all the security requirements are met, which are relevant for the safe and secure device operation, so that healthcare services can be provided in a reliable manner based on the underlying specifications	Formal Verification Toolset	KP_22
FR_10	Formal verification of security requirements	The component allows specification of the security properties and supports their verification using suitable tools (e.g. protocol verifiers)	This is an essential requirement that provides confidence in the trust models by using formal verification techniques and ensures secure-by-design approach, for the methods where such verification is possible	Formal Verification Toolset	KP_22
FR_11	Protection profiles, including the required level of trustworthiness (RTL) per device and service, as well as the corresponding mitigation actions.	The Protection Profiles should contain the defined properties for each device/service that needs to be monitored and verified during runtime	The protection profiles will include the operational parameters that should be attested during runtime verification for the various predefined levels of trustworthiness that cannot be covered by the formally verified crypto schemes	Trust Abstractions and Protection Profiles (DLT infrastructure)	KP_17, KP_19

FR_12	Device status auditing	The "health" status of a CMD shall be auditable for certification purposes. Collected data should reflect the trustworthiness of the device	When setting up communication with another device, the interacting device wishes to know the status of that device before proceeding. This should ensure that, when a communication channel is established, the communicating partners have not been compromised by a malicious party and are in a correct operational state. To facilitate this, CCs should provide verifiable evidence of trustworthiness, ensuring the authenticity and integrity of devices through decentralised identity mechanisms.	Runtime Attestation	KP_5, KP_6, KP_7, KP_8, KP_14, KP_16, KP_18
FR_13	Device Data and Traces collection	The ENTRUST runtime verification should be able to collect periodically data	In the context of the attestation schemes of ENTRUST, the device should be able to collect data to be used as attestation evidence, which can be used to prove the correctness of the configuration state of the device. Thus, the device should be equipped with a Tracer that is capable of collecting the types of data required to perform attestation of the trust properties specified in the Protection Profile of the device	Runtime Attestation, Tracer	KP_17, KP_18
FR_14	Runtime attacks detection	The ENTRUST runtime verification and tracing should be able to detect sophisticated attacks during the runtime	The attestation schemes of ENTRUST should be able to detect when one or more trust properties of the device do not deviate from values that are known to be correct. In addition, the Misbehaviour Detection component should be able to analyze network traffic data in order to identify any type of attack that may have occurred	Runtime Attestation, Misbehaviour Detection	KP_23, KP_24
FR_15	Validation of systems' integrity	The state of a system component should be monitored and verified. This verification may refer to the configuration of a system or to the integrity of a critical binary of the system	The attestation schemes of ENTRUST should be able to verify the configuration integrity of the device through the collection of the appropriate attestation evidence (i.e., configuration traces), for all specified trust properties	Runtime Attestation (Configuration Integrity Verification)	KP_13, KP_14, KP_15, KP_16
FR_16	Execution data collection for runtime attacks	The execution tracer is required to collect data from the CMDs and provide the corresponding information to be logged on the DLT and ultimately be processed by the Attestation mechanism and AI-based Misbehaviour Detection component	The collected data will be given as input to the Attestation mechanism and digital twins, while the data will also be used by the AI to identify and classify any type of possible misbehaviour profiles	Digital twins, AI-based Misbehaviour Detection	KP_25

FR_17	Threat intelligence data sharing	The MUD and Threat MUD should include the behavioural profile and mitigation strategies for threat intelligence data sharing	The MUD should be accessible and should enable the collection of all the information required for the secure deployment of the device	Risk and Threat Intelligence Engine	KP_36
FR_18	Behaviour profile enforcement	A component will require the enforcement of the security profile in the deployment scenario within the bootstrapping phase, as well as in cases where mitigation actions are needed	When a device is enrolled into the ENTRUST framework, the secure boot up process is performed, and the Risk Assessment engine performs a re-evaluation of the risk profile of the device, considering the asset cartography and interconnectivity of assets. In addition, the Protection Profile of the device will provide the appropriate mitigation actions for addressing any identified threats and vulnerabilities	Risk and Threat Intelligence Engine and Runtime verification	KP_26
FR_19	Decentralised identity and trust management using self-issued Verifiable Credentials/Presentations	Devices should be able to issue verifiable credentials which are backed by trustworthy evidence of their provenance. These VC/VPs can be used in the context of access control mechanisms for trust-aware authentication and authorization. Additionally, mechanisms for device status auditing and trust assessment should be integrated to ensure continuous evaluation of the device's health and calculation of its ATL	When someone aims to access a set of data by disclosing a set of attributes, we cannot assume that the party responsible for the verification of these attributes is trustworthy. Therefore, a medical device should be able to disclose the particular set of attributes required in order to access the desired set of data (selective disclosure)	Runtime Attestation (Configuration Integrity Verification)	KP_6, KP_27
FR_20	Mitigation actions to maintain system operation	The protection profiles should include mitigation actions to maintain the required level of trustworthiness. This information will be integrated into MUD protection profiles.	Considering the available mitigation measures within the ENTRUST framework (e.g., attestation enablers), the Protection Profile of the device should specify the most appropriate mitigation measures for the identified types of threats and vulnerabilities. In addition, in case of a failed attestation, the Protection Profile should be updated to include any additional mitigation measures to address any newly identified vulnerabilities	Risk Assessment, Threat Modelling	KP_28
FR_21	Data provenance	The devices should be authenticated and attested to ensure that data originates from reliable sources. The blockchain infrastructure will be responsible for managing the data provenance and maintaining the chain of provenance.	During the Domain Bootstrapping process, the Domain Manager issues a challenge, which is signed by the CMD using its Wallet, in order to verify its correctness before it is enrolled into the framework. In addition, the device is registered with the DLT based on its DID identifier and the signing keys generated during enrolment	Wallet, DLT	KP_17

FR_22	Trust assessment to calculate ATL	The ENTRUST framework should be able to calculate the Actual Level of Trustworthiness (ATL) and validate it against RTL. If discrepancies are detected, necessary reconfiguration or software updates should be performed.	Within the operation of the CMD, continuous monitoring ensures that the ATL aligns with the RTL. After an attestation process evaluates safety-criticality properties, additional measures need to be taken if the ATL is below the RTL to increase the device's security posture.	Formal Verification Toolset, Risk and Threat Intelligence Engine, Trust Controls, Certification Auditing, Runtime Attestation	KP_1, KP_2, KP_3, KP_4, KP_29
FR_23	Digital Twins for enabling secure and scalable software updates	The Digital Twin component enhances IoT security, reliability, and efficiency by mirroring real-time device behavior in a virtual environment. It supports advanced anomaly detection and secure software/firmware updates, fostering trust in IoT ecosystems	The secure management of software/firmware updates through the Digital Twin ensures the integrity and reliability of device operations. By integrating rigorous validation and update processes, the twin mitigates risks associated with compromised updates, reinforcing trust in IoT ecosystems and safeguarding connected devices	Device Data and Execution Tracer, Risk Assessment, Threat Modelling	KP_33, KP_34
FR_24	Recording of evidence-related information in DLT	The DLT infrastructure should accommodate the secure storage of information from ENTRUST operations. Such data are: a) attestation data, b) trust policy data (device and domain), c) application data, d) eMUDs (domain), e) threat intelligence data, f) conformity certificates (device and domain)	Trust policy data and other relevant metadata from ENTRUST operations should be written in the Blockchain, while data should be stored encrypted in off-chain facilities for traceability of operations (raw attestation evidence due to large size). In case of a failed attestation process, the raw trace data used as attestation evidence should be encrypted and stored (off-chain) so that they can be used to determine the cause of the failure	DLT Infrastructure	KP_17
FR_25	Support of smart contracts in DLT	The DLT should facilitate the writing of smart contracts for transparency, immutability and traceability purposes, every time a recording transaction takes place in ENTRUST Blockchain	The use of smart contracts for the execution of security policies enables the monitoring and transparency of blockchain-enabled transactions	DLT Infrastructure	KP_17

FR_26	Support of private and public channels in DLT	The DLT should include both a private and a public channel, where the private channel will contain sensitive and private information, while the public channel will store anonymous metadata for any verification/certification purposes	The DLT infrastructure of ENTRUST should provide data access capabilities based on the confidentiality level of the data and the permissions of the parties attempting to access the data. In this context, the data stored on the public ledger should not contain information that may compromise the anonymity of a device or the confidentiality of the stored data. Private channels will accommodate trust policy data, attestation evidence location pointers, and application data. Public channels will accommodate eMUDs, CCs, and threat intelligence data (the latter in the Hygiene Marketplace public channel)	DLT Infrastructure	KP_17
FR_27	Analysis of network traffic data using AI-based methods	The Misbehaviour Detection component should be able to detect anomalies in network traffic data through the use of AI-based methods	During the operation of a device, it is possible to deploy Network Monitors to collect network traffic data, which provides information on the volume and frequency of data exchanged with the device. This data is stored on the DLT in the context of collaborative data sharing and can be used in the training set of the AI-based Misbehaviour Detection component to enable classification between benign and malicious behaviours	AI-based Misbehaviour Detection	KP_30
FR_28	Use of time-series for device misbehaviour analysis	The AI-based Misbehaviour Detection component should run analysis at runtime through the use of time-series data based on network traffic data	After the AI-based classification model of the Misbehaviour Detection component has been trained, it should be able to receive network traffic data and detect any abnormal or unexpected behaviour (e.g., unusually high traffic load or traffic spikes)	AI-based Misbehaviour Detection	KP_30
FR_29	Use of Trusted Components for misbehaviour detection	The AI-based Misbehaviour Detection component should use TCs for analysis purposes	In order to safeguard data used in misbehaviour analysis, the Trusted Components of the device are used to sign any transmitted data, and the DLT is used to ensure the integrity and correctness of the stored data	AI-based Misbehaviour Detection	KP_30

FR_30	Use of a hybrid Trusted Component approach	ENTRUST should employ a hybrid approach with regard to the Trusted Components (TCs) integrated into the device, utilizing both a PUF and a TEE	The two employed TCs will serve different needs. Specifically, the PUF will be used for integrating hardcoded device keys on the device so that its identity can be verified based on physical properties, and the TEE will use keys derived from the aforementioned device keys to perform various cryptographic operations	Runtime Attestation, Trust Abstractions and Protection Profiles (DLT infrastructure)	KP_10, KP_13
FR_31	Use of high-entropy cryptographic keys	The cryptographic keys employed in the context of ENTRUST should be created based on seeds provided by the PUF.	The PUF is able to provide seeds with high entropy, thus leading to highly cryptographically-secure keys This will guarantee a high level of trustworthiness with regard to the security of the performed cryptographic operations, as well as a system as a whole	Runtime Attestation	KP_10, KP_11, KP_12
FR_32	ABAC and ABE mechanisms in ENTRUST Blockchain	ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure should employ ABAC service for granting access to blockchain data only to authorized entities through leveraging of Verifiable Presentations. In addition, data stored in the Off-Chain Storage of ENTRUST DLT should be encrypted through attribute-based encryption mechanisms	Attribute-based access control mechanisms should be employed in ENTRUST DLT for the authorization of any entity attempting to record/retrieve data to/from the Blockchain. ABE encryption will also ensure the security and privacy of data residing in the on-chain and off-chain facilities of ENTRUST blockchain, ensuring that only entities with the correct decryption keys will have access to the stored encrypted data	DLT Infrastructure	KP_17, KP_31

Table 4.1: Framework Requirements

4.2 Security Requirements

The security requirements for ensuring the secure operation of CMDs, addressing the integrity of performed operations and exchange data, as well as protection against tampering and malicious activities, were initially defined in Deliverable D2.1. In the context of Deliverable D2.2, these requirements have been revisited and updated to reflect the latest developments, ensuring that the ENTRUST framework remains aligned with current security needs and effectively addresses any newly identified challenges or vulnerabilities. These include requirements pertaining to the correctness of the operational state of the device, the integrity of the exchanged data, the prevention of tampering on the device or data by any malicious actors, and the mitigation of any potential threats or identified vulnerabilities. In Table 4.2, each security requirement is accompanied by its ID, name, description, reasoning, and corresponding KPI ID.

Id	Name	Description	Reasoning	KPI
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SR.1	Access Control	The CMD allows each role to access only the functions it is authorized for	It should be possible to provide the required level of granularity in system and data access, based on the role of the party attempting to access a particular function or set of data (e.g., doctor, nurse, hospital administrator) in a manner that fulfils all relevant security requirements	KP_8, KP_9
SR.2	Critical Data Protection	The CMD protects critical data against accidental/intentional change and loss	It should be ensured that safety-critical data pertaining to patient health must be protected against tampering or other compromises, in order to ensure that the provision of healthcare to patients is not Jeopardized	KP_8
SR.3	Code Integrity Check	The CMD checks the integrity of the program code every time it is restarted	It should be ensured that the CMD is in a correct operational state, both with regard to the integrity of the firmware and the properties specified by the Protection Profile, in order to ensure the reliability and safety of all actions performed pertaining to the security of the handled data Analyse source code for known security vulnerabilities through SW unpacking leveraging Code integrity Validation (CIV) techniques such as memory fuzzing and concolic testing	KP_8, KP_16
SR.4	Patch Application, Roll-back and Access Control	The CMD allows patches to be applied. It allows to remove defective patches again, and it limits the ability to apply or remove patches to users. Also, the CMD checks changed program code (patches) for integrity before first use and when restarted	To facilitate updates and fixes, to ensure system stability and safety and maintain system security, and to ensure system stability and safety, it should be ensured That system updates on devices should be performed in a manner that guarantees the correctness of the software patch, as well as the correctness of the device configuration, both before and after the update has been performed	KP_8
SR.5	Audit Log and Traces Protection	The CMD logs all essential actions on the system in an audit log and collect traces related to the operation of the CMD	It should be possible to record the outcomes from the execution of all security controls (e.g., attestation actions), so that an auditor or certification body with the appropriate permissions is able to access those results. In addition, it should be possible to maintain and isolate a record of system activities for analysis and identification of new threats and Vulnerabilities	KP_18
SR.6	Runtime identification of vulnerabilities and attacks	The CMD is protected through the implementation of mechanisms capable of detecting runtime attacks	Following a failed attestation action, it should be possible to use the attestation evidence (e.g., system raw traces) in order to perform additional SW verification actions and to identify vulnerabilities and attack paths in the system, thus ensuring the security and reliability of the CMD	KP_20, KP_26

SR_7	Authenticated and Encrypted Communications	All communications of CMD should be encrypted and authenticated. The CMD only transmits data via its data interfaces in ciphered form. This applies to the communication between CMDs but also to external data carriers	All data exchanges between devices and parties should be performed in a manner that achieves security and integrity of the transmitted data, and it should be ensured that this data has not been compromised by a malicious third party	KP_8, KP_12
SR_8	Data Integrity	Protects the integrity of the data against unwanted modification	It should be possible for all parties receiving messages from a device or actor participating in the ENTRUST network to be able to verify the integrity of the message and the contained data, in a manner that ensures a high level of trustworthiness in all data exchanges	KP_7, KP_8, KP_12, KP_15, KP_16
SR_9	Certificate Exchange	Allows the exchange of certificates	It should be possible to establish a secure communication channel between the CMDs and the Certification Authority (CA) during the secure enrolment phase for the issuance of certificates	KP_8, KP_9
SR_10	Cryptographic Libraries	Cryptographic libraries must ensure enhanced integrity, confidentiality, and agility by using state-of-the-art cryptographic primitives. They must also be pre-tested and regularly updated to maintain the highest level of security	The ENTRUST framework must ensure the security and reliability of cryptographic functions through rigorous mathematical proofs and formal verification. Libraries must remain up-to-date, avoiding deprecated versions, with all identified vulnerabilities patched to prevent malicious exploitation	KP_8, KP_11, KP_12
SR_11	Key Uniqueness	Uses different technologies or keys for different functions	It should be ensured that we do not use the same key for two or more different cryptographic functions, so that in case one key has been compromised, the security breach is contained to one specific context and does not propagate to other security functions of the system	KP_11, KP_12
SR_12	Certificates Authentication	Certificates need to be authenticated	It should be ensured that certificates originate from a legitimate source and not have been tampered with during transmission or storage. It should also be ensured that an outdated or deprecated certificate is not used, so that it cannot be exploited by a potentially malicious third Party	KP_8, KP_9
SR_13	Integrity of Traces	The integrity of the collected traces which reflect the system state needs to be ensured	In the context of the attestation schemes of ENTRUST, the correctness and integrity of the raw traces collected by the Tracer as attestation evidence should be ensured, so that they have not been corrupted or tampered by a malicious third party, thus leading to incorrect attestation results (e.g., generating a successful attestation result while a malicious third party has tampered with the traces in order to mask their compromise of the device)	KP_25

SR_14	Isolated execution of security critical functions	The CMD should be equipped with essential mechanisms to effectively isolate the execution of sensitive functions	Critical services, particularly cryptographic ones, must operate in complete isolation from other software components. The reasoning behind this approach is that, in case one such service is compromised, the attack cannot propagate to different services and components, thus reducing the potential impact of the attack	KP_10, KP_13
SR_15	Detection of abnormal deviations in the device behaviour	Mechanism for detecting abnormal behaviour of a CMD as part of a network	We need to implement and deploy mechanisms, which are able to compare the configuration state of the device or the execution of a software process against a state that is known to be correct and trustworthy, so that a deviation from this state can be flagged as a potential indication of risk. Thus, the detection of an abnormal behaviour can be used in order to identify zero-day threats and new Vulnerabilities.	KP_24
SR_16	Integration of a Root-of-Trust to the CMDs	The Root-of-Trust will underpin all secure operations on a chip and will protect the CMDs. The RoT needs to provide a unique and unforgeable foundation. CMDs should have an RoT used for storage of keys, collection of traces and reporting of results	A root of trust will be used to securely manage the root key material of the platform as well as to ensure secure Bootstrapping of the platform, collection of traces and reporting results. This will ensure the integrity and correctness in the creation and storage of all required underlying cryptographic material, and will provide a high level of trustworthiness guarantees in the execution of all cryptographic processes	KP_13
SR_17	Secure cryptographic Key Management/Storage	The cryptographic keys used for the critical security functions need to be securely managed and stored	The Root-of-Trust must provide capabilities for the secure storage and management of all keys required in the context of the security controls and functions employed in the context of ENTRUST (e.g., remote attestation)	KP_10, KP_11, KP_12
SR_18	Confidentiality of SW/FW updates and security patches	SW updates should be encrypted to ensure that they remain unknown to an attacker eavesdropping transmissions	A Malicious third party may attempt to hijack the software update process of a device, in order to obtain illicit access to the device and compromise its integrity. Thus, we should be able to prevent unauthorized access and tampering by ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity of the updates, especially guarding against potential eavesdropping attacks.	KP_32, KP_34
SR_19	Secure security/vulnerability patching over-protected communication channels	Patching vulnerabilities should be handled with secure communication and cryptographic operations	A secure update process is needed, that enables patching vulnerabilities that have been identified by the intrusion detection mechanisms of ENTRUST following the execution of a security function (e.g., failed attestation). The integrity of the secure update process should be guaranteed through the utilization of the underlying Root-of Trust (RoT)	KP_32, KP_34

Table 4.2: Security requirements

4.3 Operational Requirements

As previously mentioned, before deploying and integration a device into the operational environment of a healthcare organization, several key requirements must be met to ensure secure, reliable, timely, and uninterrupted healthcare service. The operational requirements were initially defined in Deliverable D2.1. Here, we have revisited to verify that they align with the current needs of the project. Table 4.3 provides the detailed list of these requirements, and confirming their relevance and applicability, particularly regarding the actions to be undertaken by the device manufacturer of the security administrator of the target organization.

Id	Name	Description	Reasoning
OR_1	User Environment Definition, Data Interface Identification and Protocol Specifications	The manufacturer defines the intended user environment (neighbouring system identification) and identifies all neighbouring systems that may connect to the CMD. Identifies all data interfaces and specifies protocols and standards used for each data interface. Also, defines CMD functions accessible to each role and neighbouring system.	In order to perform risk assessment after a device is introduced into the network, we need to consider the network topology, number and type of assets, and asset interconnectivity. The motivation is to understand the operating environment and its potential vulnerabilities, to understand potential points of interaction, to understand all points of data transfer and ensure secure and standardized data transfer, and to manage access to CMD Functionalities.
OR_2	Role List Creation and interaction role lost	The manufacturer creates a list of all roles that may interact with the CMD	It is possible that parties that fulfil different roles (e.g., patient, doctor, IT security administrator) aim to interact with the CMD. It is necessary for all such roles to be identified, in order to enable the design and implementation of access control mechanisms based on these roles.
OR_3	Unspecified User/Behaviour Risk Analysis and Risk acceptance criteria	The manufacturer analyses risks if the system is used by a non-specified user or adversary, and the impact if a function of the device is used by any adversary. Also, she analyses specific risks resulting from the choice of technologies, including programming language, SOUP/OTS components, and generates risk acceptance criteria based on CMD intended use and safety criteria.	Since risk is defined as likelihood times impact, we should consider these factors within the employed risk assessment methodology. The reasoning is to understand potential risks from unauthorized use (attack scenarios showing the risks), and define acceptable levels of risk.
OR_4	Security Threat Modelling	The manufacturer identifies threats and vulnerabilities using threat modelling for safeguarding CMDs. It involves delineating the scope of the CMD, creating a comprehensive overview of its architecture, and identifying critical components and examining potential threats and vulnerabilities.	The motivation behind the risk assessment approach followed in ENTRUST is to identify and manage potential IT security threats and impacts. Based on this, we can prioritize addressing the most impactful and critical threats, thus allowing for the implementation of targeted security controls and countermeasures.
OR_5	Overloading System Risk Investigation	The manufacturer investigates consequences of overloading the system with too many requests or large volumes and defines actions.	Overloading the system with too many requests may have adverse effects on the execution of software processes, including safety-critical processes and mathematical computations required for the execution of cryptographic operations. Therefore, it is necessary to identify and mitigate risks caused by system overload.

OR.6	Buffer Overflow Mitigation Measures	The manufacturer defines measures that can find and eliminate buffer overflows	Buffer overflow attacks may lead to the leakage of data, which may create vulnerabilities that can be exploited by malicious parties. Therefore, it is necessary to implement the necessary countermeasures for the prevention and mitigation of buffer overflow attacks.
OR.7	Network Availability Risk Analysis	The manufacturer analyses consequences if the network is no longer available or no longer in expected quality	Network availability issues may lead to the inability for devices and backend components to exchange safety-critical data. This may lead to the inability to execute security processes, such as attestation actions. Therefore, such issues may lead to compromises in the overall system security, and it is necessary to mitigate risks caused by network failures
OR.8	Pre-Delivery Malicious Code Testing	The manufacturer tests software (source code and binaries) for malicious code before delivery and/or protects all components involved in software development and "CMDion" against malware. The manufacturer takes measures to ensure tools used, platforms, and SOUP/OTS components are free of malicious code	There have been various types of attacks identified in the literature based on the insertion of malicious code snippets and the installation of malware. This type of attacks is one of the most prominent threats to the security, integrity, and confidentiality of the stored data, but also the devices themselves. Therefore, it is necessary to implement the necessary measures (e.g., intrusion detection and attestation enablers) to prevent such malware infections
OR.9	Patch Management Plan	The manufacturer documents a plan for the application and removal of patches, including development, distribution, installation, and review. The manufacturer assesses how often patches are required and how they should be installed	It is possible that a malicious party may attempt to compromise the software update process, in order to obtain illicit access to a device and potentially install malicious code. Therefore, in order to maintain system security and stability, it is necessary to implement a secure software update process that entails verifying the correctness of the configuration state of the device before, during, and after the update process, as well as the integrity of the update patch itself
OR.10	Functionality Assurance Assessment	The manufacturer assesses the functionality the medical device must guarantee in the event of a cybersecurity compromise	Since ENTRUST deals with applications belonging to the healthcare sector where it is crucial to maintain healthcare functionalities with little to no downtime, we need to implement mechanisms that enable maintaining essential functionality in the event of a breach
OR.11	Usual Attack Vector Security Check	The manufacturer includes a security check against the usual attack vectors in the test plan	There have been several potential threats and vulnerabilities identified in the literature for the types of devices considered in ENTRUST, as well as attacks noted in various threat intelligence databases. To this end, it is necessary to implement mechanisms that are able to check for the presence of such attacks, as well as to implement the appropriate mitigation measures for such attacks

OR_12	Risk-Control Measures Effectiveness Check	The manufacturer has checked the effectiveness of all risk-control measures	In order to ensure the effectiveness of the ENTRUST solution, it is necessary to validate the effectiveness of the implemented risk-control measures in a formal manner, through the use of rigorous mathematical proofs and dedicated verification tools
OR_13	CMD Delivery Check	The manufacturer has described how it is ensured that only the exact intended artefacts (files) in exactly the intended version are delivered in the CMD or as a CMD	Using a deprecated version of the CMD may lead to potential security risks, such as the exploitation of vulnerabilities which may have been addressed in later versions of the CMD. To this end, it is necessary to ensure that the correct and intended version of the CMD is delivered
OR_14	Post-market Surveillance Plan	The manufacturer has created a post-market deployment surveillance plan	Even after the ENTRUST platform has been released to the market, it is possible that new types of threats and vulnerabilities are identified, for which dedicated countermeasures and mitigation measures are required. To this end, it is necessary to keep track of the CMD's performance and issues after it has been released to the market
OR_15	Downstream Phase Information Channels	The manufacturer has described how and through which channels information is collected from the downstream phase	In order to apply the appropriate mitigation measures and attestation enablers, it is necessary to collect information from the downstream phase of the operation of a device. Therefore, we need to ensure the effective collection of such information
OR_16	Patch Acquisition and Installation Assurance	Defines how the customer obtains the patches, as well as how the manufacturer ensures that the patches are correctly installed	In order to ensure that all newly identified vulnerabilities are addressed in a manner that is accessible to customers in a timely and efficient manner, we need to ensure that patches are easily and promptly accessible to customers, and that patches are installed properly by the customers
OR_17	Neighbouring system and topology identification	The security administrator identifies the neighbouring systems, referring to devices directly linked within a network, and the network structure itself (topology identification)	In order to effectively perform risk assessment, it is necessary to consider the interconnectivity between assets and devices belonging to the target network, to understand interconnected devices, and the structural layout of the network. Thus, it becomes possible to identify potential attack paths that may be followed by a malicious party in order to obtain illicit access to a device and compromise its integrity
OR_18	Security Risk Evaluation	The security administrator evaluates the CMD-related risks after the deployment of the Device	Following the execution of a failed attestation process, it should be possible to perform an investigation on the data used as attestation evidence in order to identify the cause that led to the failure, and to potentially identify any new zero-day vulnerability. Thus, it is necessary to regularly evaluate and manage IT security risks and identify appropriate mitigation measures

OR.19	Regulatory Requirement Identification	The manufacturer identifies all relevant regulatory requirements in all markets	Organisations operating within the health-care sector are subject to various regulations pertaining to security, data integrity, etc. To this end, it is necessary to ensure compliance of all tools and security solutions provided by ENTRUST with all relevant regulations
OR.20	Risk Acceptance Criteria Generation	The manufacturer generates risk acceptance criteria based on CMD use and state-of-the-art	Based on the criticality of a component or an underlying software process, it is necessary to define acceptable levels of risk, and to prioritise the most prominent and impactful risks that should be addressed with the available mitigation measures.

Table 4.3: Operational requirements

4.4 Refined List of KPIs

This deliverable outlines a detailed overview of the approach adopted by ENTRUST. Following the definition of all core aspects, the focus is now on refining the plan for validating the ENTRUST framework. Thus, this section describes a list of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) ensuring a comprehensive assessment of the presented framework and aligned with project objectives. These KPIs are linked to the refined list of requirements presented in the previous section. Note that, however, operational requirements are not linked to any KPI as their nature for describing properties in a qualitative way does not fit with the quantitative measurement provided by KPIs.

Id	Requirement	KPI	Description	Values
KP.1	FR.22	Number of use cases where TAF is evaluated	All possible trust relationships in these use cases will be instantiated and evaluated, meaning referral (node-centric) and direct (node-centric and data-centric) trust relationships.	= 4 UCs, considering 3 trust models of different complexity
KP.2	FR.11, FR.22	Latency of standalone trustworthiness level assessment execution by the TAF	These calculations represent the time it takes for the TAF to respond with an Actual Trustworthiness Level (ATL) or a Trust Decision (TD) after it receives a Trust Assessment Request (TAR) from an application. Note that this does not include the time needed to collect and process data communicated by other entities. We also exclude any network latency caused by the reception of trust sources from neighbouring nodes. The requirement focuses only on the TAF internal operation and the trust level calculation after all the necessary input is there.	Efficiency of key hierarchy construction and verifiable key restriction usage policies: < 200 ms (excluding network latency)
KP.3	FR.22	Number of nodes supported by the TAF	The TAF should be scalable in order to assess the trustworthiness levels of all involved CMDs and the data exchanged between the nodes, within strict time requirements, even if the number of nodes is very high.	≥ 10 nodes

KP_4	FR_22	<p>TAF result correctness for 1st scenario: All entities are trustworthy (i.e., not compromised by an attacker)</p> <p>TAF result correctness for 2nd scenario: One or several entities are not trustworthy because they have been compromised by an attacker</p>	<p>To evaluate whether the TAF provides the correct result that an entity is trustworthy or not, a scenario-based evaluation will be conducted for all envisioned use cases</p> <p>Since in 1st scenario, all entities are trustworthy, the output of the TAF for all propositions should be that the corresponding entities are also trustworthy.</p> <p>In 2nd case, the results of the TAF for the propositions containing these entities should be that the corresponding entities are untrustworthy</p>	<p>In $\geq 70\%$ of successful attacks, which represent the existence of a compromised entity in the medical-service-graph-chain, propositions regarding the trust level of this compromised entity should fail the ATL $>$ RTL test.</p>
KP_5	FR_12, FR_19	Trust Sources	These trust sources are collected so that they are verifiable through trustworthiness claims	≥ 3 different trust sources
KP_6	FR_12, FR_19	Size of the Trustworthiness Claims	TCs that hold runtime evidence should not impose a big increase in the network's bandwidth	<p>< 40 bytes when a claim is sent without the VCs (so as to be able to fit to security headers of commodity communication protocols (TLS, IPSEC etc) without fragmentation)</p> <p>< 150 Kbytes when claims are sent with VCs (wrapped within the VC)</p>
KP_7	FR_12, SR_8	Signing and verification times for the TCs	This considers the signing and verification times required for TCs. These processes ensure that devices can provide verifiable evidence of their trustworthiness	<p>$> 100/s$ signing/verifications per second as per ETSI specifications for ECC-based signs for TC claims</p> <p>< 500 ms for ZK and Signcryption</p>
KP_8	FR_12, SR_1, SR_2, SR_3, SR_4, SR_7, SR_8, SR_9, SR_10, SR_12	Crypto agility	Supporting different types of crypto primitives in order to cover all the advanced security requirements of ENTRUST	≥ 3 crypto primitives that can be supported
KP_9	SR_1, SR_9, SR_12	Overhead of crypto operations regarding the management of certificates considering the strict privacy requirements of medical domain	In terms of overhead introduced due to the volume of data, by the size of crypto structures (i.e., signatures and certificates), associated to trust related information, compared to the FIR standardised certificates regarding identity management	Linear to the number of attributes to be disclosed

KP_10	FR_30, FR_31, SR_14, SR_17	Overhead of using keys with and without key restriction usage policies	This will allow the detailed benchmarking of both local and remote attestation processes that ENTRUST will provide for extracting information evidence as trust sources	<15% overhead should be introduced by the key restriction usage policy manager introduced by the employed ENTRUST TCB.
KP_11	FR_31, SR_10, SR_11, SR_17	Efficiency of key-based policy management	This considers the construction of the appropriate key hierarchies associated with specific session handles/policies regarding the keys comprising all of the necessary crypto primitives and keys, needed to support the entire lifecycle of a CMD	< 60 ms
KP_12	FR_31, SR_7, SR_8, SR_10, SR_11, SR_17	Types of keys to be supported and maintained	This outlines the types of cryptographic keys used by ENTRUST that must be supported and maintained to ensure secure and trustworthy crypto operations.	≥ 4 keys
KP_13	FR_15, FR_30, SR_14, SR_16	Number of operations supported by the TCB	The TCB should be able to support all the operations that are required for the advanced Trusted Computing operations that ENTRUST provides (i.e., storage, measurement, reporting)	≥ 3 operations
KP_14	FR_12, FR_15	Time needed for the execution of the local attestation assuming the provision of authenticated runtime measurements	Evaluate time required to execute a local attestation when authenticated runtime measurements are provided. The attestation process ensures the integrity of system components through the collection and assessment of attestation evidence	< 200 ms
KP_15	FR_15, SR_8	Time needed for the construction of the TCs abstracting any details on the trust evidence	The focus is on the time required to create TCs that attest to system integrity while avoid the specific details of the underlying trust evidence	< 900 ms
KP_16	FR_12, FR_15, SR_3, SR_8	Time needed for the execution of configuration integrity verification	The time required to verify system configurations and validate integrity by assessing attestation evidence against defined trust properties	< 100 ms
KP_17	FR_11, FR_13, FR_17, FR_21, FR_24, FR_25, FR_26, FR_32	Management of trust-related information to the Blockchain for auditability and certifiability.	The management of trust-related information involves utilizing Blockchain technology for ensuring auditability and certifiability. Trust policy data, metadata, and other critical information from ENTRUST operations are securely recorded on the Blockchain to enable transparent traceability	< 800 ms for reading and writing < 2 sec for access control
KP_18	FR_12, FR_13, FR_14, FR_16, SR_5	Efficiency of tracing	The device traces should not pose a substantial overhead to its operation	< 20% overhead to the executable that is being traced

KP_19	FR_11	Updating the trust policies of the TAF based on the latest version of the protection profiles	Protection profiles will contain information that affects trust policies. Profiles may be updated leading to their retrieval, parsing, enriching and publication in the blockchain, along with the appropriate updates in the TAF.	< 5 sec
KP_20	FR_1, FR_2, FR_3, FR_4, FR_5, FR_6, FR_7, FR_18, FR_20, SR_6	Dynamic Risk Assessment based on the identification of new threats	This focuses on evaluating the time required to process a new Dynamic Risk Assessment by the identification of new threats	< 2 sec considering the identification of a new threat (by a security administrator) based on monitored evidence collected as part of a failed attestation process that indicates a possible risk
KP_21	FR_1, FR_2, FR_3, FR_4, FR_5, FR_7	Recalculation of RTL considering the identification of new risks	This metric evaluates the performance and latency of recalculating the Required Level of Trustworthiness (RTL) within the runtime security framework of ENTRUST.	< 2 sec
KP_22	FR_8, FR_9, FR_10, FR_22	Convergence of Formal Verification models	Formal Verification models should be able to converge under the maximum threat model (model that covers the maximum number of threats and vulnerabilities identified as a common set for the Use Cases)	TRUE (< 1 day)
KP_23	FR_14	Trust Sources Monitoring	All Trust Sources, such as attestation evidence and misbehavior detection results, should be collected. . .	< 5 sec for the (synchronous) end-to-end collection of trust evidence
KP_24	FR_14, SR_15	Misbehavior Detection Accuracy	Use of developed advanced misbehaviour detection techniques should lead to an improvement on the accuracy	in case of attacks triggering misbehaviour detectors, the target is the improvement of at least 10% in the expected average detection ratio with respect to the "As-Is" use cases
KP_25	FR_16, SR_13	Monitoring agent (tracing for DT)	The monitoring agent should send enough types of relevant evidence to the digital twin while not incurring in a large overhead over normal CPU operation	< 10 % overhead on the normal CPU operation > 6 = types of evidence to be collected
KP_26	FR_1, FR_2, FR_3, FR_4, FR_5, FR_7, FR_18, FR_20, SR_6	Dynamic Risk Assessment and identification of possible attack paths	The Risk Assessment Engine should be able to provide results in a timely manner according to the size of the topology, while attack path identification based on AI does not need to be real time but should aim for good timeliness	Linear to the number of nodes of the topology for ENTRUST Risk Assessment Engine ≤ 8 min for LLM-based attack path identification
KP_27	FR_19	CC construction	Construction of a Conformity Certificate to prove the abstracted trustworthiness attributes of a device to a verifier	< 2 sec
KP_28	FR_20	eMUD Update	If Detection of ATL < RTL then Domain Manager should check MUD and Threat MUD for mitigation and new actions	< 4 sec Includes retrieval and DLT access
KP_29	FR_22	CC revocation	Adding the CC in the revocation list of the DLT	< 5 sec not realtime

KP_30	FR_27, FR_28, FR_29	Ai-based misbehavior detection accuracy	The misbehaviour detection component based on AI should achieve good accuracy on its predictions	80% accuracy
KP_31	FR_32	ABAC performance	The attribute-based access control should lead to a manageable overhead for blockchain operations	< 900 ms
KP_32	SR_19	Establishment of secure and authenticated channels	Secure and authenticated channels based on the negotiation of keys with privacy-preserving techniques	< 800 ms
KP_33	FR_23	SW update end-to end time	The digital twin based component will provide OTA updates to software for CMDs	< 3 min
KP_34	FR_23, SR_18, SR_19	SW update scalability	The digital twin based component will manage OTA updates for CMDs in a domain and must be able to scale to cover multiple nodes	> 50 CMDs
KP_35	FR_6	New risk assessment after topology is updated	The risk assessment framework monitors the complete environment and must be updated when the topology changes, e.g. with the addition of a new node	< 5s
KP_35	FR_17	Retrieval and parsing of threat data in MUD	MUD files should be available and will be retrieved and parsed to recover threat intelligence data	< 2s

Table 4.4: KPIs for Compliant Protection of CMDs

4.5 Most Valuable Product (MVP)

We previously outlined all envisioned requirements of the ENTRUST platform, based on the methodology that was defined in D2.1 [5]. In this deliverable, the list of requirements was refined based on the feedback of the use case partners, based on needs of actual and practical medical domain applications. This section is dedicated to the mapping of the user stories of ENTRUST (Tables 4.5 4.7, 4.9, 4.11, 4.13) with the technical requirements of the ENTRUST framework (Sections 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3). The end goal is the definition of the **Most Valuable Product (MVP)** of ENTRUST, prioritizing the requirements which are the most relevant in all use case demonstrators. First, in Tables 4.6, 4.8, 4.10, 4.12, and 4.14, we provide the mapping of the aforementioned requirements (Framework, Security, and Operational) to the user stories of ENTRUST, in order to identify the requirements that are fulfilled by each user story.

Id	Description	ENTRUST Functionalities	Demonstration
KA.US1	As a security administrator, I would like to assess the integrity of the device during the bootup.	Runtime attestation, Trust Controls, Certification & Auditing, SW Verification, Digital Twin	M24
KA.US2	In the case of a security incident, I would like to enforce an action (fallback action or remote firmware update) and assess that the device operates correctly after the update.	Runtime attestation, Trust Controls, Certification & Auditing, Software Enforcement, SW Verification, Digital Twin	M24 (M36)
KA.US3	As a Security Administrator, I would like to ensure that the CMD is continuously assessed, issues conformity certificates, and enforces any necessary security measures.	Runtime attestation, Trust Controls, Attestation Agent, Device Data & Tracer, Certification & Auditing	M24 (M36)

KA.US4	As a Security Administrator, I would like to ensure that CMDs are continuously assessed against their predefined behaviour, calculates its level of trust and enforces any necessary security measures.	Runtime attestation, Misbehavior Detection, Trust Assessment Framework(TAF), Attestation Agent, Device Data & Tracer, Certification & Auditing, AI-based Misbehavior Detection	M24
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Table 4.5: Kardinero use case (UC1) user stories

Id	KA.US1	KA.US2	KA.US3	KA.US4	Id	KA.US1	KA.US2	KA.US3	KA.US4
Functional Requirements					Security Requirements				
FR_1	X		X		SR_1		X		
FR_2	X		X		SR_2		X		
FR_3	X	X			SR_3		X		X
FR_4		X			SR_4		X		
FR_5		X	X		SR_5		X	X	X
FR_6					SR_6			X	X
FR_7			X		SR_7				
FR_8		X		X	SR_8			X	X
FR_9		X		X	SR_9			X	
FR_10		X		X	SR_10	X			
FR_11			X	X	SR_11	X			
FR_12		X	X	X	SR_12	X		X	
FR_13			X	X	SR_13				
FR_14			X		SR_14	X			
FR_15		X	X	X	SR_15				X
FR_16			X	X	SR_16	X		X	X
FR_17	X		X		SR_17	X			
FR_18	X	X		X	SR_18		X		
FR_19	X	X			SR_19		X		
FR_20	X	X	X	X	Operational Requirements				
FR_21	X		X		OR_1	X			
FR_22			X	X	OR_2				
FR_23		X		X	OR_3				X
FR_24	X		X	X	OR_4				
FR_25	X		X	X	OR_5				X
FR_26			X	X	OR_6				X
FR_27				X	OR_7				X
FR_28				X	OR_8		X		
FR_29				X	OR_9		X		
FR_30	X		X	X	OR_10		X		
FR_31	X		X	X	OR_11			X	X
FR_32	X		X		OR_12				
					OR_13				
					OR_14		X	X	X
					OR_15			X	
					OR_16		X		
					OR_17				
					OR_18				
					OR_19				
					OR_20		X		

Table 4.6: Mapping of ENTRUST requirements to the user stories of the Kardinero demonstrator

Id	Description	ENTRUST Functionalities	Demonstration
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TLU.US1	As a Security Administrator, I would like to automate the onboarding and authentication of gateways	Zero Touch Onboarding, Enhanced MUD Profile Server, ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base, Conformity Certificate Issuance	M24
TLU.US2	As a Security Administrator, I would like to ensure the secure onboarding of third-party CMDs at the gateway level.	Zero Trust Onboarding, (Design-time) Trust Assessment, ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base, Runtime Attestation, Verifiable Credential Management	M24
TLU.US3	As a Security Administrator, I would like to manage the fleet of gateways, assess its trustworthy state during runtime and enforce updates if needed.	Dynamic Trust Assessment, Runtime Attestation, AI-based Anomaly Detection, SW/FW Update Process, SW/FW Verification Component	M36
TLU.US4	As a Security Administrator, I would like to assess the trustworthiness of the CMD during runtime and issue Conformity Certificates based on the collected verifiable evidence.	Dynamic Trust Assessment, Risk Assessment, Runtime Attestation, AI-based Anomaly Detection, Conformity Certificate Manager, ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure	M24 (M36)

Table 4.7: Tellu use case (UC2) user stories

Id	TLU.US1	TLU.US2	TLU.US3	TLU.US4	Id	TLU.US1	TLU.US2	TLU.US3	TLU.US4
Functional Requirements					Security Requirements				
FR_1			X	X	SR_1	X	X		
FR_2			X	X	SR_2	X	X		
FR_3					SR_3			X	X
FR_4					SR_4			X	
FR_5					SR_5				X
FR_6	X	X			SR_6			X	X
FR_7					SR_7		X		
FR_8					SR_8				
FR_9			X	X	SR_9	X	X		X
FR_10					SR_10	X	X		
FR_11				X	SR_11	X	X		
FR_12				X	SR_12	X	X		X
FR_13			X	X	SR_13				
FR_14			X	X	SR_14	X	X		
FR_15	X	X	X	X	SR_15				X
FR_16			X	X	SR_16	X	X		
FR_17				X	SR_17	X	X		
FR_18				X	SR_18			X	
FR_19	X	X			SR_19			X	
FR_20				X	Operational Requirements				
FR_21	X	X			OR_1	X	X		
FR_22			X	X	OR_2	X	X		
FR_23			X	X	OR_3				
FR_24				X	OR_4				
FR_25	X	X	X	X	OR_5				
FR_26				X	OR_6				
FR_27				X	OR_7				
FR_28				X	OR_8	X	X		
FR_29				X	OR_9			X	
FR_30	X	X			OR_10				
FR_31	X	X			OR_11				
FR_32					OR_12				
					OR_13	X			
					OR_14			X	X

	OR_15				
	OR_16			X	
	OR_17	X	X		
	OR_18				
	OR_19				
	OR_20				

Table 4.8: Mapping of ENTRUST requirements to the user stories of the TELLU demonstrator

Id	Description	ENTRUST Functionalities	Demonstration
UC3.S1.US1	As a Security Administrator, I would like to ensure the secure onboarding of third-party CMDs at the ambulance	Zero Touch Onboarding, Enhanced MUD Profile Server, ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base, Conformity Certificate Issuance, Runtime Attestation	M36
UC3.S1.US2	As a Security Administrator, I would like to assess the trustworthiness of the CMD during runtime and issue Conformity Certificates based on the collected verifiable evidence.	Runtime attestation, Trust Controls, Certification & Auditing, SW/FW Verification, Digital Twin	M24
UC3.S1.US3	As a Security Administrator, I would like to assess the trustworthy state of the gateway and enforce a SW update in case of a security incident.	Dynamic Trust Assessment, Runtime Attestation, AI-based Anomaly Detection, Secure SW/FW Update, SW/FW Verification Component	M24
UC3.S1.US4	As a Security Administrator, I would like to be notified if suspicious or malicious behaviour is detected in the gateway, isolating the gateway from the network	Dynamic Trust Assessment, Risk Assessment, Runtime Attestation, AI-based Anomaly Detection, Conformity Certificate Manager, ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure	M36
UC3.S1.US5	As a Medical Doctor, I would like to receive patient data from ambulances only if meeting the hospital's security requirements and trust policies.	ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure, Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC), Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE)	M36

Table 4.9: PARTICLE use case (UC3.1) user stories

Id	UC3.S1 .US1	UC3.S1 .US2	UC3.S1 .US3	UC3.S1 .US4	UC3.S1 .US5	Id	UC3.S1 .US1	UC3.S1 .US2	UC3.S1 .US3	UC3.S1 .US4	UC3.S1 .US5
Functional Requirements						Security Requirements					
FR_1		X	X	X		SR_1	X				X
FR_2		X	X	X		SR_2	X			X	X
FR_3					X	SR_3		X	X	X	
FR_4					X	SR_4		X		X	X
FR_5				X	X	SR_5			X		
FR_6	X				X	SR_6		X	X	X	
FR_7				X	X	SR_7					X
FR_8					X	SR_8					X
FR_9		X	X		X	SR_9	X		X		
FR_10					X	SR_10	X				
FR_11			X	X		SR_11	X				
FR_12			X			SR_12	X		X		
FR_13		X	X			SR_13					
FR_14		X	X	X		SR_14	X			X	
FR_15	X	X	X	X		SR_15			X	X	
FR_16		X	X	X		SR_16	X				
FR_17			X	X		SR_17	X				
FR_18			X	X		SR_18		X			X

FR_19	X					SR_19		X				
FR_20			X	X		Operational Requirements						
FR_21	X				X	OR_1	X					X
FR_22		X	X	X		OR_2	X					X
FR_23		X	X			OR_3				X		X
FR_24			X			OR_4						
FR_25	X	X	X			OR_5						
FR_26			X			OR_6				X		
FR_27			X	X		OR_7				X		
FR_28			X	X		OR_8	X			X		
FR_29			X	X		OR_9		X				
FR_30	X					OR_10				X		
FR_31	X					OR_11				X		
FR_32						OR_12						
						OR_13	X					
						OR_14		X	X	X		
						OR_15						
						OR_16		X				
						OR_17	X				X	
						OR_18						X
						OR_19						X
						OR_20						X

Table 4.10: Mapping of ENTRUST requirements to the user stories of the PARTICLE demonstrator

Id	Description	ENTRUST Functionalities	Demonstration
UC3.S1.US1	As a Security Administrator, I would like to assess the network of the medical organization to identify threats and vulnerabilities related to the interconnected nature of the devices.	ENTRUST Risk Assessment, Threat Modelling, MUD Server	M24
UC3.S1.US2	As a Security Administrator, I want to securely have access to the health state information of a CMD, in order to be able to predict any maintenance and management control actions	ENTRUST Attestation Agent, Tracing Capabilities, Blockchain Infrastructure, Verifiable Credentials Management, Attribute-based Access Control, Digital Twin, Attack Emulation Engine	M24 (M36)
UC3.S1.US3	As a Security Administrator, I would like to be able to do a SWARM attestation, dynamically change the topology of CMDs infrastructure, dynamically add/decommissioning CMDs	ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base, Attestation Agent, Zero Touch Onboarding, Swarm Attestation, Tracing Capabilities	M36
UC3.S1.US4	As a Security Administrator, I want to be able to enforce authenticated system updates in an efficient and scalable manner as a result to newly identified vulnerabilities in the deployed medical software stack	ENTRUST Trust Assessment, Digital Twin, SW/FW Update Process, AI-based Anomaly Detection, Attack Emulation Engine, SW/FW Verification Component	M24 (M36)
UC3.S1.US5	As a Security Administrator, I would like to be able to efficiently monitor the security and trustworthiness state of a fleet of low-End devices and correctly map my security solutions based on up-to-date secure risk assessment, in order to always employ optimised security policies	ENTRUST Trust Assessment, Zero Touch Onboarding, Tracing Capabilities, Conformity Certificates Management, Attestation Agent	M24

UC3.S1.US6	As a Security Administrator, I want to ensure that monitored healthcare data can be disclosed to entities with the appropriate privileges and trust properties	ENTRUST Verifiable Credentials Management, Attribute-based Access Control, Self-Sovereign Identity, Privacy-Preserving Attribute-based Credential	M36
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Table 4.11: POLARIS use case (UC3.2) user stories

Id	UC3.S2.US1	UC3.S2.US2	UC3.S2.US3	UC3.S2.US4	UC3.S2.US5	UC3.S2.US6	Id	UC3.S2.US1	UC3.S2.US2	UC3.S2.US3	UC3.S2.US4	UC3.S2.US5	UC3.S2.US6
Functional Requirements							Security Requirements						
FR_1	X				X		SR_1		X		X		X
FR_2	X				X		SR_2		X		X		
FR_3				X	X		SR_3				X		
FR_4	X			X	X		SR_4				X		
FR_5	X			X	X		SR_5		X		X		X
FR_6	X		X		X		SR_6	X				X	
FR_7	X				X		SR_7						
FR_8				X			SR_8						X
FR_9				X			SR_9						
FR_10				X			SR_10						
FR_11	X						SR_11						
FR_12		X	X	X		X	SR_12						
FR_13		X	X		X		SR_13			X		X	
FR_14			X		X		SR_14						
FR_15			X	X	X		SR_15			X			
FR_16			X		X		SR_16						
FR_17		X					SR_17						
FR_18				X	X		SR_18				X		
FR_19		X		X		X	SR_19				X		
FR_20		X		X	X	X	Operational Requirements						
FR_21							OR_1						
FR_22					X		OR_2						X
FR_23		X		X			OR_3	X					
FR_24		X				X	OR_4	X				X	
FR_25		X				X	OR_5	X					
FR_26		X				X	OR_6						
FR_27							OR_7	X		X			
FR_28							OR_8				X		
FR_29							OR_9				X		
FR_30			X				OR_10				X	X	
FR_31			X				OR_11					X	
FR_32		X				X	OR_12					X	
							OR_13						
							OR_14		X		X		
							OR_15	X					
							OR_16					X	
							OR_17	X					X
							OR_18						
							OR_19						
							OR_20					X	X

Table 4.12: Mapping of ENTRUST requirements to the user stories of the POLARIS demonstrator

Id	Description	ENTRUST Functionalities	Demonstration
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SL.US1	As a Security Administrator, I would like to ensure the secure onboarding of the gateway device.	Zero Touch Onboarding, Enhanced MUD Profile Server, ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base, Conformity Certificate Issuance, Runtime Attestation	M24
SL.US2	As a Security Administrator, I would like to assess the trustworthy state of the gateway device during its entire lifetime and to ensure its integrity.	Dynamic Trust Assessment, Risk Assessment, Runtime Attestation, AI-based Anomaly Detection, Conformity Certificate Manager, ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure	M24
SL.US3	As a Security Administrator, I would like to enforce a remote FW update in case of a security incident.	Dynamic Trust Assessment, Runtime Attestation, AI-based Anomaly Detection, Secure SW/FW Update, SW/FW Verification Component	M24
SL.US4	As a Security Administrator, I would like to calculate the trustworthiness of data produced and exchanged throughout the entire chain of the medical stakeholders, given multiple trust sources.	AI-based Misbehaviour Detection, Calculation of trust level from multiple trust sources	M36

Table 4.13: Sentio Labs use case (UC4) user stories

Id	SL.US1	SL.US2	SL.US3	SL.US4	Id	SL.US1	SL.US2	SL.US3	SL.US4
Functional Requirements					Security Requirements				
FR_1					SR_1	X		X	
FR_2					SR_2	X		X	X
FR_3			X		SR_3		X	X	
FR_4			X		SR_4			X	
FR_5		X	X		SR_5		X	X	X
FR_6	X				SR_6		X		
FR_7					SR_7				
FR_8		X	X		SR_8				X
FR_9		X	X		SR_9	X			
FR_10			X		SR_10	X			
FR_11		X			SR_11	X			
FR_12			X		SR_12	X			
FR_13		X		X	SR_13		X		X
FR_14		X			SR_14	X			
FR_15	X	X	X		SR_15				
FR_16		X		X	SR_16	X	X		X
FR_17		X		X	SR_17	X			
FR_18			X		SR_18			X	
FR_19	X		X		SR_19			X	
FR_20			X		Operational Requirements				
FR_21	X			X	OR_1	X			
FR_22		X			OR_2	X			
FR_23			X		OR_3		X		
FR_24					OR_4				
FR_25	X				OR_5				
FR_26					OR_6				
FR_27					OR_7				
FR_28					OR_8	X		X	
FR_29					OR_9			X	
FR_30	X	X		X	OR_10		X	X	
FR_31	X	X		X	OR_11				
FR_32					OR_12				
					OR_13	X			

	OR_14			X	
	OR_15				X
	OR_16			X	
	OR_17	X			
	OR_18				
	OR_19				
	OR_20			X	

Table 4.14: Mapping of ENTRUST requirements to the user stories of the Sentio Labs demonstrator

The ENTRUST MVP, shown in Table 4.15, depicts the shared vision of the consortium regarding the definition of the core set of requirements of ENTRUST. A necessary step towards defining the ENTRUST MVP is the prioritization of the identified requirements based on the involvement of the use case demonstrators, which is crucial towards guiding the definition of the core functionalities of the ENTRUST framework. Thus, the Table provides the mapping between requirements of the MVP and their applicability per use case, towards achieving their categorization as "must have" and "should have".

Id	Present in all UCs	Present in UC1 (Kardiner)	Present in UC2 (TELLU)	Present in UC3.1 (PARTICLE)	Present in UC3.2 (POLARIS)	Present in UC4 (Sentio)
Functional Requirements						
FR_1		X(2)	X(2)	X(3)	X(2)	
FR_2		X(2)	X(2)	X(3)	X(2)	
FR_3		X(2)		X(1)	X(2)	X(1)
FR_4		X(1)		X(1)	X(3)	X(1)
FR_5		X(2)		X(2)	X(3)	X(2)
FR_6			X(2)	X(2)	X(3)	X(1)
FR_7		X(3)		X(2)	X(2)	
FR_8		X(2)		X(1)	X(1)	X(2)
FR_9		X(2)	X(2)	X(3)	X(1)	X(2)
FR_10		X(2)		X(1)	X(1)	X(1)
FR_11	X	X(2)	X(1)	X(2)	X(1)	X(1)
FR_12	X	X(3)	X(1)	X(1)	X(4)	X(1)
FR_13	X	X(2)	X(2)	X(2)	X(3)	X(2)
FR_14	X	X(1)	X(2)	X(3)	X(2)	X(1)
FR_15	X	X(2)	X(4)	X(4)	X(3)	X(3)
FR_16	X	X(2)	X(2)	X(3)	X(2)	X(2)
FR_17	X	X(2)	X(1)	X(2)	X(1)	X(2)
FR_18	X	X(2)	X(1)	X(2)	X(2)	X(1)
FR_19	X	X(2)	X(2)	X(1)	X(3)	X(2)
FR_20	X	X(4)	X(1)	X(2)	X(4)	X(1)
FR_21		X(2)	X(2)	X(2)		X(2)
FR_22	X	X(2)	X(2)	X(2)	X(1)	X(1)
FR_23	X	X(2)	X(2)	X(2)	X(2)	X(1)
FR_24		X(3)	X(1)	X(1)	X(2)	
FR_25	X	X(3)	X(4)	X(3)	X(2)	X(1)
FR_26		X(2)	X(1)	X(1)	X(2)	
FR_27		X(1)	X(1)	X(2)		
FR_28		X(1)	X(1)	X(2)		
FR_29		X(1)	X(1)	X(2)		
FR_30	X	X(3)	X(2)	X(1)	X(1)	X(3)
FR_31	X	X(3)	X(2)	X(1)	X(1)	X(3)
FR_32		X(2)			X(2)	
Security Requirements						
SR_1	X	X(1)	X(2)	X(2)	X(3)	X(2)
SR_2	X	X(1)	X(2)	X(3)	X(2)	X(3)
SR_3	X	X(2)	X(2)	X(3)	X(1)	X(2)
SR_4	X	X(1)	X(1)	X(3)	X(1)	X(1)

SR_5	X	X(3)	X(1)	X(1)	X(3)	X(3)
SR_6	X	X(2)	X(2)	X(3)	X(2)	X(1)
SR_7			X(1)	X(1)		
SR_8		X(2)		X(1)	X(1)	X(1)
SR_9		X(1)	X(3)	X(2)		X(1)
SR_10		X(1)	X(2)	X(1)		X(1)
SR_11		X(1)	X(2)	X(1)		X(1)
SR_12		X(2)	X(3)	X(2)		X(1)
SR_13					X(2)	X(2)
SR_14		X(1)	X(2)	X(2)		X(2)
SR_15		X(1)	X(1)	X(2)	X(1)	
SR_16		X(3)	X(2)	X(1)		X(3)
SR_17		X(1)	X(2)	X(1)		X(1)
SR_18	X	X(1)	X(1)	X(2)	X(1)	X(1)
SR_19	X	X(1)	X(1)	X(1)	X(1)	X(1)
Operational Requirements						
OR_1		X(1)	X(2)	X(2)		X(1)
OR_2			X(2)	X(2)	X(1)	X(1)
OR_3		X(1)		X(2)	X(1)	X(1)
OR_4					X(2)	
OR_5		X(1)			X(1)	
OR_6		X(1)		X(1)		
OR_7		X(1)		X(1)	X(2)	
OR_8	X	X(1)	X(2)	X(2)	X(1)	X(2)
OR_9	X	X(1)	X(1)	X(1)	X(1)	X(1)
OR_10		X(1)		X(1)	X(2)	X(2)
OR_11		X(2)		X(1)	X(1)	
OR_12					X(1)	
OR_13			X(1)	X(1)		X(1)
OR_14	X	X(3)	X(2)	X(3)	X(2)	X(1)
OR_15		X(1)			X(1)	X(1)
OR_16	X	X(1)	X(1)	X(1)	X(1)	X(1)
OR_17			X(2)	X(2)	X(2)	X(1)
OR_18				X(1)		
OR_19				X(1)		
OR_20		X(1)		X(1)	X(2)	X(1)

Table 4.15: ENTRUST MVP

Thus, the ENTRUST MVP consists of **27 "must-have" requirements** and **44 "should-have" requirements**. The former are suggested as the initial core requirements for the delivery of the platform and are deemed the most important ones, as they are pertinent in all use case demonstrators. However, the goal of the consortium is the validation of all identified requirements based on the defined KPIs, which have been provided in Section 4.4 and will be evaluated in the context of D6.1.

Chapter 5

Threat Landscape and ENTRUST Countermeasures

In continuation to the previous Chapter, as well as the attack profiling and threat definition performed in D2.1 [5], here we perform a complete attack profiling of the healthcare domain in order to better motivate and position the need of a complex security solution. In this regard, the core motivation of ENTRUST is to offer a dynamic Trust Assessment framework that aims to not only cover the requirements of medical domain applications, but also go beyond healthcare by being applicable to other application domains. In this context, we first aim to answer the question: *Is there a need to employ and instantiate more advanced Trust Assessment protocols in the healthcare domain?* To answer this question, we first need to consider the most prominent types of threats affecting modern supply chain ecosystems, and to then determine whether they are applicable to actual, real-world medical application scenarios, based on feedback from the use case demonstrators of ENTRUST. This will demonstrate the ability of ENTRUST to not only handle such threats in medical domain ecosystems, but also to address threats that may be present in various other application domains.

To answer the aforementioned question, we follow a **top-to-bottom methodology** for the construction of the threat landscape of ENTRUST, which will culminate into the demonstration of the applicability of ENTRUST in actual medical domain organizations based on the identified threats. At the top of this methodology, as demonstrated in Table 5.1, we start with the **Top 10 Mobile Risks** of 2024 as identified by the **Open Worldwide Application Security Project (OWASP)** [4], which constitutes a generic list of threats and vulnerabilities affecting systems regardless of the application domain they belong to. In this Table, we also list the functionalities of ENTRUST that are able to address each one of these categories of threats and vulnerabilities, thus highlighting its applicability in addressing multi-domain threats and attacks.

Next, we proceed with the attack profiling process by expanding this list to be made specific to the healthcare domain. Specifically, in Section 5.1, we list the most prominent attacks affecting medical and healthcare organizations, as documented by the **Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG)**, with focus on the impact on the safety of patient data. This results in a full attack profiling of the healthcare domain, considering the latest types of threats affecting such large-scale Systems-of-Systems (SoS). Afterwards, in Section 5.2, the aforementioned aspects converge into the mapping of the medical domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities with the corresponding OWASP-identified threats, as well as the identification of the **types of trustworthiness evidence** that need to be monitored in order to support the **safety and security controls** that can be used for the mitigation of these threats.

Finally, in the remainder of this Chapter, we flesh out the identified medical domain threats with **realistic threat examples in the context of the use case demonstrators of ENTRUST, based on actual**

encountered incidents by the use case partners, which will also drive the experimentation and evaluation plan to be documented in D6.1 [9]. Thus, the identified security requirements were driven by realistic threats and vulnerabilities exposed by CMDs purchased and operated by actual medical organizations. Essentially, the main question that drive the extraction of such requirements is *to what extent the transition to more automated healthcare provision comprising medical service graph chains may introduce new security gaps that can compromise the security of the citizens?* As a result of all the above, we achieve a complete attack profiling considering gaps at each layer of the CMD continuum, from the far edge medical device all the way up to the backend services.

ID	OWASP Top 10 Mobile Risks	ENTRUST Functionalities
M1	Improper Credential Usage	ENTRUST provides advanced mechanisms for the protection of credentials, so that they are only able to be used by the medical devices or users for which they are used. This is achieved by adopting Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) mechanisms in order to connect the identity of the user to their credentials in a secure and trustworthy manner with strong trustworthiness guarantees, as well as capabilities for detecting improper credential usage, as detailed in D4.2 [7].
M2	Inadequate Supply Chain Security	ENTRUST is able to provide supply chain security throughout the operational lifecycle of devices operating within the medical domain through a variety of operations (zero-touch onboarding, revocation, recommissioning, etc.), by leveraging the notion of MUD profiles (defined in D3.2 [6]) and also including threat information provided by the CMD Manufacturer. It also extends this definition to include domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities when the device is deployed to the target medical domain.
M3	Insecure Authentication/Authorization	ENTRUST provides the capability for the authentication and authorization of users and CMDs with strong trustworthiness guarantees. To this end, as detailed in D4.2 [7] ENTRUST supports the issuance of Verifiable Presentations (VPs) protected through the use of hardware-based keys (Root ID keys) for binding the VPs to the specific CMD and the associated set of attributes. This allows for continuous authentication, authorization, and access control based on VPs embodying security claims as attributes.
M4	Insufficient Input/Output Validation	This risk is associated with insufficient I/O validation leading to exposing the CMD to critical attack vectors (outlined in Section 5.1). In ENTRUST, this is captured with novel trust extensions (such as attestation mechanisms, detailed in D4.2 [7]) where we can verify the correctness of not only these I/O mechanisms, but also the behaviour of the devices themselves, to ensure that they they are protected against the identified attack vectors.
M5	Insecure Communication	The establishment of secure communication is part of the Trust Assessment process of ENTRUST for establishing secure lifecycle management. This starts from the secure and trust-aware Zero-Touch Onboarding (ZTO), and based on this, provides runtime trust establishment, authentication, and maintenance through advanced cryptographic agility tools, with strong guarantees on the security of the communication and integrity of the exchanged data. Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC), described in D4.2 [7], is used to prove ownership of attributes for enabling symmetric key establishment. Thus, ENTRUST provides mechanisms for ensuring secure communication and bootstrapping of trust for CMDs, either within the same medical service graph chain, or for cross-domain communication.
M6	Inadequate Privacy Controls	ENTRUST aims to ensure the privacy of users and devices in the context of selective disclosure, by enabling them to only share the specific set of attributes needed in order to access a service or set of data. Thus, ENTRUST provides a crypto agility layer (described in D4.2 [7]) with capabilities for providing privacy-preserving properties to various operations. For instance, in the creation of the Conformity Certificates, Privacy Attribute-Based Credentials (pABCs) are used for enabling sharing device attributes related to the collected trust evidence in a privacy-preserving manner. In addition, CMDs are able to create Verifiable Presentations (VP) as a subset of their VC, containing only the specific attributes that are needed. In addition, ENTRUST provides zero-knowledge signatures that can be used in tandem with the FHIR standard [1], so that doctors are able to process patient data without disclosing any identifiable information about the patients, thus achieving privacy requirements in data provenance.

M7	Insufficient Binary Protections	This risk is related to attacks on app binaries, aiming to compromise the integrity of the CMD software, for instance through the inclusion of malicious code. To this end, ENTRUST provides runtime attestation schemes, such as Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) (D4.2 [7]) for ensuring the integrity of the binaries and the CMD configuration dynamically during runtime, and Swarm Attestation for attesting multiple devices simultaneously in an efficient manner. In addition, the AI-based Misbehaviour Detection component (described in D3.2 [6]) is able to detect anomalies in the behavior of the devices so that new risks and vulnerabilities are identified.
M8	Security Misconfiguration	ENTRUST is able to continuously assess the security configuration and execution of the components and devices belonging to a medical domain infrastructure, and deploy the appropriate mitigation measures for any identified threats or vulnerabilities. This is achieved through the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) of ENTRUST (described in D3.2 [6]), which is able to employ Trust Models (TMs) capturing all the possible types of trust relationships between assets of the medical domain belonging to the entire Service Graph Chain (SGC). Note that the TM leverages Manufacturer-specific information, provided through the Manufacturer MUD. Then, the runtime trustworthiness assessment of CMDs is performed through the calculation of their Actual Trust Level (ATL) based on the data collected by the available Trust Sources (e.g., attestation enablers, AI-based Misbehaviour Detection, Digital Twin, etc.).
M9	Insecure Data Storage	ENTRUST provides the capability to store data in a manner that only enables users and stakeholders with the appropriate permissions to decrypt the data (detailed in D5.1 [8]). To this end, it employs an Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE) scheme to enable the secure storage of encrypted information (e.g., attestation raw traces), so that they can only be decrypted through the demonstration of a VP containing the required attributes. This is supported by the ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base (TCB), which provides the required trustworthiness guarantees to these operations. As part of secure storage, ENTRUST is also one of the first projects of its kind to demonstrate the applicability of integrating lightweight Roots-of-Trust (RoTs) in low-end and high-end devices. Specifically, we use Trusted Execution Environment (TEEs) for providing secure storage, and Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) for secure key management that can enable secure storage (which is a core innovation of ENTRUST).
M10	Insufficient Cryptography	ENTRUST not only adopts standardized crypto schemes for supporting the offered security enablers, but also provides a crypto toolbox (analyzed in D4.2 [7]) featuring a wide gamut of crypto enablers, such as Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV), Attribute-Based Signatures (ABS), and Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC). These schemes can be formally verified not only through the Formal Verification component of ENTRUST, but are also validated through complete mathematically rigorous security proofs.

Table 5.1: ENTRUST functionalities for mitigation of OWASP Top 10 Mobile Risks

5.1 Attack Profiling in CMD Ecosystems

As part of the aforementioned top-to-bottom methodology, in Table 5.9 we provide a list of MDCG-identified threats documented by the MDCG, as well as a description of the process that may be followed by a malicious party in order to capitalize on each threat. Then, we provide details on the **properties that may be violated** by each threat, as well as the **safety and security impact** of each threat on medical ecosystems. This will provide the basis for the identification of the appropriate security controls and corresponding trustworthiness evidence for the mitigation of these threats to be documented in the next Section.

Table 5.2: Attack Profiling in CMD Ecosystems¹

Attack Profiling in CMD Ecosystems	
Threat-1	Custom malware on the external programmer

Description	The identified threat, 'Custom malware on the external programmer', in the case of the Sentio Labs use case, may lead to incorrect analysis of the data collected by the Feel Emotion Sensor (FES) at the side of the Feel Mobile Application. Thus, this vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing unintended stimulation or inability to adjust settings, leading to incorrect therapy outcomes.
Property violation	IT Security Architecture
Safety Impact	Unintended stimulation or inability to adjust settings, leading to incorrect therapy outcomes.
Security Impact	Unauthenticated access to device firmware leading to potential data breaches.
Threat-2	Unauthorized adjustment of therapy settings
Description	The identified threat, 'Unauthorized adjustment of therapy settings', involves a potential breach impacting low-end CMDs, such as the KardinBLU device. This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing incorrect therapy adjustments due to incorrect data (e.g., ECG, SpO2 levels, temperature) transmitted, thus causing harm to the patient.
Property violation	Identity and Access Management
Safety Impact	Incorrect therapy adjustments causing harm to the patient.
Security Impact	Unauthorized therapy adjustments compromising patient treatment efficacy.
Threat-3	Data modification in transit causing misdiagnosis
Description	The identified threat, 'Data modification in transit causing misdiagnosis', involves a potential breach impacting low-end CMDs. In the PARTICLE smart ambulance use case, this may lead to the incorrect transmission of data collected by low-end devices (e.g., KardinBLU or Benevision N1 MD) from the ambulance to the hospital backend, which could compromise patient safety by causing misdiagnosis affecting critical care decisions and worsening the patient's condition.
Property violation	Cryptography
Safety Impact	Misdiagnosis affecting critical care decisions and worsening the patient's condition.
Security Impact	Compromised data integrity resulting in incorrect medical decisions.
Threat-4	Overwhelming requests causing device fatigue and battery depletion
Description	The identified threat, 'Overwhelming requests causing device fatigue and battery depletion', involves a potential breach impacting low-end devices, such as the KardinBLU in the Kardinero use case. This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing reduced availability of life-critical devices due to early battery depletion.
Property violation	IT Security Administration
Safety Impact	Reduced availability of life-critical devices due to early battery depletion.
Security Impact	Device unavailability due to resource exhaustion, impacting patient care.
Threat-5	Unauthorized reconfiguration leading to incorrect infusion
Description	The identified threat, 'Unauthorized reconfiguration leading to incorrect infusion', involves a potential breach impacting healthcare quality in a hospital setting. For instance, in the POLARIS Emergency Care Unit use case, incorrect data from the Econet Compact 7 device may lead to incorrect infusion dosage (e.g., by a smart infusion pump) with potentially severe health consequences.

Property violation	Identity and Access Management
Safety Impact	Incorrect infusion dosage with potentially severe health consequences.
Security Impact	Critical treatment errors caused by incorrect device configurations.
Threat-6	Network-spread malware (e.g., worm) encrypting hard drive content
Description	The identified threat, 'Network-spread malware (e.g., worm) encrypting hard drive content', involves a potential breach impacting the any medical device employing storage units, such as the backend servers in the PARTICLE Smart Ambulance, the POLARIS Emergency Care Unit, and the Tellu Remote Patient Monitoring system. This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing critical healthcare systems rendered inoperable due to encrypted data.
Property violation	Incident Management and Response
Safety Impact	Critical healthcare systems rendered inoperable due to encrypted data.
Security Impact	System inoperability due to widespread malware infection.
Threat-7	Weak passwords guessed for physical access
Description	The identified threat, 'Weak passwords guessed for physical access', involves a potential breach impacting any system that may rely on password access, such as computers functioning as backend servers in the aforementioned use cases. This may lead to loss of critical patient data, thus impacting the capability of healthcare provision. Also, the use of weak passwords may enable a malevolent user to take access to the system and perform unintended software update, thus opening the path to multiple new attack vectors.
Property violation	Physical and Environmental Security
Safety Impact	Tampering of stored patient data, endangering patient safety.
Security Impact	Compromised physical access allowing tampering with device settings.
Threat-8	Export of sensitive patient data via USB due to weak passwords
Description	The identified threat, 'Export of sensitive patient data via USB due to weak passwords', involves a potential breach impacting any case where USB devices are used for transporting patient data (e.g., patient data processed by the TelluCare cloud platform). This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing privacy violations and potential misuse of sensitive data.
Property violation	Identity and Access Management
Safety Impact	Privacy violations and potential misuse of sensitive data.
Security Impact	Unauthorized export of sensitive patient data leading to privacy violations.
Threat-9	Flooding network interface with malformed requests causing crashes
Description	The identified threat, 'Flooding network interface with malformed requests causing crashes', involves a potential breach that may impact complex medical domain ecosystems where the transmission of large amounts of data in a time-sensitive manner, such as Smart Ambulance settings where several ambulances aim to transmit data to several different hospitals. Also, in hospital or operating floor settings, this could affect the collaboration and cooperation capability of devices, as flooding the network with meaningless data may cause additional overhead and affect the composability of the medical service graph chain. This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing critical downtime during medical procedures due to system crashes.
Property violation	IT Security Architecture
Safety Impact	Critical downtime during medical procedures due to system crashes.

Security Impact	Disrupted medical procedures caused by system crashes.
Threat-10	Eavesdropping on communication between patient monitor and central system
Description	The identified threat, 'Eavesdropping on communication between patient monitor and central system', involves a potential breach where a low-end sensor device transmits data to a high-end device for medical processing (such as the communication between the Feel Emotion Sensor and the mobile device where the Feel Mobile Application is running, in the Sentio Labs use case). This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing unauthorized access to sensitive health data, such as mental health-related data in the Sentio Labs use case.
Property violation	Cryptography
Safety Impact	Unauthorized access to sensitive health data leading to breaches.
Security Impact	Eavesdropping on sensitive data leading to privacy breaches.
Threat-11	Malware installed via USB access
Description	The identified threat, 'Malware installed via USB access', involves a potential breach impacting any device where data is shared via USB device (for instance, in cases where a doctor receives patient data collected at the Tellu-Care platform). This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing loss of device functionality leading to risks in patient safety.
Property violation	Physical and Environmental Security
Safety Impact	Loss of device functionality leading to risks in patient safety.
Security Impact	Malware infection causing loss of critical device functionality.
Threat-12	Manipulation of ventilator alarm messages sent to central system
Description	The identified threat, 'Manipulation of ventilator alarm messages sent to central system', involves a potential breach impacting monitoring systems, such as alarm systems in a hospital setting in the POLARIS Emergency Care Unit use case. This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing delayed emergency responses due to manipulated alarm systems.
Property violation	Detection and Logging
Safety Impact	Delayed emergency responses due to manipulated alarm systems.
Security Impact	Manipulated alarm messages delaying emergency responses.
Threat-13	Manipulation of PACS network traffic to falsify medical images
Description	The identified threat, 'Manipulation of Picture archiving and communication system (PACS) network traffic to falsify medical images', involves a potential breach impacting the PACS, which may be used as an imaging system in a hospital setting, such as the POLARIS Emergency Care Unit use case. This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing false diagnoses due to tampered PACS images.
Property violation	IT Security Architecture
Safety Impact	False diagnoses due to tampered PACS images.
Security Impact	Falsified medical images leading to misdiagnosis or incorrect treatments.
Threat-14	Ransomware attack encrypting PACS systems
Description	The identified threat, 'Ransomware attack encrypting PACS systems', involves a potential breach impacting the PACS, which may be used in an Emergency Care Unit hospital setting. This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing delayed medical decisions due to unavailability of PACS systems.

Property violation	Resilience and Recovery
Safety Impact	Delayed medical decisions due to unavailability of PACS systems.
Security Impact	Unavailability of PACS systems due to ransomware attacks, delaying medical decisions.
Threat-15	Exploitation of legacy third-party components
Description	The identified threat, 'Exploitation of legacy third-party components', involves a potential breach impacting legacy components in hospital environments, such as the low-end Econet Compact 7 legacy CMD employed in the POLARIS Emergency Care Unit test case. This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing increased risk from unpatched vulnerabilities in critical systems.
Property violation	IT Security Maintenance
Safety Impact	Increased risk from unpatched vulnerabilities in critical systems.
Security Impact	Exploitation of outdated systems leading to increased vulnerability to attacks.
Threat-16	Malicious DICOM objects spreading malware across systems
Description	The identified threat, 'Malicious DICOM (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine) objects spreading malware across systems', involves a potential breach impacting imaging systems used in hospital settings (e.g., X-ray Machine, PACS). This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing delays in operations due to compromised system integrity.
Property violation	IT Security Maintenance
Safety Impact	Delays in operations due to compromised system integrity.
Security Impact	Compromised system integrity due to malicious DICOM objects, disrupting operations.
Threat-17	Ransomware causing shutdown of non-isolated systems
Description	The identified threat, 'Ransomware causing shutdown of non-isolated systems', involves a potential breach impacting high-end gateway devices, such as the Tellu Personal Health Gateway (PHG). This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing widespread disruption of interconnected systems, by making low-end devices incapable to transmit their data to their parent high-end devices.
Property violation	Incident Management and Response
Safety Impact	Widespread disruption of interconnected systems.
Security Impact	Widespread disruption of interventional systems caused by ransomware.
Threat-18	Employee stealing data using USB storage
Description	The identified threat, 'Employee stealing data using USB storage', involves a potential breach impacting any case where medical data is transported via a physical USB device. This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing unauthorized data extraction and breaches of sensitive information.
Property violation	Human Resource Security
Safety Impact	Unauthorized data extraction and breaches of sensitive information.
Security Impact	Unauthorized data extraction leading to privacy violations and data misuse.
Threat-19	Network-based malware leading to blue screen on devices

Description	The identified threat, 'Network-based malware leading to blue screen on devices', involves a potential breach impacting any network-connected computer, such as backend servers (e.g., hospital backend server in the Smart Ambulance or Emergency Care Unit use cases). This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing delays in critical diagnostics affecting treatment timelines.
Property violation	Detection and Logging
Safety Impact	Delays in critical diagnostics affecting treatment timelines.
Security Impact	System crashes due to network-based malware, delaying critical diagnostics.
Threat-20	Unauthorized router configuration causing loss of connectivity
Description	The identified threat, 'Unauthorized router configuration causing loss of connectivity', involves a potential breach impacting any case which relies on a router for the transmission of data, such as the transmission of data from the Tellu Personal Health Gateway to the backend over the internet. This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing loss of operational control impacting healthcare services.
Property violation	Ecosystem Management
Safety Impact	Loss of operational control impacting healthcare services.
Security Impact	Loss of connectivity due to unauthorized router configurations, disrupting workflows.
Threat-21	Compromised interventional systems due to worm or ransomware
Description	The identified threat, 'Compromised interventional systems due to worm or ransomware', involves a potential breach impacting the Interventional Systems, such as the Tellu PHG, where medical intervention may be required based on feedback from the TelluCare Platform. This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing significant delays in diagnostics or treatment.
Property violation	Resilience and Recovery
Safety Impact	Significant delays in diagnostics or treatment.
Security Impact	Interventional systems rendered inoperable due to ransomware or worm infections.
Threat-22	Contaminated system with reduced performance (e.g., slowed operations)
Description	The identified threat, 'Contaminated system with reduced performance (e.g., slowed operations)', involves a potential breach impacting the high-end devices that may need to perform computationally intensive operations, such as the Tellu PHG. This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing reduced efficiency in life-critical diagnostic systems.
Property violation	IT Security Maintenance
Safety Impact	Reduced efficiency in life-critical diagnostic systems.
Security Impact	Reduced system performance hindering critical diagnostic processes.
Threat-23	Use of outdated or unsupported third-party components

Description	The identified threat, 'Use of outdated or unsupported third-party components', involves a potential breach impacting the Medical Devices using legacy systems (such as the Econet Compact 7 device in the Emergency Care Unit use case). This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing increased risk of exploitation due to unpatched vulnerabilities, leading to potential device failure or incorrect functioning during critical operations.
Property violation	IT Security Maintenance
Safety Impact	Increased risk of exploitation due to unpatched vulnerabilities, leading to potential device failure or incorrect functioning during critical operations.
Security Impact	Device failures caused by the use of outdated third-party components.
Threat-24	Unauthorized physical access to a device resulting in system configuration changes
Description	The identified threat, 'Unauthorized physical access to a device resulting in system configuration changes', involves a potential breach impacting any medical device where a malicious party may have physical access, such as the Econec Compact 7 device in a hospital setting in the Emergency Care Unit use case. This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing incorrect device configurations can result in unsafe operating parameters, endangering patient safety.
Property violation	Physical and Environmental Security
Safety Impact	Incorrect device configurations can result in unsafe operating parameters, endangering patient safety
Security Impact	Unsafe device configurations due to unauthorized physical access.
Threat-25	Tampering with medical workflows or stored data
Description	The identified threat, 'Tampering with medical workflows or stored data', involves a potential breach impacting the Medical workflows and stored data systems, such as the ones performed by the TelluCare platform based on patient data received from the Tellu PHG. This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing altered workflows or data can lead to incorrect diagnoses, improper treatment plans, or delays in critical decision-making.
Property violation	Detection and Logging
Safety Impact	Altered workflows or data can lead to incorrect diagnoses, improper treatment plans, or delays in critical decision-making.
Security Impact	Altered medical workflows leading to incorrect diagnoses or delayed treatments.
Threat-26	Lack of a structured incident response plan
Description	The identified threat, 'Lack of a structured incident response plan', involves a potential breach impacting the Healthcare IT systems, which is applicable in all use case demonstrators relying on a server backend system (e.g., PARTICLE Cloud Server, POLARIC BMC Server, TelluCare platform). This vulnerability could compromise patient safety by causing delayed responses to security incidents could result in prolonged device unavailability, indirectly affecting patient care.
Property violation	Incident Management and Response
Safety Impact	Delayed responses to security incidents could result in prolonged device unavailability, indirectly affecting patient care.

Security Impact	Delayed responses to incidents prolonging device unavailability and affecting care.
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5.2 Mapping of Security and Safety Controls to Evidence

As outlined in D3.2 [6] regarding the Trust Assessment process, when new attacks are identified for a CMD, we need to identify the **safety and security controls** that are able to **decrease the impact** of those attacks on the CMD. The types of identified threats, in tandem with the available safety and security controls, provide the basis for the calculation of the **Required Trust Level (RTL)** of the device. In addition, we need to identify the **Trust Sources** and the corresponding **types of trustworthiness evidence** they provide as output. In this context, evidence refers to the output of the Trust Sources, which is afterwards given as input to the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)**, in order to provide verifiable information about the corresponding **Trust Property**. Thus, in order to assess a specific **Trust Relationship**, it is important to include the evidence that is necessary to assess the particular property. This trustworthiness evidence enables the calculation of the **Actual Trust Level (ATL)** of the CMD by the TAF during runtime. Thus, by comparing the ATL with the RTL, we are able to deduce whether the CMD is in a trustworthy state or if mitigation actions are required.

Trust on Communication	Trust on System Integrity	Trust on Application
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection mechanisms of communication (i.e., Trust Sources that provide evidence on proof of transit) • Hardware security mechanisms • Secure boot • Run-time integrity check • Known OS-vulnerabilities • Up-to-date OS/firmware • Authentic OS update • Run-time operational assurance • Known application-vulnerabilities • Trusted execution environment • Misbehaviour detection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reputation based system • Spoofing detection • Intrusion detection system (IDS) • Existence of Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) mechanism • Item definition and decomposition • Hazard analysis and risk assessment • System-level safety concept • Hardware-level safety concept • Software-level safety concept • Production and operation concepts • Validation and Verification • Identification and evaluation of hazards caused by the intended function 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification and evaluation of triggering events • Functional modification to reduce Safety Of The Intended Functionality (SOTIF)-related risks • Definition of SOTIF-related verification and validation strategy • Protection level • Integrity risk • Time to alert • Output latency

Table 5.3: Types of evidence from different types of Trust Sources

In Table 5.3, we provide a generic list of types of trust evidence, categorized on whether they quantify **trust on communication**, **trust on system integrity**, and **trust on application**. Then, building upon the results of the previous section, in Table 5.4 we provide a list of security and safety controls corresponding to each threat documented in Table 5.9. In addition, we provide the types of corresponding trustworthiness evidence that need to be collected in order to enable the operation of these safety and security controls, drawing upon the list provided in Table 5.3.

Note that, in this Table, **Item definition and decomposition** and **Hazard analysis and risk assessment** are listed under the Trust on System Integrity category. These types of evidence are not included as corresponding to specific threats, as they provide fundamental knowledge on the operation of Trust Assessment, and are thus monitored by default. Specifically, the former entails the decomposition of the

medical domain ecosystem into components and is a prerequisite for the deployment of the Trust Model, and the latter refers to the recalculation of the RTL definition dynamically during runtime in case any zero day threat or anomaly is detected.

Mapping of Security and Safety Controls to Evidence	
Threat-1	Custom malware on the external programmer
OWASP threat(s)	M4, M7
Safety Control	Enforce message authentication and prevent installation of third-party applications.
Security Control	Message authentication, prevent third-party application installation, limit access to OS.
Types of Evidence	Protection mechanisms of communication, Known OS-vulnerabilities, Up-to-date OS/firmware, Authentic OS update, Known application-vulnerabilities
Threat-2	Unauthorized adjustment of therapy settings
OWASP threat(s)	M7, M8
Safety Control	Require user authentication and enforce proximity-based access mechanisms.
Security Control	Implement user authentication; require inductive programming wand for proximity-based access.
Types of Evidence	Validation and Verification, Reputation based system, Spoofing detection, Intrusion detection system (IDS), Existence of ABAC mechanism
Threat-3	Data modification in transit causing misdiagnosis
OWASP threat(s)	M3, M5, M10
Safety Control	Use secure communication protocols (SSL/TLS) to prevent tampering.
Security Control	Use SSL/TLS encryption for secure data communication.
Types of Evidence	Protection mechanisms of communication, Encryption mechanisms
Threat-4	Overwhelming requests causing device fatigue and battery depletion
OWASP threat(s)	M2, M8
Safety Control	Deploy device management protocols to avoid resource exhaustion.
Security Control	Prevent excessive requests to avoid premature battery depletion.
Types of Evidence	Output latency, Run-time operational assurance, Known application-vulnerabilities, Spoofing detection, Intrusion detection system (IDS), Identification and evaluation of hazards caused by the intended function, Identification and evaluation of triggering events , Time to alert
Threat-5	Unauthorized reconfiguration leading to incorrect infusion
OWASP threat(s)	M3, M5, M8
Safety Control	Apply access controls and audit access logs.
Security Control	Proper definition of user types and access rights.
Types of Evidence	Existence of ABAC mechanism, Reputation based system, Spoofing detection, Intrusion detection system (IDS), Validation and Verification
Threat-6	Network-spread malware (e.g., worm) encrypting hard drive content
OWASP threat(s)	M5, M9, M10
Safety Control	Ensure robust backup systems and network segmentation.
Security Control	Disconnect affected devices from the network; ensure alternative devices are ready for use.

Types of Evidence	Run-time integrity check, Known OS-vulnerabilities, Run-time operational assurance, Known application-vulnerabilities, Misbehaviour detection, System-level safety concept, Hardware-level safety concept, Software-level safety concept, Production and operation concepts
Threat-7	Weak passwords guessed for physical access
OWASP threat(s)	M1, M3, M4
Safety Control	Implement multi-factor authentication for sensitive operations.
Security Control	Enforce strong password policies and implement role-based access controls.
Types of Evidence	Existence of ABAC mechanism, Reputation based system, Spoofing detection, Intrusion detection system (IDS), Validation and Verification, Trusted Execution Environment
Threat-8	Export of sensitive patient data via USB due to weak passwords
OWASP threat(s)	M2, M6
Safety Control	Deploy encryption for data at rest and in transit.
Security Control	Enforce password complexity policies and restrict access to USB ports.
Types of Evidence	Protection mechanisms of communication, Hardware security mechanisms, Hardware-level safety concept, Integrity risk, Trusted Execution Environment
Threat-9	Flooding network interface with malformed requests causing crashes
OWASP threat(s)	M4
Safety Control	Monitor network activity and filter abnormal traffic.
Security Control	Deploy intrusion detection/prevention systems; enhance network resilience.
Types of Evidence	Spoofing detection, Intrusion detection system (IDS), Output latency, Run-time operational assurance, Misbehaviour detection
Threat-10	Eavesdropping on communication between patient monitor and central system
OWASP threat(s)	M5, M6, M10
Safety Control	Ensure encryption of communications to protect sensitive data.
Security Control	Encrypt network communication using robust protocols (e.g., SSL/TLS).
Types of Evidence	Protection mechanisms of communication, Spoofing detection, Software-level safety concept, Production and operation concepts
Threat-11	Malware installed via USB access
OWASP threat(s)	M2, M8
Safety Control	Restrict physical USB access and secure boot processes.
Security Control	Restrict physical USB access, use secure boot mechanisms, and implement device whitelisting.
Types of Evidence	Hardware security mechanisms, Secure boot, Existence of ABAC mechanism, Hardware-level safety concept, Identification and evaluation of triggering events, Integrity risk, Protection level, Trusted Execution Environment
Threat-12	Manipulation of ventilator alarm messages sent to central system
OWASP threat(s)	M1, M3, M5
Safety Control	Use redundant systems to ensure alarms are always active.
Security Control	Secure communication channels; ensure redundancy in alarm systems.

Types of Evidence	Time to alert, Protection mechanisms of communication, System-level safety concept, Run-time operational assurance, Production and operation concepts
Threat-13	Manipulation of PACS network traffic to falsify medical images
OWASP threat(s)	M5, M9, M10
Safety Control	Apply real-time monitoring and secure data channels.
Security Control	Enforce network access controls; use traffic monitoring and tamper-proof data handling.
Types of Evidence	Misbehaviour detection, Existence of ABAC mechanism, Integrity risk, Spoofing detection, Intrusion detection system (IDS), Run-time operational assurance, Software-level safety concept
Threat-14	Ransomware attack encrypting PACS systems
OWASP threat(s)	M4, M10
Safety Control	Conduct regular backups and test recovery protocols.
Security Control	Implement firewalls, antivirus, backups, and conduct regular security awareness training.
Types of Evidence	Existence of ABAC mechanism, Reputation based system, Spoofing detection, Intrusion detection system (IDS), Validation and Verification
Threat-15	Exploitation of legacy third-party components
OWASP threat(s)	M2, M8
Safety Control	Patch vulnerabilities promptly and isolate legacy systems.
Security Control	Isolate legacy systems, enforce strict patch management, and conduct vulnerability assessments.
Types of Evidence	Known OS-vulnerabilities, Up-to-date OS/firmware, Authentic OS update, System-level safety concept, Hardware-level safety concept, Production and operation concepts
Threat-16	Malicious DICOM objects spreading malware across systems
OWASP threat(s)	M5
Safety Control	Implement whitelisting to block unauthorized operations.
Security Control	Harden systems; block execution of untrusted DICOM objects using whitelisting.
Types of Evidence	Protection mechanisms of communication, Protection level, Integrity risk, Hardware-level safety concept, Software-level safety concept
Threat-17	Ransomware causing shutdown of non-isolated systems
OWASP threat(s)	M4, M5
Safety Control	Enforce strict isolation protocols for compromised systems.
Security Control	Harden systems; block malware scanning on unvalidated devices.
Types of Evidence	Protection mechanisms of communication, Protection level, Integrity risk, Hardware-level safety concept, Software-level safety concept
Threat-18	Employee stealing data using USB storage
OWASP threat(s)	M2, M6
Safety Control	Conduct regular audits and restrict data access.
Security Control	Implement user and user group permissions; restrict unauthorized USB access.
Types of Evidence	Existence of ABAC mechanism, Protection mechanisms of communication, Reputation based system, Spoofing detection, Production and operation concepts, Validation and Verification, Trusted Execution Environment

Threat-19	Network-based malware leading to blue screen on devices
OWASP threat(s)	M3, M4, M5
Safety Control	Deploy backup systems and maintain alternative options.
Security Control	Use antivirus, robust network protection, and alternative devices.
Types of Evidence	System-level safety concept, Production and operation concepts, Validation and Verification, Run-time operational assurance, Known application-vulnerabilities
Threat-20	Unauthorized router configuration causing loss of connectivity
OWASP threat(s)	M1, M3, M5
Safety Control	Secure configuration interfaces and enforce access policies.
Security Control	Secure router management interface; enforce network access controls.
Types of Evidence	Existence of ABAC mechanism, Reputation based system, Spoofing detection, Intrusion detection system (IDS), Output latency
Threat-21	Compromised interventional systems due to worm or ransomware
OWASP threat(s)	M4, M5
Safety Control	Deploy hardened systems and enforce malware detection.
Security Control	Isolate systems and enforce strict malware scanning protocols.
Types of Evidence	System-level safety concept, Production and operation concepts, Validation and Verification, Run-time operational assurance, Known application-vulnerabilities
Threat-22	Contaminated system with reduced performance (e.g., slowed operations)
OWASP threat(s)	M8, M9
Safety Control	Ensure regular updates and monitor system performance.
Security Control	Conduct regular system updates and performance optimizations.
Types of Evidence	Run-time integrity check, Known OS-vulnerabilities, Up-to-date OS/firmware, Authentic OS update, Run-time operational assurance, Known application-vulnerabilities, Output latency, Time to alert
Threat-23	Use of outdated or unsupported third-party components
OWASP threat(s)	M2, M8
Safety Control	Avoid using unsupported components, enforce regular patching, and apply compensating controls such as network isolation.
Security Control	Isolate such components and apply compensating controls, such as network segmentation.
Types of Evidence	Known OS-vulnerabilities, Up-to-date OS/firmware, Authentic OS update, System-level safety concept
Threat-24	Unauthorized physical access to a device resulting in system configuration changes
OWASP threat(s)	M2, M8
Safety Control	Ensure secure device hardening
Security Control	Enforce physical security measures like badge authentication and monitoring.
Types of Evidence	Hardware security mechanisms, Hardware-level safety concept, Identification and evaluation of triggering events, Integrity risk, Trusted Execution Environment
Threat-25	Tampering with medical workflows or stored data
OWASP threat(s)	M9, M10

Safety Control	Implement integrity verification mechanisms (e.g., hashing), secure logging, and monitor workflows for tampering.
Security Control	Implement integrity verification mechanisms (e.g., hashing, secure logs).
Types of Evidence	Run-time integrity check, Run-time operational assurance, Functional modification to reduce SOTIF-related risks, Definition of SOTIF-related verification and validation, Misbehaviour detection, Spoofing detection, Intrusion detection system (IDS)
Threat-26	Lack of a structured incident response plan
OWASP threat(s)	M2
Safety Control	Develop and periodically test incident response plans, establish clear escalation protocols
Security Control	Develop and periodically test an incident response plan.
Types of Evidence	Identification and evaluation of triggering events, Functional modification to reduce SOTIF-related risks, Definition of SOTIF-related verification and validation strategy, Identification and evaluation of hazards caused by the intended function, Intrusion detection system (IDS), Production and operation concepts

Table 5.4: Mapping of Security and Safety Controls to Evidence

5.3 Threat landscape for Dynamic Trust Assessment in ECG Monitoring Portable Devices and Complex Stationary Devices in a Hospital Setting

The realistic threat scenarios, alongside with the relevant OWASP Top 10 Threats and Countermeasures provided by ENTRUST for the "TDynamic Trust Assessment in ECG Monitoring Portable Devices and Complex Stationary Devices in a Hospital Setting" Use-Case are in the following table:

Table 5.5: Threat Scenarios in Use-Case

Threat Scenarios	
	Compromising Low-End Devices During Runtime
Description	The KardinBLU ECG and multi-parameter monitoring system, which collects and transmits cardiological data as well as measurements from SpO2, temperature, and acceleration sensors, operates with constrained resources. These limitations make it particularly vulnerable to runtime attacks, as it may not support advanced security mechanisms such as intrusion detection systems (IDS) or robust cryptographic protocols. Attackers can exploit these vulnerabilities to compromise the integrity or functionality of the KardinBLU device, potentially disrupting the broader chain of medical services that rely on accurate data.
Threats	M2, M7, M8, M10
Countermeasures	ENTRUST leverages lightweight security solutions, such as PUF-based cryptographic protocols and TCB extensions, to provide effective protection for the KardinBLU device without overburdening its limited computational resources.
	Attacking and Hiding Malicious Activity in a Swarm of CMDs

Description	<p>In complex medical service chains, devices such as the KardinBLU ECG and multi-parameter monitoring systems often operate in swarms, collecting and transmitting various types of patient data (e.g., cardiological data, SpO2, temperature, and acceleration measurements). In environments such as operating rooms, where multiple KardinBLU devices are deployed simultaneously, an attacker could compromise a single KardinBLU device or one of its connected sensors. The attacker might then mimic the behavior of security functions, such as by forging security claims sent back to the backend system, to evade detection.</p> <p>For example, if there are 15 KardinBLU devices in a swarm and one device is compromised, the attacker could mimic the data sent by security functions and conceal malicious activity. This would allow the attacker to leak sensitive patient information without disrupting normal operations or triggering alarms. The threat in this scenario may not only be operational disruption but also data leakage, which poses a critical risk to patient privacy and data integrity.</p>
Threats	M2, M7, M8, M10
Countermeasures	ENTRUST employs swarm attestation mechanisms, which analyze the collective behavior of KardinBLU devices and their connected sensors to detect and isolate compromised units, ensuring the integrity of the medical service chain.

5.4 Threat landscape for Remote Patient Monitoring Intelligent System for Supporting Independent and Safe Living

The realistic threat scenarios, alongside with the relevant OWASP Top 10 Threats and Countermeasures provided by ENTRUST for the "Remote Patient Monitoring Intelligent System for Supporting Independent and Safe Living" Use-Case are in the following table:

Table 5.6: Threat Scenarios in Use-Case

Threat Scenarios	
	Improper Use of Credentials for Onboarding

Description	The secure onboarding of the Tellu Personal Health Gateway (PHG) or its connected CMDs into the service graph chain is essential for maintaining system integrity and safeguarding patient data. The PHG collects medical data from devices such as the KardinBLU and forwards it to the TelluCare cloud platform for medical processing. While the current onboarding process is functional and secure for most use cases, there is an opportunity to enhance its robustness by addressing potential vulnerabilities associated with traditional authentication methods, such as passwords, and pre-configured credentials. For example, improvements can be made in areas like Bluetooth pairing configurations and credential management to ensure the highest level of security against potential threats. Although there have been isolated attempts to target similar gateways in the industry through weak authentication practices, Tellu is proactively advancing its security strategies. Leveraging the innovative mechanisms developed within the ENTRUST framework, Tellu is implementing cutting-edge solutions to further strengthen the PHG’s security posture. These enhancements will help ensure seamless and secure onboarding while maintaining the integrity of patient data across the service graph chain.
Threats	M1, M2, M3, M6 M10
Countermeasures	ENTRUST enforces robust cryptographic protocols and secure credential management practices, including attestation mechanisms, to ensure that only authorized devices can be onboarded into the system.

5.5 Threat landscape for Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Wellbeing of Patients and Carers

5.5.1 Smart Ambulance

The realistic threat scenarios, alongside with the relevant OWASP Top 10 Threats and Countermeasures provided by ENTRUST for the "Smart Ambulance" Use-Case are in the following table:

Table 5.7: Threat Scenarios in Use-Case

Threat Scenarios	
	Detecting Novel Exploits Across the Entire Medical Service Graph Chain

Description	<p>In this scenario, the medical service graph chain involves multiple interconnected components, including sensors in ambulances (e.g., KardinBLU and Benevision N1), the PARTICLE Gateway, the PARTICLE Cloud Server, and hospital systems. Ensuring the secure transmission of data and the proper operation of devices in this chain is critical for patient safety.</p> <p>While traditional security measures like Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) and firewalls provide baseline protection, novel attack methods could bypass these safeguards by targeting less conventional aspects of the system. For instance, an attacker could manipulate network connectivity between the ambulance and hospital. Network quality is a key factor in routing patients to the most suitable healthcare institution. If an attacker degrades the network or falsifies connectivity metrics, they could mislead the system into sending patients to an inappropriate or poorly equipped hospital, endangering lives. Such attacks are subtle and may leave no traces in operational logs, focusing instead on subtle performance disruptions that evade traditional detection mechanisms.</p>
Threats	M4, M5
Countermeasure	<p>ENTRUST introduces dynamic trust assessment that evaluates the trust level of the system based on real-time evidence gathered from security extensions, integrity checks, and network characteristics. This capability enables the system to differentiate between legitimate network fluctuations and malicious degradation, ensuring accurate routing decisions for patient safety.</p>
Impersonation of Hospitals	
Description	<p>Hospitals within the medical service graph chain operate as distinct trust domains, each with its own specific trust requirements and security policies. Ambulances must be equipped to adapt dynamically to the trust models of different hospitals. For example, a hospital with weaker security infrastructure may demand stronger guarantees from the ambulance, such as additional data encryption or verified attestation, before accepting data. Conversely, hospitals with robust security systems may require less stringent measures.</p> <p>If an attacker successfully impersonates a hospital, they could manipulate the trust negotiation process, weakening the ambulance’s security guarantees and gaining unauthorized access to sensitive patient data. This scenario becomes particularly critical when sensitive information is transmitted during emergencies, as compromised data could impact patient care.</p>
Threats	M6
Countermeasure	<p>ENTRUST supports dynamic trust assessment across multiple models, ensuring that each hospital’s unique requirements are met without compromising security. By validating the trustworthiness of domains in real time, ENTRUST mitigates the risk of attackers impersonating legitimate entities in the chain.</p>
Secure Onboarding of Third-Party CMDs in Ambulances	

Description	<p>Ambulances in this use case are equipped with sensors such as the KardinBLU device and Benevision N1, which are integral to monitoring patient vitals. Over time, these devices may require replacement due to damage, wear and tear, or upgrades. The secure onboarding of new devices is essential to prevent misconfigured or compromised components from entering the system. If such devices are introduced, they could serve as attack vectors, jeopardizing the integrity of the service graph chain and compromising patient safety. This challenge is amplified in emergency scenarios, where time constraints make manual verification impractical. Without proper safeguards, attackers could exploit this process to onboard compromised devices, undermining the security and reliability of the connected smart ambulance system..</p>
Threats	M1, M10
Countermeasures	<p>ENTRUST enforces a secure onboarding process by verifying the configuration, authenticity, and security posture of new sensors before integration. This ensures that only compliant devices are permitted to join the service graph chain.</p>

5.5.2 Hospital environment

The realistic threat scenarios, alongside with the relevant OWASP Top 10 Threats and Countermeasures provided by ENTRUST for the "Hospital Environment" Use-Case are in the following table:

Table 5.8: Threat Scenarios in Use-Case

Threat Scenarios	
	Improper Software/Firmware Updates
Description	<p>Maintaining up-to-date software and firmware for connected medical devices (CMDs) is essential for mitigating vulnerabilities and ensuring reliable system operation. Legacy CMDs, such as the Econet Compact 7, are particularly vulnerable, as they often no longer receive manufacturer support or updates. In this use case, these devices are securely integrated into a hospital environment via the ENTRUST Gateway, which ensures safe data exchange between the legacy CMDs and the BMC Server.</p> <p>Updating the Gateway or related components, such as the Windows Update Server, requires careful handling to prevent potential risks. While updates are currently managed in a supervised manner, relying on the physical presence of an IT administrator at the hospital, this approach has inherent challenges. The process depends heavily on the technical expertise and knowledge of the administrator. A lack of expertise or errors during manual updates could inadvertently introduce new attack vectors or vulnerabilities into the system.</p> <p>Moreover, risks such as rollback attacks—where older, more vulnerable software versions are reintroduced—highlight the need for robust update mechanisms. To address these concerns, updates must be distributed over authenticated and secure channels to prevent interception or tampering. Additionally, central monitoring mechanisms, such as digital twins, can ensure consistency, verify the integrity of updates, and detect anomalies in the update process. These enhancements will provide additional layers of security while mitigating reliance on individual expertise during updates.</p>

Threats	M2, M3, M9
Countermeasures	ENTRUST employs strong cryptographic protocols, secure channels, and centralized monitoring through the digital twin infrastructure to ensure the integrity and security of software and firmware updates. Rollback prevention mechanisms ensure that updates follow a monotonic progression.

5.6 Compliant Protection of Wearable Devices for Mental Health Monitoring and Integrity of Accompanying Data

The realistic threat scenarios, alongside with the relevant OWASP Top 10 Threats and Countermeasures provided by ENTRUST for the "Compliant Protection of Wearable Devices for Mental Health Monitoring and Integrity of Accompanying Data" Use-Case are in the following table:

Table 5.9: Threat Scenarios in Use-Case

Threat Scenarios	
	Data Falsification
Description	<p>In this use case, wearable devices like the Feel Emotion Sensor (FES) collect sensitive medical data such as sweat levels, heartbeat, and skin temperature, which are critical for monitoring the mental health of patients. This data is transmitted to the patient’s mobile device via low-power protocols like Bluetooth (BLE). Although these protocols are energy-efficient and suitable for wearable devices, they have inherent vulnerabilities that can be exploited by malicious actors.</p> <p>One such threat is data falsification, where an attacker manipulates the sensor data in transit to alter vital signs or other health metrics. For instance, fabricated or altered data could mislead healthcare applications, causing incorrect analysis, inappropriate notifications, or delays in providing critical interventions. These attacks target the integrity of transmitted data, undermining trust in the system. Additionally, the resource constraints of low-power protocols make it difficult to implement traditional security measures, leaving the system exposed to sophisticated adversaries.</p>
Threats	M2, M5
Countermeasures	ENTRUST employs dynamic trust assessment that associates each piece of data with an ATL. This ATL provides a measure of confidence that the data source has not been compromised, ensuring the integrity and reliability of the information used in decision-making.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

In this deliverable, we provided a final, comprehensive reference architecture of the ENTRUST framework, including all core technical artefacts, components, and processes offered by ENTRUST, and by defining their positioning within the overall ENTRUST architecture and detailing their role in the establishment of the trustworthiness of CMDs operating within a medical domain infrastructure, but also of the system as a whole.

Specifically, the reference architecture documented in Chapter 2 included the latest versions of the components centered around the operation of the **Trust Assessment Framework** which were described in D3.2 [6], namely the **Formal Verification** component, the **Software Verification and Threat Modeling**, the **Protection Profiles** (device- and domain-level MUDs), the **Digital Twin** (including the **Secure Software Update** and **AI-based Misbehavior Detection** components), and their interaction with the **Risk Assessment** component for the calculation of the RTL of the CMD. The architecture also included information on the usage of the crypto and security enablers documented in D4.2 [7], specifically the **authentication**, **onboarding** and **enrolment** processes at the Pre-deployment phase, but also the attestation schemes (**CIV** and **Swarm Attestation**) to be executed during runtime, as well as the core crypto structures and primitives (**Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE)**, **Attribute-Based Signature (ABS)**, **Attribute-Based Credentials**, **Direct Anonymous Attestation (DAA)**). Finally, the action workflow included the Blockchain-related processes documented in D5.1 [8] pertaining to the auditability and certifiability of trustworthiness establishment processes.

In Chapter 3, we provided detailed action workflows for each individual technical artefacts of ENTRUST, focused on their interactions with other components and their role in the overall process of trust establishment. Specifically, these include the verification of the correctness of software processes with the **Software Verification** component, and the formulation of a unified, streamlined threat landscape for a CMD with the **Threat Modeling** components. The role of the **Formal Verification** component pertains to the verification of the correctness of the security processes of ENTRUST, considering the device- and domain-specific requirements and properties. The **Risk Assessment** component and **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)** are responsible for the calculation of the RTL and the ATL of the CMD, respectively, and the **Tracer** is responsible for the collection of the required attestation evidence to support the calculation of the ATL of the device. Finally, the **Digital Twin (DT)** and the **Anomaly Detection** component are able to receive such evidence for the identification of new threats and vulnerabilities, and the **Secure Software/Firmware Update** component goes through the DT in order to securely deploy patches and updates in response to security events, based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities.

Chapter 4 was focused on the provision of refined and comprehensive lists of requirements of the ENTRUST framework, split into **Framework Requirements**, **Security Requirements**, and **Operational Requirements**. These were based on the initial definition of requirements performed in D2.1, but was

also expanded to include refined descriptions and reasoning for their relevance to ENTRUST, as well as specific ENTRUST components that are able to fulfil each requirements, and correspondence with the KPIs through which the fulfilment of each requirement can be evaluated. In turn, the KPIs which were initially defined in D2.1 were expanded and refined, including concrete numerical values for their evaluation. Finally, Chapter 5 documented the threats targeting each use case demonstrator, focused on **practical, real-world situations that may be encountered by medical organizations**. For each of these, various types of information were provided, such as affected assets, potential impact, targeted assets, and vulnerabilities exploited, and the role of ENTRUST in their mitigation was described, thus highlighting the applicability of ENTRUST for providing trust assurance services to actual medical domain and healthcare provision organizations.

Overall, this deliverable constitutes a comprehensive document of all core offerings of ENTRUST, as well as their positioning within their overall framework, and their capability to detect, identify, and mitigate various types of threats and vulnerabilities affecting practical medical domain scenarios. The outcomes of this deliverable will provide the basis for the experimental activities and evaluation activities to be carried out and documented in D6.1, towards extracting conclusions on the performance of the ENTRUST artefacts and the definition of the next steps in the implementation and evaluation activities of ENTRUST.

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